
UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

Assessing the impact of social media to engage
modern consumers and to create brand awareness.

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Abstract:

The consumers' demands on the businesses grow as consumerism develops. In today's modern era, individuals expect more and more from the organisations, and they have become more cynical regarding the corporate sector as a whole and multinationals in particular. SMEs need to understand the apprehensions and concerns of customers to engage them in a much more proactive way with culture and its people. Social media has become increasingly important for consumers as well as for business corporations. Organisations has started using social media networks as a communication network to initiate direct dialogue with their customers and to spread their messages. The main purpose of the research is to assess and enhance the consumer engagement through social media channels and highlight the individuals' characteristics and businesses' social media activities that can help SMEs to create brand awareness.

This research examines the impact and the role of social media networks in customer engagement and analyse the different methods by which SMEs can create brand awareness through different social media activities. The study carries three main objectives. Firstly, it investigates the importance and effectiveness of social media channels on individuals' life in today's digital age. Secondly, this paper provides a detail understanding on consumer engagement and brand awareness. Furthermore, it reviews the individuals' characteristics regarding brands that can help SMEs to understand consumers' behaviour and explore opportunities for branding to reach their potential online consumers, and to engage them through social media activities. Thirdly, this research identifies the possible risks and threats regarding the brand image, and it also provides some suggestions and recommendations in the light of estimated findings, which can save a brand from possible threats and damages as well as to reach their potential consumers.

A quantitative approach is employed to collect the data via releasing an online survey. A well-known online survey tool, Survey Monkey is used to send the link for questionnaires survey through emails and different networks of social media (such as WhatsApp, Viber and Facebook). The descriptive and SPSS, multiple regression model based on different variable approach is employed to analyse the collected quantitative data. Moreover, the research first utilises the descriptive statistics to find percentage and frequencies associated with brand awareness for the expressive clarification of the results. Then, inferential statistics, multiple regression model is used on different variables through SPSS software.

The findings of the research deliver valuable implications for both academic as well as practice in the field of consumer engagement, social media, and the creation of brand awareness through online social platforms. The research findings explore many opportunities and provide essential implication for SMEs and international marketers to understand the behaviours, attitudes, and preferences of online consumers. The study results also facilitate marketers to select appropriate strategies for social media marketing to reach their potential customers to create brand awareness, and to keep them engaged with their brands.

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Declaration

In this thesis, no piece of work has been submitted to this or any other university or institute of learning in the support of an application of another degree or qualification. I declare that this research is my own work and original, and all other materials that are not my own are identified and referenced.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1. Research background:

Social media technology is increasing rapidly, and the behaviour of customer shopping is changing because of social media influence (Geissinger and Laurell, 2016). Social media networks are considered as hot platforms for organisations to create brand awareness and consumer engagement. According to Blazquez (2014), by engaging in a variety of social media marketing activities, fashion shoppers particularly can now access fashion brands and product information. Furthermore, customers are appeared to provide product feedbacks, create, and co-create value by generating in-depth content and interact with other customers and brands on social media networks (Laroche et al., 2012; Schivinski et al., 2016). Thus, it is essential for SME's and brands to recognise the better ways to engage modern consumers through social media activities as well to create a value that can influence individuals' purchase behaviours/intentions.

The concept of social media and blogging has been evolving since the turn of the century and received positive response by audience (Hussey, 2012). At first, platforms of social media were used as a network to communicate with family and friends and blogs were used to discuss personal issues to the community. But now businesses are using these channels to advance and enhance their communication to the consumers by exploring opportunities including mass outreach (Ta'eed, 2010); Chan, 2011). Social media offers its users an online network to communicate and share their experiences (Singh and Diamond, 2012). These social channels have appeared as a fast, convenient, and cost-efficient way for small-medium organisations to create brand awareness, modern consumer engagement and to reach its potential consumers worldwide. Consumer engagement represents the attachment of a consumer to its brand (Fierro et al., 2013). Social media channels are emerging and introducing better and new ways of communication between businesses and consumers that helps to determine customer behaviour (Verhoef et al., 2010).

Studies show that modern ways of social marketing are replacing traditional and old way of marketing (Ashley and Tuten, 2015). About a decade ago, it was quite difficult for SMEs to run a campaign and advertising to create brand awareness and consumer engagement due to high cost involved, but now social media advancement has transformed the way of communication and provides different methods to reach potential consumers to create brand awareness (Singh and Diamond, 2012). Furthermore, social media offers small-

medium companies' same opportunities as large companies to target their potential consumers worldwide with affordable budget, and these social platforms are extremely useful to develop strategies according to consumers' behaviour and trends. As noted by Rose et al., (2011), advanced marketing blogs tend to integrate with the leading social media platforms such as YouTube and Facebook and Instagram. Jett (2012) suggests that the main purpose of using social media and blog marketing is to increase widest consumer outreach and their engagement.

Several brands and organisations have adopted SNSs (social networking sites) as an effective tool for marketing communication to reach a large number of online communities and potential consumers (Ashley and Tuten, 2015, Felix et al., 2017, Mayshak et al., 2017 and Dimitriu and Guesalaga, 2017). In today's modern world, it is widely accepted that microblogs can generate positive effects for an organisation or brand by spreading brand popularity, to reach out and attracting more potential consumers, enhancing customers' brand awareness, sustaining, and improving customer relationship and brand loyalty (Wei et al., 2015). Brands can utilise the social media channels to understand consumers behaviour by analysing the individuals' conversation and their engaging activities (Schweidel and Moe, 2014). Thus, it is essential to provide an effective and practical strategies to attract consumers and keep them engaged (Lei et al., 2017; Claffey and Brady, 2017).

Brands and customer interactions on the networks of social media has attracted several marketing researchers who interest on the fashion context. Social media network strategies that involve interactions, word-of-mouth, customisation, and entertainment are more likely to enhance the level of customer interaction with luxury fashion brands on social media sites (Kim and Ko, 2012; Godey et al., 2016). However, researchers argue that fast fashion aims to offer the latest trending goods at affordable prices to its consumers, and it is different from luxury fashion (Sheridan et al., (2006). Similarly, Gabrielli et al., (2013) also agreed with this statement by adding that fast fashion characteristics allow modern consumers to express their individuals' lifestyles and fashion attitudes. Moreover, Ashley and Tuten (2015) demonstrate that social media network sites provide convenient virtual platforms that enable fast fashion brands to product latest and trendy contents as compared to other traditional marketing ways.

Constantinides (2014) illustrates, customers are playing a new social role in the contemporary fashion world as the value co-creators through communicating and

interacting with the brands. Zhang et al., (2016) state that brands have lost their ability to control and limit their customer's power. To Sum up, this study is based on three research areas: the impact of social media in today's modern world, to review the individual characteristics in terms of brands to find out the way SME's can create brand awareness and keep them engaged, and finally to come up with some recommendation and suggestions in the light of findings to prevent from damages while using social media network sites.

1.2. Research problem

Despite a number of advantages of social media and blogs in the marketing mix, it has appeared that there is not much empirical research has been undertaken to determine the role of social media platform in consumer engagement and brand awareness (Linn and Huang, 2006). There are gaps in this research that identify the way in which social media can be used to engage modern consumers and to create brand awareness. It can be seen from previous studies on social media that in general that it tended to emphasis more towards consumer engagement through social media rather than narrowing down to particular social media type (Kumar et al., 2010).

Ahuja and Medury (2010) demonstrate that small medium enterprises have been ignored when empirical research focused on particularly consumer engagement through social channels. To date, SME's have proven amongst the most important drivers of economic growth (Brodie et al., 2011). Hence, empirical research of consumer engagement through social media channels could be very useful for SME's (Lee et al., 2006). The role played by different kinds of social media in the marketing mix has grown ever important over the years (Gummerus *et al.*, 2012). Generally, social media platforms have revolutionized the marketplace by significantly changing the way customers (consumers of products) and sellers interact (Vivek *et al.*, 2012). Since interaction between buyers and sellers is paramount for effective business, it follows that social media have enhanced the buyer-seller relationship (Lee *et al.*, 2006). There are gaps in study on how marketers use blogs to revolutionize marketing strategies.

Among all kinds of social media, blogs have emerged as among those which find widespread used both among buyers and sellers of products (Luck and Ginanti, 2013). Today, it is not uncommon for potential buyers of products to visit general or specific blogs

to search for information about products or to make purchases (Scott, 2009). Just like other forms of social media, blogs have not only become acceptable as part and parcel of the marketing mix but have also become crucial part in the process of marketing (Ahuja and Medury, 2010). There are gaps in studies to show how Marketers can integrate blogs with other social media platforms to maximize outreach.

Among other functions, blogs have proven useful and, in some cases, vital when it comes to important functions such as communication, distribution of products, market research, management, and promotion (Bijmolt *et al.*, 2010). In large extent, it is the way blogs affect these important functions that makes them important in marketing in general and customer engagement in particular (Schmallegger and Carson, 2008). Through social media channels and blogs, not only are firms that sell different products able to better engage their target and existing customers, but consumers are also able to interact among themselves and determine which products are available in the market (Sashi, 2012). Furthermore, social media blogs have put effort to make it a lot easier for consumers to gain understanding of the different sellers who offer different products in the market (Van *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, the information about products in general and their providers in particular has become more easily and readily available through blogs (Brodie *et al.*, 2011). A research gap has found that requires the investigator to concentrate more on the consumers' perspective to understand the attitude and behaviour of customer engagement with respect to several social media marketing activities on the social media platforms.

1.3. Significance:

The study main aim is to develop a professional case for SMEs and brands to find out the effective use of social media platforms to create brand awareness and to engage modern consumers. Modern consumers means today's consumers who are more connected with social media and other online sites than ever before. They use these online sites to follow trends, look for products, review products, check and compare the prices, share their purchase experiences, request vouchers/coupons and to purchase the products and services. The consumer behaviour has changed substantially over the last few years due to development of number of technologies, and organisations are focusing on new opportunities and possibilities for fulfilling consumer's needs. Smart phone is undoubtedly the most important driver here who has empowered the consumer to shop in many different ways, and it also offers a number of opportunities for companies.

This research is important due to the empirical information regarding the place and role of social media and blogs in consumer engagement for small-medium organisations. Research have proved that social media can assist brand marketing such as promotions and other products information including prices, offers and specifications (Jett, 2012). But critics argued that this is only possible with the selection of right social media channel for the right purpose.

Moreover, the current diversity of people of shopping online, reading the reviews online and sharing on social media attracts brands for online presence. It helps SMEs to follow the latest trends and consumers purchasing behaviour. It is widely accepted, although SMEs often get enough customers, but they failed to engage them with their brand. This study will highlight that how SMEs managers can engage consumers in a professional manner through social media and blogs as diversity to the conventional advertisement strategies.

There are different types of SMEs that naturally benefit from social media marketing such as fashion and beauty, entertainment, lifestyle and travel, health and fitness, real estate, education, recruitment, retail and restaurants. Offline businesses can also attract customers to their stores through social media marketing by creating their product/service awareness among consumers. In addition, most of businesses are trying to provide their services online such as funeral services, as statistics show that online funeral plan searches are increasing year on year, and online funeral plan sales were 60,145 in 2005 increasing to 207,700 in 2017 (Gerry King, 2019).

1.4. Rationale:

This research field has a surprising gap particularly when it has been appeared that small organisations could get more traffic to their stores and websites than large organisations through effective use of social media campaigns (Bhanot, 2012). Furthermore, scholars have asked to add more knowledge and research in this field by pointing out, “Scholars should profile the most important aspects of social media that affect SMEs” (Jagongo and Kinyua, 2013). Hence, the study will explore the impact and most important factors of social media and blogs by which SMEs can get better consumer engagement in a professional manner and examine the effective use of social media in branding in today’s modern world. The research will also highlight, whether and how satisfied and unsatisfied customers can affect on companies’ reputation and brand image.

1.5. Research questions and objectives:

Research Objectives	Research Questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ To determine the impact of social media on customer engagement and brand awareness in today's modern world. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ How does social media influence today's world? ➤ How do social media sites impact on individual's lives in terms of consumer engagement and brand awareness?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ To review the individual characteristics in terms of brands, which helps SMEs to reach their potential consumers and engage them through social media. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ How social media can help SMEs to engage modern consumers? ➤ How can SMEs create brand awareness through social media networks?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ To provide some recommendations and suggestions in the light of estimated findings, that can save a brand from unexpected damages and threats and help them to reach their potential customers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ What are the possible risks and threats towards a brand image? ➤ What policy should be implemented through social media towards brand image in connection with potential customers?

1.6. Contribution:

Social media is one of the hottest topics that is discussed every day in these days. Consumers use multiple social media channels to communicate with each other on the daily basis. Even organisations have recognised social media advantages regarding communication with consumers to initiate direct dialogues with targeted group of individuals, and organisations are appeared using different social media activities as a part of their marketing campaigns to deliver their brand messages to a large audience and keep them engage with their brands. Gummesson (2002) states that SMEs can establish positive association and communication between the consumers and a brand through a suitable social media platform.

This study will contribute to the body of knowledge of social media literature, branding and consumer engagement. As mentioned above that SMEs appeared to attract enough customers but failed to engage them with their brand, which is not in favour of long term run relationship for a business. So, I believe that findings of the research will help the SMEs to create brand awareness and better consumer engagement in a professional way through the effective use of online networking sites of social media and blogs.

1.7. Structure of thesis:

The research consists of 7 chapters. The first chapter starts with an introduction that involves research background, research motivation, the main aim of the study and its objectives. This chapter also highlights research problem, significance, rationale, and its contribution. Chapter 2 highlights the review of the literature of the impact of social media in terms to engage modern consumers and to create brand awareness. It also provides a brief description on the concept of social media marketing and its application in the fashion brand context. A research gap is found based on this review that requires the investigator to concentrate more on the consumers' prospective to understand the attitude and behaviour of customer engagement with respect to several social media marketing activities on the social media networks.

Chapter 3 reviews the different research paradigms, research philosophies and research methods, and discusses the chosen method that applied in this research. Analysis and discussion of different research philosophical stances (including epistemology, axiology,

and otology) and the major philosophical paradigms (including pragmatism, interpretivism, constructivism and positivism) helped the researcher to design an appropriate the research method to address the required research questions and objectives (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017). This chapter also highlights the data collection process and the data analysis methods precisely. Chapter 4 describes the findings of the quantitative research method in form of descriptive and inferential statistics. Further, the chapter 5 reviews and integrates the research findings towards the quantitative study and the literature review and presents the comprehensive discussion based on each research objectives.

Chapter 6 represents a conclusion of the current research and illustrates its contributions towards overall literature, knowledge, methodology and the practice, and also outlines the recommendations for SMEs and brands to reach out its potential customers to create brand awareness and provides some suggestions in the light of estimated findings of the current study which may save SMEs and brands from expected damages.

Chapter 2: Literature Review:

2.1 Introduction:

This chapter aims to gain a detail understanding of the concept of consumer engagement, the role and the impact of the social media, social media marketing activities and its application in creating brand awareness. First, this chapter is going to review then general concept of consumer engagement. Consumer engagement refers as unidimensional concept and consumer behaviour towards a brand (Brodie et al., 2011). Second, it will highlight the importance and the impact of social media in today's modern world. It will review the social media marketing concept and its application to promote services or products, to enhance consumer relationships and to facilitate consumer communicational activities. Marketing communication is considered as an essential dimension for social media marketing because, it provides opportunities to a brand to interact with its consumers on a personal level (Nair and Subramaniam, 2012). Beyond demonstrating social media marketing definition, this chapter will further highlight the effective ways for brands to facilitate customer communicational activities and to maintain public relations in contrast with marketing strategies applied through traditional ways (Castronovo and Huang, 2012).

Third, the next section (Section 2.11) will further explore marketing activities through social networks to create brand awareness. The term brand awareness represents the level of customer acceptance, recognition and a recall of a brand (Perreault et al., 2013). Furthermore, the next sections will explain the brand building activities, challenges for online branding, risks and threats for brands due to social media online presence.

2.2 Consumer engagement:

Consumer engagement is considered as an essential element and plays an integral part in a business performance. Several scholars and researchers have tried to identify the characteristics to engage consumers (Tripathi, 2009; Sashi, 2012). It has seen that SMEs usually ignore and are not aware of the importance of customer engagement (Carter, 2008). Therefore, such organisations can be seen struggling to perform long term and to attach their customer with their brands. According to Dutot (2013), businesses should not only show their interest to gain market shares, but they also need to engage customers to their brands to perform long term. In general, customer engagement represents the behaviour of a customer towards brand (MSI, 2010). Furthermore, Fierro et al., (2013) state, "such

customer engagement comprises of transactional and non-transactional processes, which are defined by loyalty and purchase intention or brand commitment, such as blogging and word of mouth”.

Brodie et al., (2011) denotes consumer engagement as a unidimensional concept and consumer behaviour is a dominant component nevertheless, Van Doorn et al., (2010) demonstrate that attitudinal antecedents are more important factors that impact on the customer engagement. There are following elements that are considered to have a great impact and enhance consumer engagement.

2.2.1 Consumer intelligence:

Consumers are one of the most important stakeholders for organisations. It is seemed that successful corporations always listen carefully to their consumers and individuals who have interest in their businesses. For instance, Dell and BMW encourage their customers to provide them new ideas and opinions to invent new and innovative products to fulfil their needs. It is because, by involving consumers in these kinds of activities keep them engage with their brand, and some creative customers could also provide some innovative and useful information and ideas. Nevertheless, due to lack of control over customers, they could appear as a threat to company as well (Cheung, Lee and Thadani, 2009).

2.2.2 Branding:

Brand refers as a company’s personality. As noted by Ashton (2009), brand of a company shows its reputation, behaviour and it indicates what individuals presume and think about the organisation. Customer’s satisfaction is a psychological communication for enterprises, which is extremely useful to engage consumers with the brand (Tripathi, 2009). Gambetti et al., (2012) demonstrate that businesses are appeared using consumer brand engagement as branding strategy due to its high impact on customer to make decision and brand equity.

A business must be able to communicate his identity to the marketplace otherwise even a solid and successful brand platform will be considered as useless. Martenson (2008) illustrates that sometimes organisations have appeared underestimating the importance of being visible and present on these online social marketplaces. A proper visibility of a brand usually linked with success, great leadership, energy and quality. An appropriate presence of a brand in a marketplace always develops and strengthens the identity of the brand. Therefore, all the communication activities reflect the core of the company and can affect

the company brand image.

The employees (people in the organisation) are the great asset for any business and their knowledge regards to the brand values play an important role in communication and developing relationship with their consumers. An employee who truly recognize the importance of the brand value, can translate into visible behaviour and impression while communicating with customers. According to Martenson (2008), these employees are considered as brand ambassadors if they speak, think and act in a way that develop a positive customer experience to increase brand image and reputation.

2.2.3 Customer satisfaction:

Satisfaction is considered one of the most general and popular explanation that represents consumer loyalty and healthy relationship. Studies have suggested that “very satisfied” customers from the purchase are more loyal than just “satisfied”. There are various types and degrees of satisfaction, different level of measurements and individual differences in how satisfied a consumer gets in different contexts. Satisfaction can be split up into two different types that are social and economic satisfaction (Geyskens and Steenkamp, 2000; Evan et al., 2008). Furthermore, according to Geyskens and Steenkamps (2000), these both types economic and social do not correlate just like loyalty and satisfaction, but all types of satisfaction lead to loyalty. Nevertheless, Soderlund (2001) points out that there are dissatisfied consumers who are loyal due to lack of other options or brand engagement, and there are satisfied consumers who are not loyal to brand.

2.2.4 Trust:

The consumer demands on businesses grow as consumerism develops. In today’s modern world, customers are expecting more and more from the organisations, and they have become cynical about the corporate sector as a whole and particularly multinationals. Companies are required to engage with the society and individuals in a much more proactive way. In addition, they need to act this way not due to ethical reasons, they should do this because it makes better business sense, and this will help to become a “citizen brand”. Numerous scandals of organisations in recent years have raised the trust issues among customers which creates a critical situation to the business environment (Martenson, 2008). As more brands are emerging in the market, it has become difficult for businesses

in a saturated market to differentiate their product or service, and even more difficult to reach towards their potential consumers through the constant noise of messages from various brands. Thus, the brands are required to work hard to be known as believable and trustworthy associates.

To maintain a mutual and favorable relationship, trust is considered as a common interest. In this social relationship, parties from both sides depend on another. In this situation if one party acts deceitfully without others' consideration then it can result in a relationship termination. A successful and strong brand always try to develop strong and long-term relationship with its consumers, that's why businesses comfortably invest in brand development (So, et al., 2016). Relationship between both parties works naturally better due to reciprocal dependence (Martenson, 2007). It seems very simple to build trust in theory, nevertheless it has appeared to be very difficult in practice. According to Fournier and Avery (2011), the common mistake that businesses make, that they forget that there are two parties involve in social relationship. A business asks for friendship, respect and loyalty, and it lose the trust at the same moment when he fails to perform on these areas. They also added that it is essential for organisations to treat their customer as allies and send them relevant offers adjusted to each individual rather than sending mass advertising to each customer (Fournier and Avery, 2011). Overall, It has seen that supplier is the one who often benefits from the relationship (Soderlund, 2001).

2.2.5 Loyalty:

Loyalty involves several psychological factors that affect consumers to make a decision and brand preference (Vivek et al., 2012). Engagement and satisfaction with the brand are those psychological factors that effect on purchasing behaviour. Organisations are becoming much more aware of the advantages of having a loyal customer base. According to Soderlund (2002), the major argument for investments in increased customer loyalty is because it helps to increase the profitability of a business. Furthermore, it is believed that maintaining an established customer is less expensive for a business as compared to gaining a new customer. As per noted by Martenson (2007), increased loyalty has been appeared to create barriers for new businesses, which serve as a base for price premium and also helps to protect the business in price wars. Therefore, Evans et al., (2008) point out that many organisations are trying different ways to engage in relationship related activities to gain consumer loyalty.

Loyalty can be described as individuals' wish based relationship for a specific object over time that can be viewed at through distinct worlds (Soderlund, 2001). A customer attitude and his behaviour show his loyalty towards a brand or organisation. For instance, common measurements can be how long he/she has been a customer for a certain brand, how frequent an individual shops and the percentage of his total expenses to a specific brand or company (Soderlund, 2001). In other words, customer's loyalty behaviour can be easily measure through actual data and purchase transactions.

2.2.6 Word of mouth (WOM):

Word of mouth (WOM) has recognised widely as a form of information which directly impacts the way consumers think, the way they feel and their behaving pattern (Groeger and Buttle, 2014). Word of mouth has proved as one of the most effective engagement, because it also involves customer to customer interaction rather than just communication between the business and customer. Electronic word-of-mouth marketing regarding social media context has emerged a great deal of interest in this new media age (Chu and Sung, 2015). Word of mouth is identified as an essential social media marketing activity that SMEs want to facilitate among their consumers (Halvorsen et al., 2013; Kim and Ko, 2012). As Thureau et al., (2004) demonstrate that by sharing experiences with their family and friends, existing satisfied customers can bring new potential customers. It is widely believed that through word of mouth, one customer on social platforms can share his experience with more than 10 million people, and on the other hand in a physical world, an individual can share his experience with 10 people (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). But word of mouth could bring threats as well and can easily damage the brand reputation as it depends upon the shared information that can be in favour or against the brand (Cheung et al., 2009).

2.3 Different models for customer engagement:

Several scholars and researchers such as Bowden (2009), Ahuja & Medury (2010), Brodie et al., (2011) and Gummerus et al., (2012) have shown interest in consumer management models. In today's world, modern consumers can be engaged through social media channels and brands' blogs which are integrated with electronic consumer relationship websites (Ahuja and Medury, 2010). They also demonstrate that these strategies help organisations to understand consumer's behaviour and trend and to gather more data. Nevertheless, social media blogs are more business centred, which may downfalls the

consumer engagement purpose, therefore, it is very essential to choose an appropriate design for these strategies (Bijmolt et al., 2010).

An ideal model of consumer engagement needs to be dynamic and multidimensional, which can enhance satisfaction with products, services, loyalty, trust and also able to manage self-brand performance's outcomes. As noted by Escalas (2004), it is very essential to have self-brand linkage with buyers for customer engagement in terms to associate and express themselves according to needs satisfaction. Subsequently, customers tend to maintain loyalty as a result of their change in continuous behaviour to buy more products (Park et al., 2007). According to Becker-Olsen and Hill (2006), successful models of consumer engagement are appeared characterised by formation of brand communities self-identities. There are large gaps and is yet to identify the appropriate ways to improve brand identities and linkage towards modern consumers.

A successful model of consumer engagement shows the buyers repurchase of products or services that represents their loyalty towards a company or brand (Naumann and Bowden, 2015). Van Dorn et al., (2010) agreed with above statement by adding that these models are enough to survive in a competitive environment.

Figure 1 shows the engagement model that was proposed by Naumanna and Bowden (2015).

Figure 1: Customer Engagement Model (Naumann & Bowden, 2015).

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Engaging modern customers required unique and new style of marketing activities as compared to old times with traditional marketing due to heavily usage of social media platforms (Brodie et al., 2013). This statement is well supported by Hollebeek et al., (2014) who added, from the turn of the century, the innovation of social media platforms has a conspicuous effect on consumer engagement. Different social media platforms attract and assist the consumers differently to engage them with their brand or corporation and deliver their needs (Sashi, 2012). According to Harrigan and Choudhury (2010), effective customer engagement require room for communication, brand community's establishment, administrative roles and access through technologies. Hoyer et al., (2010) added that social media entry has provided many strategies with endless opportunities for nurturing consumer engagement.

Brodie et al., (2013) proposed different dimensions of theoretical framework of customer engagement. As Van Bruggen et al., (2010) demonstrate, it is extremely essential for sellers to communicate the advantages of products and services with customers to convince them to make purchases to enhance consumer engagement. As noted by Harrigan and Choudhury (2010), customer engagement's social benefits must need to be clear from the preferred communication plan to enhance the branding process, where the association is worth the promises. There are several factors regards to customers, that are required critical consideration while designing customer engagement (Brodie et al., 2013). Customers online privacy is very important, particularly when e-commerce transaction require proof of identity and address for a successful payment (Shashi, 2012).

A chain of smooth communication networks is the core competence of customer engagement (Brodie et al., 2013). Due to entry of different mobile devices and apps, more consumers are willing to engage with companies via social media (Harrigan-Thurau et al., 2010), Hence, a firm is required to adopt a policy with multiple online channels of communication on consumer engagement. There is research gap that which social media channel is reliable and whether SME's blogs and social networks are reliable communication networks for a long-term relationship.

There are three major outcomes from Brodie et al., (2013) model. The first outcome is trust, the model assumes that consumer's trust on the brand is a key of successful purchase. Trust is an essential element particularly in e-commerce, and it has received a lot of attention

among researchers over the last few years that emphasize its importance. Several gaps are appeared in this research to illustrate how SME's can build trust on brands of consumers through social media channels, and how to stop false and negative product information. Second outcome of the model is commitment (Brodie et al., 2013). As per noted by Van Bruggen et al., (2010), a successful engagement process required a stronger commitment to the brand. The third and the last outcome of the model is loyalty that every business should offer on product for the purposes of sustainable business establishment (Hoyer et al., 2010).

Figure 2: Customer Engagement Model (Brodie et al., 2013).

Verhoef, et al., (2010) offered a model for customer engagement from the perspectives of global researchers. First, the researchers coincide with Bijmolt et al., (2010) and Hennig-Thurau et al. (2010) that organizations require strategies for engaging with their customers from market led intelligence combined via different channels and social media. Second, Verhoef, et al., (2010) back the ideas of Van Bruggen et al., (2010) that models of customer engagement should have C2C connections, where product and service information flow freely in case by word of mouth or online. In this case, the customers' experiences repeat

the story about the product and services from the micro-blogs (Libai *et al.*, 2010). Third, Verhoef, *et al.*, (2010), back the views of van Doorn et al (2010) that customer engagement strategies should consider their characteristics, organizations goals, business competitors and economic times. There are not enough studies to indicate whether SMEs use blogs for client commitment can extend the item attributes, exhibit the firms' objectives in tackling issues, show the one of a unique seller recommendation from substitutes and are reasonable as per economic times.

Fourth, Verhoef, *et al.*, (2010) agree with Hoyer *et al.*, (2010) view that consumer engagement strategy must combine all marketing performance measures, customer choices, loyalty, brand equity and give space for new product development. This will ultimately increase the firm's value in the marketplace (Kumar *et al.*, 2010). There are gaps in studies to exhibit whether SMEs use blogs for customer engagement can acquire the firms needs using surveys or other ways, maintains their loyalty to a given product or brand and promises continuous quality improvement. The following figure 3 illustrates the customer engagement model as proposed by Verhoef *et al.*, (2010).

Figure 3: Customer engagement Model Source: (Verhoef *et al.*, 2010).

According to Alexander & Jaakkola (2015), an effective customer engagement model should have four stages. First, the customer engagement model should bring co-developing

behaviour (Carbonell *et al.*, 2009). This will allow the target customers to limit products that address specific needs and guarantee value for money (Edvardsson *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, the model should provide some social benefits to the customers who are fascinated by the brand (Nambisan & Baron, 2009). Choice of a client engagement model that grasps co-creating conduct is beneficial to the firm for anticipating future needs (Füller, 2010). Therefore, firms can take some appropriate steps for developments to guarantee they remain in front of rivalry (Hoyer *et al.*, 2010). However, firms must devote satisfactory assets to guarantee this objective is attainable (von Hippel, 2005). To the remainder of stakeholders, centre around co-creating conduct will guarantee the item offering is helpful to the clients (Carbonell *et al.*, 2009). There are gaps in the research to affirm how SMEs use blogs for customers engagement fuses co-advancement conduct of their buyers.

Second, as indicated by Alexander and Jaakkola (2015), a compelling client engagement model ought to have limit of affecting the buyers conduct. The desire to the objective clients is to offer reward for their loyalty as much as the vender to be rebuffed each time they fall short of the customer expected encounters (Libai *et al.*, 2010). Capacity to impact the client conduct exhibits that the dealer is a specialist in the item or services, thus, trust will assemble. Furthermore, the clients hope to sustain some social pride if the commitment is effective in affecting their buy conduct (Harris and Harrigan, 2011). To the remainder of the stakeholders, customer engagement at the behaviour influence stage should eliminate bad experiences and risks to the buyers avoiding purchase (Adjei *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, the adequate information must be provided to the stakeholders about the product, while facilitate them to make informed choices according to their expectations (Blazevic *et al.*, 2013).

Third, according to Alexander & Jaakkola (2015), customer engagement strategies should be able to strengthen the behaviour at different levels. The engagement strategy needs to align with consumers' attitudes and their special needs (Seraj, 2012), and understanding of the social benefits should be accomplished in a collective manner (sussan, 2012). This process covers the social features of the product, intellectual rights and cultural ideas while the customers are communicating between themselves (Ferrell & Ferrell, 2012). With respect to value of the firm, customer engagement methodologies sending increasing behaviour should feature the most squeezing needs at that point direct consideration regarding what is most important (Sawhney *et al.*, 2005). This process is accomplished when the firm has close relationship with the customers (Dholakia *et al.*, 2009). To the remainder of stakeholders, there is need to enhance their behaviour with remarkable products that

stand out from crowded competition (Von Hippel, 2005). Marketers are required to find ways by which SMEs can use blogs for customer engagement to improve their behaviour for strong relationship with the products or brands.

Fourth, according to Alexander & Jaakkola (2015), customer engagement strategy should be able to mobilize the behaviour of buyers by enhancing their decision process. This requires the firm to concentrating on items that clients need most after primer investigations or different methods for correspondence (Paek & Nelson, 2009). The firms should be able to organise critical mass of buyers who feel valued for their role in the business for maintaining high sales (Harris & Harrigan, 2011). The rest of the stakeholders are required to change in their behaviour in creating a long-lasting brand and guarantee all benefit from their input (Adamson & Lynch, 2013). Marketers can use blogs for customer engagement, spreading their product information and in mobilizing their conduct to continuous brand development. The following figure 4 illustrates the Alexander & Jaakkola, (2015) model for customer engagement.

Figure 4: Model of Customer Engagement (Alexander & Jaakkola, 2015, p. 13).

Progressive studies by Hollebeek (2011a, 2011b) and Hollebeek et al. (2014) on the models of customer engagement built up those intellectual, passionate and behavioural dimensions were the most investigated dimensions by the investigators.

Proof on the pervasiveness of psychological dimensions on customer engagement has been referred to when firms are displaying brands to consumers on the web (Patterson et al. 2006). Consequently, the consumer can assess the branded product and plan mentally on the potential results in the wake of accomplishing the functional targets (Abdul et al., 2011). There is uncertain research how SMEs can accomplish solid intellectual dimension inside their client engagement techniques, for example, blogging. In addition, passionate components of customer engagement are perceived by the purchasers' responses and association with the brand (Hollebeek, 2011a). Passionate elements of could be a cognizant or oblivious procedure as many buyers respond to their sentiments about the data or experiences of the branded product (Hollebeek et al., 2014). The conduct measurements prompt the buyers to act with the positive encounters prompting loyalty or referrals to others (Hollebeek et al., 2014).

2.4 Social media:

The term social media can be described as “Internet-based, disentrained, and persistent channels of mass personal communication facilitating perceptions of interactions among users, deriving value primarily from user-generated content” (Carr and Hayes, 2015, p. 49). Social media is considered as an online environment that attracts individuals with common interests come together to share their ideas, comments and thoughts (Weber, 2007). It refers as a technology that is developing with the pace of time (Kane et al., 2014). Social media is a type of electronic communication, used by group of people and individuals to communication with each other and share their views and ideas. It offers a channel for its users to communicate with one another and exchange information (Singh and Diamond, 2012). These sites and channels allow corporations to share information and explore the interest and experience with existing customers and new customers that build trust and healthy relationship (Badea, 2014).

As noted by Nielsen (2011), enterprises are seen investing increasingly to build their social media platforms to develop brand awareness through social media wide approach and viral contents. The computer giant Dell monitors almost 1500 blogs a day through social media to engage with its consumers. Similarly, several multi-national organisations such as Geico, Old Spice and P&G already changed to smart way of marketing from old and costly traditional way by sharing videos and promotions through social media channels (Kotler and Armstrong, 2007). As noted by Kietzman et al., (2011), social media has six key categories in terms of functionality as shown below in figure 5.

1	Platform to share video contents such as youtube
2	Platform for general masses such as Facebook
3	Micro blogging such as Twitter
4	Social news and bookmarking
5	Creating and maintaing blogs
6	Channel to develop professional network such as LinkedIn

Figure 5: social media categories in terms of functionality (Kietzman et al., 2011).

Social media has very powerful and huge impact on individual's life in today's world, and it proved to be a game changer in almost everything around us. Customer targeting of prospective customers is easier than ever before due to birth of social media platforms. Generally, social media is one of the greatest innovations of technology that not only give individuals ability to communicate with others but also offers businesses to market those directly they want to target. Currently, Facebook has approximately 2.1 billion active users monthly (Statista, 2018) as shown in the below figure 6.

Figure 6: Most popular social media networks (Statista, 2018).

It has appeared that due to rise in digital technology, people spend half of their time on online activities (such as You Tube, Facebook, Twitter etc.), emails and others social communication activities (Riegner, 2007). It is widely believed that social channels are the future destination for communication with one another. Furthermore, Burmaster (2009) points out that these social channels provide opportunities for organisation to monitor individuals' new trends, interests and their purchasing behaviour. People have been seen giving a lot of consideration on the feedbacks and reviews that are shared online (Weiss et al., (2008).

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2.4.1 Facebook

Facebook was launched in 2004, this network site has over a billion users who use Facebook daily and it has approximately 1.65 billion active users, in which most of them access Facebook through mobile phone (Facebook, 2016). Facebook is considered as the most popular social network sites. It provides a platform to individuals to connect with friends, family members and other individuals, and offers opportunity to users to post and share contents such as status updates, photos and videos (Stec, 2015). According to the company's websites, "Facebooks' mission is to give people the power to share and make the world more open and connected" (Facebook, 2016). As per noted by Duggan (2015), online users who have a Facebook account are about three quarters, and 7 in 10 users are reported using the platform every day, which shows the habitual and ritualized nature of Facebook use. It has appeared that 87% of Facebook users are the young adults 18-29 years old (Duggan et al., 2015).

Facebook is considered as an essential and powerful marketing tool for businesses. According to Vaidhyathan (2018), the U.S. presidential election of year 2016 observed the start of two years of Facebook negative coverage. However, the site did not see any decline in its vast business partners, nor in its monthly active user. Indeed, several businesses have aligned their business model and integrated their technology with Facebook over the past decade. Data shows that Facebook has over 6 million active advertiser and hosted over 90 million businesses by the end of 2018 (FIR, 2018). Facebook offers more than 70 languages of its users. The main purpose of this site is to develop communication between friends and family and establish and maintain relationship regarding work related situation and political affiliations. Currently, Facebook is considered a direct competitor of Google in online promotions and advertising.

2.4.2 Twitter:

Twitter is categorized as a microblogging site and was launched by Jack Dorsey in March 2006. Twitter allows people to interact in real time by using 140-character tweets to other people, and through using replies, mentions and hashtags, users can converse (Stec, 2015). Although, Fiegerman (2016) states that reports indicate the importance and popularity has declined of Twitter amid diminishing investment, nevertheless, reports suggest that there are no major changes appeared in the percentage of adult active Twitter account users (Tsukayama, 2016; Duggan, 2015).

In contrast with Facebook, where users can share various contents such as images and video, users can connect to latest information with Twitter on what they interesting. Users are required to find a public stream on their interest and follow in the conversation. SMEs can share latest

news and product information faster to a large audience through Twitter. Furthermore, from a strategic perspective, this can help SMEs (that uses Twitter) positioning their brands, and also able to gather business insight via consumer feedback to boost market intelligence in order to target consumers accurately with relative products and services and improve business relations. Studies point out that Twitter has helped many SMEs in enhancing relationship marketing, lifting brands, and improving direct sales through reaching out directly to the engaged consumers on the network (Stec, 2015). Twitter has over 320 million active users and approximately over 1 billion monthly visits to the site (Twitter, 2016).

2.4.3 YouTube:

YouTube is a video sharing social site, launched in February 2005. This site allows its user to upload, view and share informative and entertaining videos to other across the globe. YouTube is one of the most popular channels in the world, and it has undergone significant changes. Google purchased YouTube in October 2006 and followed a clear strategy to develop YouTube into a revenue generating product with a corporate model focusing of advertising (Gerhards, 2017). He also added that in order to monetize produced video content, YouTube expanded on opportunities for enterprises (Gerhards, 2017; Kim, 2012). Furthermore, there are numerous advertising formats that YouTube provides to businesses such as skippable ads, non-skippable video ads and display ads (YouTube Help, 2018).

The UGC (user generated content) social network sites (such as YouTube) encourage online communities to be more productive, creative and shape new viewing patterns (Cha et al., 2007). Product placement has appeared another opportunity for YouTube creators using their prominence on the social platform to commercialize their content (Gerhards, 2017). Moreover, the YouTube content creators have seen using their reputation as reliable endorsers and influencers in the social media sphere to promote brands products and providing in-depth product reviews. It is widely believed that an image is worth of thousands of words and picture can create huge impact on individuals' minds. This ability has provided YouTube a great competitive advantage in online marketing. In last few years, many businesses have appeared using social media influencers for marketing their products and services and providing in-depth product reviews on YouTube. Several organisations have had their breakthroughs with outstanding video campaign on YouTube in the form of brand marketing, particularly via viral videos. Such viral videos and successful campaigns credit go to brand marketers' creativity and expertise to entertain the audience, and thus motivating individuals to share the videos with

others.

2.4.4 Instagram:

Instagram is a video and photo sharing mobile application and social network site, developed by Kevin Systrom and Mike Krieger. Instagram allows its users to take pictures that can be edited with filters and share the media on this site as well as can be shared from other social sites such as Twitter and Facebook (Stec, 2015). Reports shows that there are over 400 million active users monthly, these individuals share over 40 billion images, which means with an average over 80 million photos are being shared on Instagram on the daily basis, which gets about 3.5 billion likes everyday (Instagram, 2016). According to Duggan et al., (2015), Instagram users involve more than half of young adults (between 18 to 29 years old), which represents the largest group of Instagram users.

2.4.5 Snapchat

Snapchat is a social media mobile application, developed by Evan Spiegel, Bobby Murphy, and Reggie Brown, which allows its users to send and receive photos and videos that disappear after 24 hours (Stec, 2015). People can send and received time-sensitive videos, images and text messages each other that expire upon viewing. Due to its recordability and modality affordances, the users of snapchat have grown significantly in last few years, and it is extremely popular among the young age group especially below the age 18. According to Waddell (2016), users communicate with each other photos and video clips, that up to 10 seconds long, through the Snapchats' modality affordance feature. Instagram has adopted the snapchat feature recently in which individuals have the ability to select the audience viewing their content. As per noted by (Piwek and Joinson, 2016), Snapchat has over 100 million worldwide active users, and users sent approximately more than 4 billion snaps every day.

2.4.6 The role of social media networks:

Social media networks can be defined as platforms or channels that permit users to create personal profile and websites that can be accessible for the other people to exchange and share personal contents and other useful information (Palmer and Lewis, 2009). Social media networks can be characterized into digital media, platforms and online applications, and their main objective is to facilitate interaction, collaborations and sharing the information (Palmer and Lewis, 2009). Communication is considered as the core dimension of social media networks, however, Fauser et al., (2011) point out that all platforms of social media are not equally suitable for marketing purposes, because some of them are lack of suited information,

collaboration as well as for cultivating relationships. Social media network's main objective is exchange of ideas of interest and communication between communities or peer groups. Nevertheless, it has appeared that marketers can develop and maintain a long-term relationship among the consumers and businesses through frequent communication on the social media platforms (Gummesson, 2002).

On the other side, it is believed that marketers (information providers) are the ones who build their own communities through social networks constructs and thus, discussions are led by the vocal members and staffers of these constructs (Janal, 1998). Janal (1998) also added that these vocal members are considered as opinion leaders, and that's how communication and collaboration among online customer and the marketer is developed. This statement shows that there would be no serious engagement between a business and the online communities without information flow within communities from the brand or business. Below figure 7 provides an idea that which kind of collaboration usually take place within the confines of the social environment (Fauser et al., 2011).

Figure 7: Social dynamics in the social network sphere: (Fauser et al 2011).

According to Palmer and Lewis (2009), one of the main issues that corporates are facing while interacting with social media platforms is the way to control communication environment within the system/network in order to protect their reputation and image of the brand.

2.5 Social media marketing:

It is considered as influential marketing approach in which brands can share contents, diffuse information, develop relationship and stick with their consumers (Kim and Ko, 2012; Chang et al., 2015). Ashley and Tuten (2015) state that the social media marketing has the capability to integrate with the traditional marketing functions such as advertising and promoting a product on a new engaging media by facilitating various activities and generating different productive contents on different platforms of social media. Berthon et al., (2012) demonstrate that marketing through social media transforms the conventional single-way communication to multi-way communication, thus it has proved more powerful in contrast to traditional channels of marketing such as TV, radio and magazines. In addition, Godey et al., (2016) illustrate that brand-generated messages on online social platforms can induce individuals' enthusiastic communication as well as it can impact on their behaviours as well as influence on consumers' buying decisions.

Social media marketing has two key roles, first role is to develop communication between the customer and enterprise and second role is to create communication between different consumers (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). However, this communication is a time-consuming process. Social media provides businesses a better way of communication to their consumers that was not possible a decade ago (Hudson, 2013; Dewan and Ramaprasad, 2014), and it is replacing the old and traditional way of communication (O'leary, 2011). A new concept Social Customer Relationship Management (SCRM) has emerged in a company's management system, which helps through social media channels to develop relationship and loyalty between brand and consumers (Dutot, 2013).

On the other side, blogs and social media also involves risks and threats as well, and it can backfire on the brand. Profitable social media marketing depends upon the healthy relationship between consumer and brand, and it can improve by listening and responding on time (Ramsay, 2010). As noted by Khan and Fasih (2014), consumer satisfaction can be increased through social media by connecting with customers and by keeping them engaged through various social activities. Word of mouth marketing (WOM) is high valuable for SMEs, as it refers to customer satisfaction that leads to repurchases in the future (Tripathi, 2014). However, Cheung, Lee and Thadani (2009) argued that negative WOM marketing can damage the market campaigns as well as brand reputation.

It is widely accepted that opinion of other individuals plays an essential part in a purchasing process. Research shows that a friend recommendation influence more towards purchasing, and about 63 percent of people prefer a blogger opinion rather than a magazine (Brooks et al., 2014). Although, the impact of social media implications is considered huge and powerful in terms of brand awareness and consumer engagement, nevertheless, in terms of performance it does not show the clear picture of its effectiveness (Dutot, 2013). Choosing the right channel for a right audience is one the most important key for a successful campaign. Customer's satisfaction could be assessed by monitoring customer's feedback. As Mitchel (2010) illustrates, the emerging interests and trends can be identified by monitoring customers reviews and feedbacks which helps to develop a future competitive strategic plan.

Moreover, creating and developing brand used to be expensive and difficult, but social media is providing new techniques and easy methods to reach potential consumers and keep them engaged with their brands (Vivek et al., 2012). Studies show that the investment on social media has increased more than 3 times from the last 3 years (Key Note, 2014), due to its various effective way to reach existing and new potential consumers worldwide. Ashton (2009) demonstrates that marketing through social media networks is considered as an essential element in marketing for SMEs due to extensive penetration of social networks throughout the world. In addition, an important contribution is added by Kietzmann by presenting a model "The honeycomb of social media", that explains customer engagement using social media in a structured and more sufficient way. The model consists of seven functional building blocks, that help brands to engage consumers in a systematic way and provides consumers a better understanding.

Figure 8, The honeycomb of social media, Kietzmann (2011).

The honeycomb model can be extremely useful for organisations to recognise and understand its social media landscape that helps to choose right channel and strategy. Managers of SMEs can assess social media's constantly changing activities through the Honeycomb framework. Different channels of social media such as YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn work differently as shown in the below figure 9. Therefore, this framework is beneficial for businesses to monitor and understand the way different social media platforms impact.

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Figure 9, Functionality of different social media platforms, Kietzmann (2011).

The popularity and reputation of a company or brand plays an important role in consumers purchasing behaviour. A business cannot ignore the power of reputation which is based on the experience of existing satisfied customers (Ashton, 2009). However, at the same time due to unsatisfied customers and negative comments or feedback, social media campaigns can backfire that can create instantly bad reputation for a business or a brand. (Cheung, Lee and Thadani, 2009). Although these technological social media platforms bring and explore lots of opportunities for SMEs, but competitors and unsatisfied customers can try to damage the brand reputation through posting bad reviews, comments, and offensive images. Hence, social media can be extremely harmful for a business or brand reputation if a company does not have the proper resources to monitor and respond these posts on time (Robert and Kraynak, 2008).

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2.5.1 Digital marketing:

Digital marketing plays an essential component of marketing which utilize online and internet-based technologies and other digital channels to promote services and products in today's modern world. Digital marketing can be simply defined as achieving businesses or marketing goals with the help of digital technologies (Chaffey, 2013). Baines and Fill (2014) defined the term digital marketing as, "Management and execution of marketing using specifically digital electronic technologies and channels to reach markets in a timely, relevant, personal, interactive, and cost-effective manner". The latest and advance technology is used in digital marketing to enhance the marketing activities, which can improve consumer knowledge through matching and fulfilling their demands and needs (Chaffey, 2013).

Digital marketing has become increasingly as an important communication channel for organisations. Digital marketing has appeared alongside with digital media environment as well as other digital media technologies. Digital marketing is required to integrate with both communication and channel distribution plans to work effectively, as it interdependent of traditional communication platforms, distribution channels and other marketing principles (Helm et al., 2013). People tend to behave differently in digital environment. In today's modern world, digital marketing is considered as a wide concept that involves various aspects of marketing activities such as social media marketing, email marketing and internet advertising (Baines and Fill, 2014). However, there are several aspects which appear along with digitalization that organisations need to consider. For instance, social media without doubt provides and enhance several communication channels between businesses and consumers, but without being able to control it.

2.5.2 Blogging in the context of digital marketing:

Blogging (among the different types of social media channels) is believed as an essential element for communication, source of information, product specification, enabling consumers to authenticate the product information and in digital marketing (Luck and Ginanti, 2013). It is suggested that there are several research on blogging that are applicable in digital/online advertising (Schmallegger & Carson, 2008; Brodie *et al.*, 2011). Several consumers have been seen subscribing to marketing blogs to get an additional knowledge and point of view of a particular product and service, which helps buyer to make decision

(Scott, 2009). Due to bloggers' potential reach to high number of consumers, blogs are becoming extremely important for implanting marketing mix (Ahuja and Medury, 2010).

Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) demonstrate that there are several studies that identify the certain roles for blogs to enhance marketing communication. Usually, a blog links the vendors and the consumers on the offers of a product, provide his (blogger) personal view, supply chain information, explain other consumer views from the market research and provides the product advantages and disadvantages (Bijmolt et al., 2010). In addition, according to Schmallegger and Carson (2008), blogs make some pre-purchase promises by influencing the customer's point of view of the product under marketing mix.

Although, it is believed that blogs have potential of reaching high amount of consumer and attracting them towards purchasing a particular product, but communications and interactions are also essential marketing strategy for developing loyalty (Sashi, 2012). Similarly, Van Doorn et al., (2010) illustrate that blogs help consumers by simplifying the process of customers selecting from variety of products promising similar solution to individual's needs. Furthermore, as per noted by Brodie et al., (2011), blogs popularity is increasing rapidly among modern consumers for the sake of convenience due to blogs diversity and ability to capture and present the products information.

2.5.2.1 Tactics to engage customer through blogging:

it has appeared from the different studies that marketers utilise different blogging tactics to engage with consumers according to the situation (Verman, 2014). For instance, to enhance the customer's experience travel blogs move between destinations. This statement is well supported by Pan et al., (2007) by demonstrating that increased number of visitors or tourists have been experienced in those destination that was supported by blogs by different marketers or agencies.

Although researchers have recognised the success of internet marketing in engagement with consumers, but there are some corporates who still tend to use old traditional ways of marketing to maximise their sale and to engage with their customers. In contrast with traditional ways, it is widely accepted that online tactics of marketing offer lot more convenient to the sellers and customers. Moreover, modern and young consumers tend to spend more time on social media channels and use online website for shopping. Therefore, companies and brands need to create unique selling propositions and market their products

and services in a way that it stands out during digital marketing for their potential customers (Luck and Ginanti, 2013).

Studies suggest that due to online interacting between marketers and customers, customers tend to give more feedback on products and services, and these online interactions also enhance the communication and collaborations between them (Sashi, 2012). Thus, firms can use blogging and social platforms as their preferred tactics of communication with customers to understand their needs of the later in a timely manner which can help to minimise shifting loyalty to competition. Furthermore, Pan et al., (2007) point out that consumer engagement through online marketing allows marketers to understand the customer's purchasing behaviour, focus, needs and also emphasis on the brand development. Tourist sector is considered as one of the most influenced and active users of blogs and other social media platforms (Sashi, 2012). Social media networks combine with bloggings tactics have helped tourist sector to attract maximum number of clients and inform them about different destinations. Similarly, Halligan and shah (2009) added that many organisations have adopted same tactic to market their product and services. However, there are not many research to decide for firms which particular social media channel is appropriate for a particular marketing strategy.

2.5.2.2 Challenges for blogging:

Studies demonstrate that bloggings offer many advantages, however there are few professional challenges that firms may face that could discourage consumers from purchasing goods (Lee et al., 2006). According to Lin and Huang (2006), one of the most common challenge is lack of an appropriate study to establish the usefulness of blogs to attract consumers for a certain product. Due to lack of research, wrong information or inappropriate views on a certain product can backfire which can damage the brand reputation. As Brodie et al., (2011) demonstrated that when a consumer purchases a product, most of SME's seek customer loyalty and trust for the brand to be successful. Past studies indicate the challenges that there are discrepancy of empirical research in terms of customers' activities relationship on social media networks. Hence, Kumar et al., (2010) argue that it is hard to find out whether or not customer purchasing decision was a direct result of the blogs or not.

Some consumers do not believe on the bloggers as they believe bloggers get money from firms to promote their product and thus, they would not show clear picture of the product.

Similarly, Bricci et al., (2015) illustrate that trust is a leading concern for consumers from the information they get from the blogs. Halligan and Shah (2009) also supported by saying that these trust issues occur mostly first-time customers with no experiences. A blog with lack of referrals and evidence to strengthen its information regards to a certain product or service creates the same situation where trust issues arise especially among new consumers (Luck and Ginanti, 2013). In addition, it has emerged in the research that customers shift their loyalty towards other brands or firm if they get negative experiences from a products or service attracted and promised by a blog (Kumar et al., 2010).

SMEs have appeared facing more challenges as compared to large corporations to market their brands' products and services through the blogs (Coviello et al., 2000; Gilmore et al., 2001; Reijonen, 2010; Hill, 2001). According to Reijonen (2010), SMEs face more challenges due to lack of formal marketing policies, weak organisational structures and instead of being proactive they tend to use random tactics to engage and react with customer views. SMEs should utilise appropriate social marketing channels instead of random for different marketing purposes (Gilmore et al., 2001). Moreover, SMEs has been seen less considerations for the bigger marketing strategies and often use blogs to address pressing needs (Stokes, 2000). According to Walsh and Lipinski (2009), studies show that several SMEs prefer to use conventional advertising method rather than social channels such as blogs for handling those marketing issues that do not involve consumer concerns. It has also recognised from the past research that other major challenges for the SMEs are to track sales, to stimulate buying behaviours and even to design their blogs to address customer service effectively (Harris et al., 2008). There is not enough research to point out that how SMEs can utilise blogs and other relevant social networks activities to engage consumers in a way to overcome challenges of advertising their product and services as well as to compete with large corporates within the same marketplace.

Berthon et al., (2008) point out that SMEs' managers consider blogs marketing method as overhead cost without guarantee in improving sales and thus, they hardly utilise bloggers to market their products or services. By supporting this statement, Moss et al., (2003) also added that SMEs consider bloggings just as an option for marketing strategies, and mostly their preferred marketing strategies are unknown. Studies also show that very few small firms utilise blogs as their marketing strategies to market their products and services as they believe there is no guarantee that it will improve the sale (Gilmore et al., 2001). Many SMEs do not have enough budget for this type of marketing such as blogs and Facebook marketing (Reijonen, 2010). Gimore et al., (2001) state that bloggings without doubt have

high impact on consumers, but it requires specialisation in SME activities and most of SMEs do not have mature marketing departments to address and justify the appropriate strategy. Therefore, adoption of blogs in SMEs for marketing purpose is relatively low key as compared to the large organisations (Walsh and Lipinski, 2009).

On the other hand, some researchers consider bloggings as emerging marketing strategies and due to its complexity, they believe it is not suitable for small organisation (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). Due to narrow view of products, some managers of SMEs prefer not to utilise social media marketing activities such as bloggings (Roijenen, 2010). Walsh and Lipinski (2009) demonstrate that some SMEs appeared to give less priority to potentials of blogging as a strategy because they do not have a clear distinction between advertising and marketing.

It is widely believed that conventional advertising methods were not designed for SMEs and these marketing approaches only suitable for the large organisations (Small Business Trends, 2011). Digital marketing such as Facebook, Instagram and YouTube can be suitable for SMEs, however, other emerging marketing concepts such as bloggings mostly benefit large businesses (Parr, 2009; Stoke, 2000). In addition, Reijonen (2010, p. 280) illustrates that several small medium organisations face different challenges in adopting bloggings as the suitable strategy with reference to the 4Ps of marketing that are product, place, price and promotion. According to Stelzner (2011), several SMEs close their business due to aggressive online competition and limited understanding of digital/online marketing and bias towards large corporates.

Although social media marketing activities such as blogging offer SMEs affordable ways to market their products and services, but lack of knowledge, skilled personnel and inappropriate approach could be challenge for them (Stokes, 2011). As noted by Weinberg and Pehlivan (2011), the major reasons that SMEs failed to compete with large organisations are lack of resources and implications of an appropriate marketing strategy. Research show that very few SMEs are able to take full advantage of Blogs to reach potential consumers, thus it is a challenge for most of SMEs to get skilled and specialised managers and marketers to harness the competitive advantages of blogging (Taylor, 2011). Moreover, it is appeared that many SMEs are seeking best models of blogging that will market their products in a better way to thrive and to get the competitive advantage in the marketplace (Moss et al., 2003). Overall, SMEs are appeared slow and hesitant in adopting

bloggings as their main marketing strategy due to several reasons such as lack of resources, budgets, time, skilled managers and narrow products lines.

2.5.3 Social media as a cost effectiveness:

SMEs can reach millions of potential consumers by using social media marketing that is based on online internet infrastructure (Palmer and Koenig-Lewis, 2009), at a very low cost in contrast with other old and traditional ways of marketing such as magazines, newspaper, TV and etc (Weinberg, 2009). Marketing through social media channel such as You Tube, Instagram and Facebook are a lot cheaper than other old ways, but it also more effective and have different ways to reach its potential customers faster to bring traffic to stores or websites. Old and traditional ways of marketing such as advertising on TV could cost millions and small medium start-up companies would not be able to afford to do that, whereas some of social media site are free to use and others do not cost a lot. According to Pace (2008), social media marketing is not only cheaper but also more effective and appeared effect on a high volume such as, a business can present better content information to understand stories by sharing video through You Tube.

2.6 Consumer engagement through social media:

Social sites such as Facebook and You Tube provide companies day to day interaction with their consumers that allow them to monitor the recent trends, fashion and allow seller to get immediate response from their customers (Hill and Moran, 2011). Through immediate useful response and feedback from consumers, brands can test their new ideas and products by sharing videos on You Tube and Facebook. Customer care services through social media are appeared more useful (Tariq and Wahid, 2011) due to its fast and efficient way to solve the customer complaints (Parveen et al., 2015).

Online presence of a business on social media provides a lot more opportunities, but also involves several challenges and threats. As the shared information is available for everyone during a marketing campaign (Hart el., 2000), so anyone can dislike the products, services and as a result leave the negative feedback. These negative feedback and comments from people can damage the reputation of the product and brand among other consumers. Although SMEs can target its consumers through social media quite easily to throw their message as compared to traditional ways. However, Cheung et al., (2009) argued that few negative feedbacks or comments can damage the whole campaign and businesses cannot

do a lot about that. As noted by Dutta (2010), these instant feedback and instant respond to customers might be useful to improve the products and services for a long term.

WOM (word of mouth) fuels social media marketing to spread information instantly, and if a business left his customers unhappy then it could damage the reputation. According to CEO and founder of Amazon Bezos (2011), one unsatisfied customer can express his experience 6,000 of his friends through social channels, whereas in a physical world he can tell only 6 other friends. The most significant strength of social media channels is 'explosive reach' reach and 'going viral'. However, it has been proved through numerous cases when marketing through social media not only failed but also backfired on the businesses. For instance, Kenneth Cole had to publicly apologise and delete their message for tweeting Cairo during Egyptian riots to spread their message as shows in the below figure 10.

Figure 10, Kenneth Cole Tweet (2013)

Social channels provide new start up SMEs sustainable advantages and help them to monitor existing competitor's activities and generates high customer value (Wilson and Gilligan, 2005). This statement is well supported by Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004) as they state that social media offers high quality interaction with consumers that enable customers to co-create the unique experience with the firm as well as add the better value through positive WOM. As Ferguson (2008) illustrates, due to positive word of mouth marketing, 82 percent private firms are growing rapidly in these days. But he also suggests

that there is not any evidence that word-of-mouth marketing develop brand loyalty and increase customer lifetime value (CLV).

2.7 Ethics and Other Legal Issues:

One of the most important concern using social media are ethics and other legal issues as many cases appeared when private and professional information has been shared on social sites. Copyrights and trademarks are another important issue for businesses particularly in developing countries (Steinman and Hawkins, 2010), as brand and products are the most valuable assets for an organisation. Another major issue of sharing on social media is privacy and data security. Trust is considered as an integral factor in online buying behaviour (Steinman and Hawkins, 2010), and it is very important element to keep engage consumer with the brand (Hoffman et al., 1999). As mentioned above social media platforms approach is incredible, nevertheless, Robert and Kraynak (2008) argued that due to online presence the pressure on companies also increases.

2.8 Social awareness:

Social media is expanding its reach day by day particularly in developing countries. For instance, Facebook in his home country has 191.3 million active users whereas, in India it has approximately 195.16 million active users (Singh, 2016). Social media is considered as a network to mobilise individuals for a cause as well as for various other social awareness campaigns. Leading brands are participating in social awareness campaigns through social media to create awareness in public which helps to create WOM as well (Gensler et al., 2013). It is clear that brands that are associated with these social awareness campaigns demonstrate their genuine interest in their social responsibility as well selecting different social media channels helps them to get a maximum consumer engagement. Engaging with consumers through these heart touching contents on social media channels is a great way to develop brand awareness and create positive WOM.

2.9 Social media sales funnel adoption:

A business or brand value can be increased by developing relationship between the brand and online communities through social media networks. A firm must need to find out that when and which social media platform need to use efficiently to reach its potential customers, to attract quality prospects as well as to engage customers. Streaming can be

used by selecting right social media networks with right online communities to achieve these objectives. This process is linked to sales funnel. Social media marketing funnel is a path in which customer travel from initial stage stages (when someone learn about your business) to the purchasing stage, then this map takes it to the conversion and beyond.

The funnel is considered as a metaphor which is likely wide at the top and narrow at the bottom in order to examine the sale process. There are several consumers at the top of the funnel that might be interested in company's products or services, then this process attracts those consumers through their social networking constructs. Sale section is further down at the bottom when a customer finds a brand of value and make purchases. The below figure 11 illustrates the way individuals are streamlined within the 'internet jungle' through different social media platforms of their preferences into the domain of the marketer.

Figure 11: Social media sales funnel: (<http://socialmediatoday.com/SMC/176665>).

In today's modern world, several sellers are trying to utilise social media sites to advertise their products and services. Research illustrates that marketing approach differ from business to business (Kotler et al. (2006). It also appeared from the studies that small organisations often obtain marketing ideas from their sales force team, managers and advertising agencies, and these firms do not tend to establish formal marketing groups in their strategy (Kotler et al., 2006). The marketers use multiple platforms of social media to attract individuals to their own sales funnels. If marketers successfully achieve the target by bringing right traffic to their sites, solidifying the relationship to keep the consumers and completely satisfy them, then they can act as unpaid marketers for the organisation by

spearheading positive word of mouth (WOM). These satisfied customers also market company's products offline through sharing their experience with their family members, friends, colleagues etc. Hence, it has emerged that from a successful consumer network, the customers chain can expand massively to a complex and large network.

2.10 The power and value of social networks:

Social media platforms refer as a set of relationship that have tendency to grow into enormously complex patterns (Gummesson, 2002). So, a positive relationship and interaction can be developed among the brand and consumer through an appropriate social media channel on a B2C level. Social media channels affect more on online businesses than offline. There can be many reasons for firms to decide to go online such as to grow contacts, establish a brand, to increase sales and to reach worldwide online community. The role and value of the social media networks fundamentally become more important as soon as a firm shows online appearance.

There are three different value-governance laws, which can be applied to social communities and networks. These laws are appeared to draw the importance of having vast complex patterns on a relationship. Although, studies show that inventors did not create Metcalfe's law, Reed's law and Sarnoff's law particularly for the social media channels, however due to the semblance they bear with the structure of social media networks, these laws have equally embraced.

2.10.1 Sarnoff's Law:

Sarnoff's law was created by David Sarnoff, an American businessman as well as the pioneer of American commercial television and radio networks. David Sarnoff was also the founder of NBC (National Broadcasting Company). This law was devised to determine the impact of the radio value towards its listeners. According to Sarnoff's Law, a radio station value is direct proportional to the number of listeners, so according to him if the number of listeners on that station increase then the value of radio station will increase accordingly. As noted by Evans et al., (2008), a channel consists of 100 members will be considered 10 times more valuable as compared to a channel with only 10 members in terms of reachability contrary. It is believed that Sarnoff's Law theory equally implies in the prospective of social media networks, thus the effect on brand will be as much as many people will connect to a brand through social media networks. Law implications towards

the networking of individuals can be seen in below figure 12.

Figure 12: A network representative of Sarnoff's Law (socialmediaonline.com).

2.10.2 Metcalfe's Law:

Robert Metcalfe was a Massachusetts Institute of Technology graduate, and this law is attributed to him. He was one of the inventors of the Ethernet and the founder of the networking firm 3com. Metcalfe's Law explains that the service tends to be more valuable to the community if the greater number of the users with the service, as both direct proportional to each other. So, in the social media network prospective, according to this law, the brands or individuals' profile become more valuable with the addition of new members on the networking channels (Evan, 2008). The chain of the connectivity expands further to others through social media networks by sharing customers' experiences. Such as a satisfied customer tend to share his positive experience with his family, friends and other online community. The figure 13 shows that how far a message can reach with the increase on network chain by supporting the above theory.

Figure 13: Metcalfe's Law, (mshare.net, 2012).

2.10.3 Reed's Law:

David P. Reed designed the Reed's Law. He used to work in the computer networking area and was a computer scientist at Massachusetts Institute of technology. Reed's Law states that with the increase of the size of a network also increase the function of large networks. Reed's Law appeared to be a useful use on the social network sites. This law highlights the impact on the social networks value by recognizing and supporting online communities and members. Research highlights that large online communities and well-connected networks inspire the strong sub-groups formation and increase the flow of communication which later stress on the more important and relevant information within the networks and communities (Evan, 2008). By creating opportunities to all individuals that are added to the network, supporting members of the group can be developed. The quantity of new connections expands with the addition of every new person, and it leads to the formation of another sub-group. Connectivity of individuals within network can be seen in figure 14.

Figure 14: Reeds Law: Source: socialmediaonline.com.

2.11 Brand awareness through social media activities:

The online platforms of social media invites individuals with common interests to share their opinions with each other (Weber, 2007). It is widely accepted that organisations use these internet and mobile-based technology social platforms for their marketing activities in two aspects. According to Chen et al., (2011), the first aspect is the effect which a customer has from a brand's products or services and the share he creates towards other individuals. Social media influences trust and purchasing intention as well as it facilitates sharing one's knowledge and experience among others (Hajli, 2013; Lu and Hsiao, 2010). As noted by So et al., (2017), online social media channels are used by many businesses to encourage their customers to share their purchase experiences online. Secondly, firms are appeared to utilize these social media channels for direct marketing actions, which means that businesses are using social media tools to advertise and brand promotion to their consumers at low cost as compared to traditional ways and receive feedback from their users (Hanna et al., 2011). It is found that cost-cutting measures, recognition of social media networks among consumers (such as Facebook and YouTube), and competitors' activities on these online social channels motivate marketers to carryout marketing activities on

social media networks. (Tsimonis and Dimitriadis, 2014).

Social media marketing activities have characterized as interaction, entertainment, trendiness, word of mouth and customization communication (Kim and Ko, 2012). Similarly, Seo and Park (2018) added that in airline industry, social media marketing activities can be defined as trendiness, interaction, entertainment and perceived risk. Kang (2005) demonstrated entertainment as an essential component which encourages behaviour of individuals and stability as well as continuity of follow up that generates positive feelings in the followers' thoughts and attitudes on social media about the brand. Information is simultaneously shared on social media in real time thus, it has become latest and up-to-date source of information for customers (Hamid et al., 2016).

In addition, these social networks facilitate the communication, content sharing and collaboration of companies with their potential consumers as compared to traditional mass communication channels (Wang, 2012). It has become possible to attain customers' needs and requests, their suggestions and opinions regarding brand and products in real time by utilizing social media platforms as collaborative communication among customer and firms (Vukasovic, 2013). Another important component of social marketing activities is trendiness that introduce the current, latest and popular products information for consumers (Godey et al., 2016).

It has appeared that brand page on social media networking channels provide an interactive and virtual platform which enable brands to achieve the aim of marketing communication (Tafesse, 2015). Moreover, previous studies point out that brand posts on social media websites can enhance customers' brand awareness (Taecharunroj, 2016), strengthen brand-customer relationship (Gensler et al., 2013) and simulate individuals' purchase behaviour (Kim and Ko, 2012). According to Kim et al., (2015), the contents of a brand post can be categorized in terms of brand and consumers' interactions into different themes. Most of consumers have appeared checking brand posts daily without participating in the interaction, and they tend to participate if they find topic interesting (Ashley and Tuten, 2015). Hence, marketers need to generate the branded contents that can elicit strong emotions for individuals in order to obtain their attention on the brand posts (Chen et al. 2015).

2.11.1 Brand Awareness:

The term brand awareness can be defined as “the ability of a potential buyer to recognize or recall that a brand is a member of a certain product category” (Aaker, 1991:61). Perreault et al., (2013: 199) defined the brand awareness as level of consumer acceptance, recognition and a recall of a brand in any case. Furthermore, Verbeke et al., (2005) stated that brand awareness has appeared reducing time and risk that individuals spend in search of a product to buy. Brand awareness can also be determined as crowd power in customer’s memories which reflect ability of individuals recognizing a brand in multiple conditions (Keller, 2009). According to Vark (2007), word of mouth (WOM) performs a crucial role to create brand awareness, as it is considered the most powerful brand building tool beside the product itself (Vark, 2007).

2.11.2 Brand Image:

Brand image is concerned with the views that audience and external stake holders hold regarding the brand (Walker, 2010; Black and Veloutsou, 2017). A brands’ position in the consumers’ eye is known as brand image, while a reflection of a brands’ concrete indicators considered as brand awareness such as sign, symbols, name and slogan. A brand image can be defined as, "consumer perceptions of and preferences for a brand, as reflected in various types of brand associations held in consumers' memory" (Keller, 2009). An image of a brand characterizes individuals’ personal symbolism which consists of all the evaluations and definition associated with the brand (Iversen and Hem, 2008). Furthermore, Lee et al., (2011) illustrated that a brand image includes all the opinions, ideas and information that consumers have about a particular brands’ products and services. Similarly, Riezebos (2003: 63) stated that these images that a consumer has about a brand has developed because of consumption experiences, marketing communications and social effects.

2.11.3 Brand Loyalty:

Customer loyalty refers as a commitment of a consumer to repurchase a product or service from an organisation despite competitors’ actions (Oliver, 1999), whereas a brand loyalty is a behaviour of repurchasing that shows a deliberate decision in which a customer continues to buy from the same brand (Schiffman et al., 2010: 468). According to Lee et al., (2003), loyal customers have positive effect on a business performance in a competitive environment, and in a condition, when cost of retaining current customers is lower than

acquiring new customers are increasing gradually indicates the loyalty of customers (Kumar et al., 2011; Keisidou et al., 2013). A brand loyalty shows that consumers prefer to purchase consistently from the same brand (Schiffman et al., 2010: 468). Similarly, Jones and Taylor (2007) added that customers who purchase from the same brand shows the behavioural aspect of loyalty. Furthermore, individuals who usually buy from a brand, they are not just interested about the product but care about the whole experience that a brand offers regarding both hedonic and functional brand experiences (Morgan-Thomas and Veloutsou, 2013; Merrilees, 2016). Moreover, a positive experience with a brand strengthens the brand reputation among individuals' minds via customer commitment (Hepola et al., 2017), which also leads to loyalty (Brakus et al., 2009).

2.11.4 Brand Identity:

A brand identity refers the relationship among the brand and his consumers. A brand identity provides a foundational starting point, wherefrom all activities regard to investment and brand building are derived. Brand identity needs to be clear, explicit, have structure, depth and consistency so that it can develop realistic and credible communication material. Consumers will not get confused this way. According to Martenson (2008), an organisation can obtain better internal guidance in the formation of decision making and modern marketing ideas (such as selection of an appropriate social media channel) if it has a clear core identity.

Martenson (2008) also points out that there will be more chances for a brand to be successful if:

- Authentic (It means if the brand acts in line according to his own core values).
- Unique (It refers as exclusive or enough differentiated from other companies to attract and motivate consumers over other brands).
- Consistent (It means if the consumers are getting reliable and high-quality service and receiving coherent messages from the brand every time when they interact).
- Transparent (It states if the brand is reliable and translucent).

Researchers also demonstrate that if an organisation or brand have all above mentioned qualities with a good reputation then it gets another additional quality called 'visibility' (Martenson, 2008). It is believed that customer experience a certain reliability and trust with the brand if the brand utilizes these traits in a proper manner during communication.

On the other side, an image of a brand refers the way individuals observe the brand. This term includes various types of relationships that are linked among brand and its consumer and express if these associations are enough strong, unique and beneficial. The brand associations need to be related to the target groups' purchase motives to get customer to purchase a service or product. (Martenson, 2008). Consumer usability is one the essential element that brands need to consider. Consumers attracted to the certain brand with expectation that their objectives will be fulfilled, so brands need to make sure that their products must fulfill a given purpose.

2.11.5 Brand equity:

Brand equity can be described as the name and value of a brand in the minds of consumers (Martensen et al., 2007). Research shows that brands develop brand equity through creating positive experiences with their customers so that they continue purchasing from them to attain a competitive advantage over competitors. It is widely believed that brand power lies on various aspects such as what a customer has leant, seen, felt and heard about the certain brand over the time (Keller, 2008). Therefore, marketers directed to develop strong brands by ensuring that their customer gets positive experience with their products and services. Keller (2008) also suggested that the total experience of customers which is created through the brands' different communication channel (online and offline) networks must be consistent and in accordance with the consumer. Positive experience with the brand can strengthen the brand in the customers' minds both indirectly and directly through customer engagement that leads to brand equity (Mishra et al., 2014).

The importance of the brand equity differs from one company to another (Martensen et al., 2007). Lemon et al., (2001) addressed the four key factors, which explain the criteria in which brand equity matters the most, as shown below.

- Brand equity is vital when the use of the product or service is highly visible to other consumers.
- It is essential for those purchases that have low involvement and simple decision process such as customer packaged products.
- Brand equity is essential for credence goods that involve impossible to check the quality of a product prior to consumption.
- The role of the brand equity could be critical when the experiences associated with the service or product tend to pass from one customer to another.

2.11.6 Challenges for online branding:

The online branding has become an integral part of businesses marketing activities since the mid-90s when the internet development began. Online branding has become more important since the online activities started performing greater roles than ever before in sales and marketing communications. Thus, Smith (2008) illustrates that internet offers opportunities for SMEs to develop their brand online efficiently and to increase their worldwide reach. On the other hand, it is not an easy journey for online firms particularly in these days to develop a brand online. There are multiple challenges that marketers are facing to influence social media networks, as it is widely believed that modern customers also know to leverage firms for their own benefits and advantages. Research illustrate that the social media channels can create and destroy the brand image at the same time (Cheung et al., 2009), and it is considered as ‘double edged sword’ that can cut both ways. For instance, word of mouth (WOM) is considered as the most powerful tool in brand building, and it spread very quickly however, negative word-of-mouth communication generates e complaining, which can damage the brand image and trust among its consumers (Harrison-Walker, 2001).

Generally, managers main focus and motivation to use social media networks was to develop and maintain the relationship with online communities and to send their message to millions of customers in short period of time. However, it did not work in this way and customer started to use these online platforms such as Facebook and Twitter for complaining and negative reviews on products (Gendel-Guterman, and Levy, 2017), rather than look for product information, prices etc. For instance, Netflix (an online streaming media company based in USA) announced through a blog that they would increase subscription plan by 60% (Ludwig, 2011). More than 4100 customers comments on Netflix official blog and most of them were negative. One customer said, “You’ve decided to raise customer rates during a period of economic downturn, when people are struggling to pay for basic necessities and when cable TV is just too damned expensive” (Ludwig, 2011). Similarly, Darrin Wright of Zimmer Radio Group also wrote on the Netflix official blog, “You’re forcing me to pay more for products and services I’ve paid for loyally for quite a while now. You’re really, REALLY making me reconsider this business relationship.” In addition, Todd Hayward of Old Dominion wrote, “You’re going to be losing a lot of business with this decision.” This situation created an uproar and their stock plummeted substantially within a short span of time. Thus, the company had to apologies and reverse

their decision accordingly, but this scenario already done the massive damaged to business. This example demonstrates that how brands' marketers have no longer control on the reach of their messages and how weaknesses and shortcomings of a business could be exposed.

Marketers also suffer from self-inflicted catastrophe besides damaged caused by online channels communities. If an organisation use anonymous individual and invents consumer to influence discussions recommending a product or service for a brand through social media networks, then that firm is believed to suffer reputation risk. According to Aula (2010), This seems like an unethical way to present product/service offers of a company and it can lead to damage the brand image and reputation if the information's leak out to the public. Consumers are enabled to serve as creators and disseminators of branded content due to multiple factors such as open-source branding, a situation that requires collaborations, participation and social linked behaviour (Fournier and Avery, 2011). Therefore, Chaffey (2004) argued that if the social channel turns out to be poor in regard to structure, performance, or information content then there is a danger for brands to move online due to possibility of reducing brand equity. Furthermore, there are risks for developing SMEs of meeting such threats in an effort of building a brand online through cheaper alternatives to save costs.

On the other side, it is appeared that large and established organisations invest on social media with better strategies and seize the opportunity of growing brand online for their already existing brand. Although there are several challenges for SMEs, nevertheless, studies highlight that there is good return on investment (ROI) through social media marketing, and it helps the brands to spread their wings to a bigger territory, that tend to reach to many more consumers and to create brand awareness, which is most likely to boost the profitability curve of a business in future.

It is crucial to examine the major impacts of social media networks on a brand. A proper analytical measure needs to be outlined to establish consumer's knowledge effectively. Evan (2008, p.145) analyses the metric of brand awareness through social media as shown in table 1.

Target Knowledge	Interpreted Information	Underlying Metric
Audience	Who`s reading	aggregate profile
Unique visitors	Page views, visitor`s info, blog mentions, click analysis, traffic patterns, source of traffic via Referrer measure	Web Analytics: Unique visitors
Influence	Memes (thoughts, ideas etc) and intensity overtime	Time on site, blog context, review polarity
Engagement	Clicked on length of stay conversation	Time on site, pass-alongs, comment-to-post ratio, blog mentions, reviews, bounce rates
Action	Conversions	Pass-alongs, conversions, reviews
Loyalty	Trends: subscribers, repeat visitors, referrals	Pass-alongs, blog mentions, time on site, bounce rate

Table1, Social media metric (Evans. D, 2008, 145).

2.12 Challenges and risks of Social Media Marketing:

Marketing through platforms of social media offers a number of advantage and low-cost strategies to SMEs to reach its potential consumers throughout the world. Nevertheless, as noted by Stelzner (2011), SMEs may face many challenges and risks before achieving success, as social media marketing requires specialised knowledge in this field. Generally, Many SMEs adopt social media marketing due its cost efficiency and easy to use. But many studies demonstrate that sometime social media can be expensive and hard to adopt as it depends on the numerous aspects such as the type of a business, age and size and style of the management (Cheng et al., 2015).

It has appeared that foremost SMEs are required to engage time and human resource to manage their online presence on social media networks effectively. It is essential that employees of SMEs are ready and able to communicate with their online consumers, and respond to their messages, complaints and feedbacks on the daily basis. SMEs' employees that are responsible for online communities' engagement must be properly trained and highly skilled so that they can respond to individuals' each feedback and complains effectively. Furthermore, these employees engaged in social media activities should be able to control and manage every possible scenario such as negative feedbacks and product reviews before these comments are found by thousands of other customers, which can damage the brand or product image (Gendel-Guterman and Levy, 2017). Responsible marketers for social media campaigns need to be active and are required to create fresh content regularly according to the situation to enhance and keep consumers engaged to the brand. In this way a brand can create a process of continuous communication with their customers. It is believed that consumers get annoyed if they keep getting irrelevant advertising, emails or messages, therefore, firms need to make sure not to publish or advertise irrelevant contents to individuals.

To understand the efficiency of marketing strategy, marketers need to control and assess the outcomes of the social media marketing. Studies show that different marketing platforms of social media have different influence on the SMEs (Dessart et al., 2015), depending on the customer target and business type. So, some of them may occur more efficient than others and other can be very expensive and time-consuming. Consequently, marketers are required to choose an appropriate platform of social media for a specific purpose (Simon et al., 2016). In addition, it is difficult to find out the return on investment (ROI) for social media marketing channels. It is considered one of key challenges that

SMEs face from social media marketing channels. If marketers are unable to measure the outcomes of social media marketing, then this impossibility restricts managers of SMEs to know whether the social media channel is the best strategy for them or not (Gilmore et al., 2007). So, there are not enough research that can help marketers to find out that which exactly social platform they should choose, and the appropriate way to trace the sale to know whether it is helping to improve brand awareness or not.

Brand image is another potential threat for SMEs, who use social media networks for marketing. Social media marketers can damage the brand reputation by using social sites ineffectively (Jeon and Baeck, 2016). Many customers unfollow the business on social media and get annoyed due to excessive use of advertising by the social media marketers and sometimes customers leave the negative reviews as well due to this behaviour of companies. Employees of SMEs need to be active with positive attitude and behaviour, because one bad comment from an employee can damage the brand reputation within short span of time. It is essential for brands' marketers to discover suitable ways to handle these crisis situations more effectively such as fake news (Berthon et al., 2018), brand sabotages (Kahr et al., 2016), negative publicity (Gendel-Guterman and Levy, 2017), negative reviews (Ullrich and Brunner, 2015) and collaborative brand attacks or online firestorms (Rauschnabel et al., 2016), with an emphasis on adjusting these negative experiences according to their nature. Hence, social media marketing must be managed appropriately because reputational risks can be easily exceeded than the reputational advantages on social media networks.

There is no doubt that online existence creates opportunities for businesses, however it also brings many challenges and complication for the social media marketing process. According to Hart et al., (2000), a website present same information online to all the consumers and support the need for consistency in the design, planning, implementation, and control of online marketing communication. SMEs need to consider following five major drawbacks while using social media networks for marketing.

2.12.1 Time consuming:

Social media is appeared to be interactive and successful. Marketing nature in networks of social media is changing continuously, and SMEs are focusing to create long-term relationships with their consumer to increase sales and loyalty. According to Barefoot and Szabo (2010), SMEs need to appoint someone responsible to monitor each channel, answer

to customer questions, respond to both (positive and negative) comments and to post product/service information regularly. It is very difficult for brands to compete without an appropriate service to manage these social media networks. A significant amount of time investment is required for a successful social media marketing, and it is considered crucial and first preliminary consideration (Barefoot and Szabo, 2010). They also added that if firms decide to use social media marketing, then they must consider time commitment in their account otherwise they may face many challenges and negative feedbacks through their social sites.

2.12.2 Trademark and Copyright Issues:

Trademark and copyright are considered key issues for brands. It is essential for the brands while using social networks for advertising to protect their trademarks and copyrights. A trademark and other intellectual properties are valuable assets for a company (Steinman and Hawkins, 2010). Copyright and trademark laws apply to social media in a same manner as other traditional marketing. It is widely accepted that activities on social media are considered commercial with few exceptions because they are designed to enhance the interaction with consumers. Social media networks offer communication with customers on a real-time basis, help organization to promote their brands and disseminating copyrighted material. However, as per noted by Steinman and Hawkins (2010), there are high chances that it may ease third-party abuse of a firm's trademarks and copyrights.

Marketers must monitor the use of their trademarks and copyrights regularly during using social media through firm's own social media platforms or via third party. To ensure that providing contents on social media outlets are not misusing their intellectual property, it is necessary for the companies to monitor their own social media outlets and third-party social media channels. Steinman and Hawkins (2010) point out that modern technologies and software provides internet tracking and screening services to the companies in order to monitor business's copyright use on third-party sites such as to check other social media channels for usernames or profile that are identical to your brands and business's names. It has examined in various studies that if firms neglect and left it unchecked then it may damage the company's brand and reputation (Steinman and Hawkins, 2010). Such monitoring can have positive impact on the business. Furthermore, businesses with online presence on social media sites must have an appropriate terms and condition policy with clearly specifying the way others should use the companies and third-party trademarks and intellectual property. Marketers should have proper regulations in place such as

impersonation, copyright infringement and trademark during conducting social media marketing campaigns, promotions and user-generated content campaigns.

2.12.3 Trust, Privacy and Security Issues:

Trust, privacy and data security issues are other important factors for the brands while using social media networks to promote products and services. It is essential for organisations to take these issues in their accounts and take appropriate actions to limit their exposure to liabilities in regard to personal data collection, usage as well as maintenance. Hoffman et al., (1999) refer trust as the unique dimensions of transactional privacy and security. They also added that trust plays an essential role for social media marketers in gaining consumer loyalty. Research demonstrate that online payment credit/debit card frauds are among major reasons that some customers are afraid to buy online (Ratnasingham, 1998).

Generally, most of social media channels such as YouTube, Instagram and Facebook have their own terms and condition and privacy policies that protect copyrights and personal data from third-party. Every organisation has to follow these policies in order to run their campaigns on these social media channels. SMEs who use these social channels need to make sure that their marketing campaigns abide this privacy policies and these campaigns should not persuade consumers to engage in practices that would violate privacy rules of any social media platforms. Marketers of SMEs who use their own blogs and sites also ensure that they also maintain their comprehensive privacy policies that disclose the data collection, and storage practices of a company (Steinman and Hawkins, 2010).

Trust is considered as an essential element in the online buying process, and it is closely related to security. Research illustrates that trust of brand have a huge impact on individuals' behaviour and their purchasing decision as customers cannot feel, smell and touch the product in online buying process (Lovett, 2011). Thus, trust on a brand contributes to a reduction of uncertainty. Moreover, it is believed that loyalty is an additional component of the trust. Therefore, brand trust and loyalty can aid SMEs to overcome some of the disadvantages of online channels and online marketing. According to Gommans et al., (2001), A 'third-party approval' can be used as a tool to build trust. Nevertheless, unreliable marketplaces, dishonesty and unsafe internet connections are the perceptions that stopping individuals to buy from online social sites.

2.12.4 User-Generated Content (UGC):

People have been seen spending more time using social networking sites, sharing information, thoughts and views with each other during last few years. New form of communication and, collaborations and content generation apps are appearing on the internet. According to Filho and Tan (2009), marketers are using new type of marketing strategies that involves social media sites incorporate user-generated content. User-generated content (UGC) refers to the content that mostly made by the users of a certain brand, and it is believed as more authentic and honest. User-generated content (UGC) has become crucial part of modern marketing strategy and it allows the users to make comments on the specific products and services in different forms such as videos, audio, photos, ratings, articles, reviews, blogs and podcasts (Filho and Tan 2009). UGC is appeared as high degree of credibility in the consumer's eyes.

UGC in connection with social marketing strategy also comes with several risks as it can provide some damaging contents. Negative, inappropriate comments and poor product feedback can significantly damage the brand (Ullrich and Brunner, 2015). Thus, marketers must be careful when they rely on consumer-generated content media to carry their online presence. Unknown and unreliable sources are another prominent issue of UGC. In addition, marketers must be familiar with all the legal aspects that come with UGC, if they choose to opt for UGC campaign.

2.12.5 Negative Feedbacks:

Studies highlight that social media has ability to convert consumers into marketers through feedbacks and word of mouth marketing, however these consumers can create positive and negative impact on the brand according to their experience with the products or services (Robert and Kraynak, 2008). According to Ghose et al., (2009), consumer generated product reviews are considered as valuable source of information for other individuals regarding purchase decision online. Due to emergence of Web 2.0 technologies, these products reviews and feedbacks are rapidly increasing on the social media networks and creating a huge impact on the business particularly online ones (Forman, Ghose and Wiesenfeld, 2008). On the other hand, negative reviews and feedback from customer can damage the whole marketing campaign and easily destroy the certain product reputation (Ullrich and Brunner, 2015). It is widely accepted that social media platforms are accessible to everyone, so competitors and unhappy customer are able to post a negative experience

and offensive posts to destroy the brand image, and there is not much a marketer can do to stop these comments (Cheung, Lee and Thadani, 2009). Nevertheless, these negative responses cannot be ignored and are required appropriate response from employees of the organisations. Similarly, Hennig-Thurau et al., (2010) also illustrate that SMEs need to manage their social network campaigns appropriately through immediate response to negative feedback and by neutralizing harmful posts.

2.13 Summary:

This chapter has provided a detail understanding of the concept consumer engagement and highlights the influence of social media in today's modern consumers. It has also reviewed social media marketing concept and its application to promote products and services in order to enhance customer relationships and to facilitate consumer communicational activities. Furthermore, the literature has pointed out the brand building activities and effective ways of social media marketing activities that offer various opportunities to SMEs to create brand awareness, as well as to interacts with their customers on personal level. This section has identified the major challenges for online branding, and also highlighted the threats and risks that a brand may face due to social media presence. Overall, this chapter has covered all the aspects of research objectives and questions of the study that would help in the next chapters during data analyses and discussion.

Chapter 3 Research Methodology:

3.1 Introduction:

The major purpose of this chapter is to highlight the employed methodology process in detail by providing the supporting evidence to attain the objectives of this study. Firstly, the purpose of research is discussed in order to select an appropriate research methodology (Creswell, 2003). Then, different research philosophies are discussed followed by research approaches (deductive approach and inductive approach). Furthermore, research design and research choices are critically explained and rational for using quantitative methods for data collection also discussed. Then, following the questionnaire design, the sampling strategy, sample frame and sample size is discussed. The data collection process is explained in the section 3.8, and pilot test is carried out on small scale to test the statistical properties of the measuring items and to get the feedback before releasing the main survey to the large sample, as pilot survey can be generally small that can be consist of 10-40 individuals (De Vaus, 2013).

3.2 Purpose of the research:

It is essential to consider the study purpose to determine the appropriate research methods and research methodology (Creswell et al., 2003). The research aim is to develop a professional case for SMEs to find out the effective use of social media channels to create brand awareness and to engage modern consumers. This research is important due to the empirical information regarding the place and role of social media networks in consumer engagement for small-medium organisations and to enhance the brand awareness among consumers.

The current diversity of people of shopping online, reading the reviews online and sharing on social media attracts brands for online presence (Dessart et al., 2015). It helps SMEs to follow the latest trends and consumers purchasing behaviour. It is widely accepted, although SMEs often get enough customers, but they failed to engage them with their brand. This study will highlight how SMEs managers can engage consumers through social media and blogs.

Research have proved that social media can assist brand marketing such as promotions and other products information including prices, offers and specifications (Jett, 2012). But critics argued that this is only possible with the selection of right social media channel for the right purpose (Chang et al., 2015). Nevertheless, it has appeared that there is no clear literature and published research has examined this matter. As noted by Creswell (2012) and Muaz (2013), Exploratory, descriptive and explanatory are the most common purposes for undertaking research. These research methods can be combined, even though, they are distinct with one another. Similarly, Cuthill (2002) illustrated, descriptive and exploratory research can be combined depending on nature of research.

Descriptive research focuses on situation, population or phenomenon that is being studied. It mainly concentrates on finding out questions such as what, when, how and when, rather than why. It is mainly used to insight into a problem and population. According to Anastas (1999) and Babbie (2007), descriptive research boost availability of research questions and population for analysis prior to the initiation of a research study. Similarly, Anastas (1999) and Creswell (2002) state that a descriptive study can be employed to gather information regards to present status of trends and to analyse the current variables in a particular situation.

Explanatory research is conducted to find the problem in depth, and it is mainly used to get some conclusive evidence that can help us to understand issues more efficiently. As per noted by Collis and Hussey (2009), this type of research emphasizes on relationships between variables, to deeply identify cause and effect, define the effect of interventions, test hypotheses and to test theoretical model, among others. In other words, it explains the interferences from a sample to the population of interest. On the other hand, exploratory research can be used to identify those research problems that are still under investigated. According to Cuthill (2002), if there are few or no research available for references related to specific research problems, then exploratory research is conducted. The major focus of this approach is to obtain insights and ideas. Methods used in exploratory research provide the advantages in reviewing the literature in-depth, and in making the descriptive research more effective.

From the above classifications, the research is considered descriptive and exploratory (as it tries to illustrate the current usage of social media by modern consumers and the way SME's can engage them through social channels to enhance brand awareness). The aim of this research is to develop a professional case for SMEs to find out the effective use of

platforms of social media to create brand awareness and to engage modern consumers. This aim focuses the “what” question in the research. As per noted by McNabb (2008), this technique provides insight into a situation as well as observe the environment in its natural settings without changing the environment.

The major aim of the research is to obtain a rich descriptions and in-detail understanding of the key elements in which consumer engagement can be improved and to create brand awareness. A descriptive design suits the research, because there is no intention to experiment with, and there is no need to change the environment of the subject. In addition, A selection of a descriptive research design is more suitable in which answers to particular research questions are required other than “why” (Anastas, 1999). The main research questions and research objectives for this study are:

Research Objectives	Research Questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ To determine the impact of social media on customer engagement and brand awareness in today’s modern world. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ How does social media influence today’s world? ➤ How do social media sites impact on individual’s lives in terms of consumer engagement and brand awareness?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ To review the individual characteristics in terms of brands, which helps SMEs to reach their potential consumers and engage them through social media. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ How social media can help SMEs to engage modern consumers? ➤ How can SMEs create brand awareness through social media networks?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ To provide some recommendations and suggestions in the light of estimated findings, that can save a brand from unexpected damages and threats and help them to reach their potential customers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ What are the possible risks and threats towards a brand image? ➤ What policy should be implemented through social media towards brand image in connection with potential customers?

3.3 Research Philosophies:

It is essential to understand the term of research philosophy to select a suitable methodology (Clough and Nutbrown, 2012; Creswell, 2002). According to Bowling (2005) and Remenyi et al., (1998), there are several hierarchies and research philosophies in regard to research quality evidence, and as the research object is to obtain a new and better understanding in a systematic way so the research needs to clarify that what they consider to be “knowledge”. Generally, there are two distinct frequently cited research philosophies called positivism and interpretivism. Interpretivism utilise the social science approach and it uses open ended approach to collect and analyse the data (mostly qualitative audio and visual data) in which knowledge is constructed/interpreted and values are more subjective (Creswell, 2002).

On the other hand, positivism utilise the natural science approach in which data is collected and analysed objectively through quantitative data collection method and theory/hypothesis testing (Creswell, 2003). It is clear that both of these research philosophies have different basic theories that what and how study needs to be conceived. It is widely believed that philosophy term concerns about the knowledge creation and its nature, and suitable research philosophy helps to attain objectives and aim of the research (Creswell, 2002; 2003).

A proper understanding of research philosophy is essential to carry out research due to several reasons. Firstly, it allows the investigator to focus and choose an appropriate research strategy. Secondly, it critically evaluates the various methodology types and the available methods for the researcher, and last but not least as per noted by Easterby-Smith et al (2008), a proper understanding of research philosophy turns the investigator into more innovative and creative by adapting new and appropriate research methods that were probably never been used by researcher and out of his/her experience. Hence, in order to select a suitable research approach to answer the research questions, it is essential to analyse the current research philosophy.

It is widely believed that that research philosophies are known as knowledge claims that are established by scholars to start the research with specific theories and assumptions that relates to what and how they are going to find out during investigation or analysis (Lincoln and Guba, 2000; Neuman, 2013; Creswell, 2002). Blanche and Durrheim (2004) state that generally researchers follow different paradigms used in a research process that depends on the logical and empirical outcomes, that are connected with the evidence. It has been

appeared that research philosophies provide a rationale for the study and assist the investigator by directing him to utilize specific techniques to collect, observe and to interpret the data. A better understanding to the philosophical problems of research methodology is considered as a dynamic aspect of research design (Easterby-Smith et al, 2008). Guba and Lincoln (1994, p.105) stress the importance of research philosophy by claiming that, “Both qualitative and quantitative methods may be used appropriately with any research paradigm. Questions of methods are secondary to questions of paradigm, which we define as the basic belief system or world view that guides the investigation, not only in choices of method but in ontologically and epistemologically fundamental way”.

Research philosophy can be related to the knowledge nature as well as knowledge progress. However, Collis and Hussey (2009) demonstrate this term as “progress of scientific practice based on people’s philosophies and assumptions about the world and the nature of knowledge; in this context, about how research should be conducted”.

It is important to describe the epistemological and ontological stance to understand the chosen research design for the current research. Ontology refers as the things that comprise reality or the study of reality (Slevitch, 2011). Similarly, ontological consideration can be described as ‘what is the form and nature of the reality’, hence what can be know about it is “how things really are” as well as “how things really work”. Allison and Hobbs (2006) state that the term of ontology is about the nature of the knowable or what is reality of the nature. On the other hand, epistemology is concerned with the nature of knowledge and learning ways about social reality. An epistemology consideration concerns the questions of what is regarded as acceptable knowledge in a discipline in the social world (Bryman and Bell, 2011). It also refers as the nature of relationship between the known (Knowledge) and the knower (the inquirer) (Allison and Hobbs, 2006). In simple words, epistemology aims on the knowledge, and ontology concentrates on the reality that we seek to know.

3.3.1 Epistemological stance:

Several scholars believe that the research philosophies can be either interpretive or positivist (Saunders et al., 2009; Easterby-Smith et al., 2012; Hussey and Hussey, 1997). Easterby-Smith et al., (2012) demonstrate that positivist paradigm can be described as the world is external and objective and on the other hand, interpretive concept can be referred as the world is subjective and socially constructed. The researcher must need to focus more on facts if he/she employ the positivist paradigm. In this case, as noted by Mackenzie and

Knipe (2006), investigation leads to a condensed phenomenon with the simplest elements retained. On the other hand, by employing the interpretive paradigm, the researcher needs to find out that what is happening while examining the overall situation presented. The researcher is then required to develop the ideas through the induction of collected information by employing different techniques to establish diverse outlooks from several schools of thought (Carson et al., 2001). From these arguments it is appeared that interpretive paradigm seems better than positivist theory. Nevertheless, it has been appeared in the past where positivist paradigm dominated several research disciplines such as science, clinical health, management and psychology research. As per noted by Bowling (2005), qualitative/interpretivist research has seen the lowest quality of evidence on the hierarchy of research evidence. In contrast with, later this bias has been challenged by several scholars by arguing that positivist research produce knowledge and explains only what and how but unable to clarifies why (Creswell, 2003).

Many scholars believed that positivistic studies are generally undertaken for analysing hypotheses (Buchanan and Shortliffe, 1984), while the truth can be examined as a collective factor such as language realization and shared meaning by way of interpretative studies (Bogdan and Biklen, 1998). One of the main disadvantages of interpretative study is subjectivity dilemma and difficulty to make a decisive estimation of public fact with the concept that the investigator would not be able to prevent disturbing the analysis by justifying the reality. According to Bordens and Abbott (2002), the way in which research topic is considered indicates the difference between these two theories. The truth is independent from our beliefs of it as per idea of the positivist anthology. Similarly, several researchers illustrate that although research consider actions of humans as a social issue, but the truth cannot be separated from its natural setting (Bordens and Abbott, 2002).

The key differences between positivism paradigm and interpretivism paradigm are shown in below table 2.

Positivism tends to:	Interpretivism tends to:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have an artificial location • Use large samples 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have a natural location • Use small samples

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be concerned with hypothesis testing • Produce results with high reliability but low validity • Produce precise, objective, quantitative data • Allow results to be generalised from the sample to the population of interest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be concerned with generating theories • Produce findings with low reliability but high validity • Produce ‘rich’, subjective, qualitative data • Allow findings to be generalised from one setting to another similar setting
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Table 2: Difference between Positivism and interpretivism, (Collis and Hussey, 2009, p.62).

As the main purpose of the study is to enhance customer engagement and to create brand awareness, so it is justified that positivistic approach can be used for an appropriate paradigm, because positivistic approach looks at a society as a whole and to understand the general laws that shape human actions as well as numerical data has been seen the only way to research and compare the large data.

Initially, it was decided to use mixed-method approach to collect the data. According to Greene (2008), with quantitative data, the researcher can get many individuals for sampling and precise statistical analysis, and in the meantime, small samples can be used for an in-depth understanding of phenomenon through the qualitative data approach. However, the nature of the study and research objectives suggest using descriptive and statistical analysis, thus quantitative technique is employed for data collection. Furthermore, the pandemic situation of Covid-19 also favors the quantitative approach, as taking interviews (qualitative method) could be extremely hard in the current situation. The descriptive analysis is considered useful for identifying new hypotheses and variables that may be further analysed through inferential and experimental studies (Marsh & Stocker, 2010, P.271). It is also useful for taking the trends and behaviour of the individuals straight from the data properties and the margin for error is very small. High degree of objectivity and neutrality is another key advantage of descriptive analysis (Lans and Van Der Voordt,

2002). Moreover, one of the key reasons to choose positivism is that it accepts the abstract and supernatural as data for research purposes. A knowledge gained through positivist approach is based on a real and objective interpretation of the data.

3.3.2 Ontological stance:

According to Collis and Hussey (2009), to enhance the choice of research methods, it is essential to recognize the prospects of all philosophies. In order to do that, there are a few theories behind each philosophy methods that are compared as below:

Assumption	Questions	Quantitative	Qualitative
Ontological	What is the nature of reality?	Reality is objective and singular, apart from the researcher	Reality is subjective and multiple as seen by participants in a study
Epistemological	What is the relationship of the researcher to that researched?	Researcher is independent from that being researched	Researcher interacts with that being researched
Axiological	What is the role of values?	Value-free and unbiased	Value-laden and biased
Methodological	What is the process of research?	Deductive process Cause and effect Static design-categories isolated before study Context-free Generalisations leading to prediction, explanation and understating Accurate and reliable through validity and reliability	Inductive process Mutual simultaneous shaping of factors Context-bound Emerging design-categories identified during research process Patterns, theories developed for understanding Accurate and reliable through verification

Figure 15: Various assumptions of the paradigms (Collis and Hussey, 2009).

Logically, the research paradigm here rotates around the power of social media in today's modern world. The question of how (epistemology) to determine that new SME's can reach their potential customers to create brand awareness and the link between characteristics with the above-stated claim. The study tries to expand the power of social media networks to enhance the consumer engagement, to create brand awareness (axiology), and an appropriate approach need to be used to produce outcomes (methodology) (Creswell, 2009).

The concept of pragmatism approach recommends developing a research design according to the nature of the research objectives. Previous studies have examined that pragmatism does not depend on a severe dualism between the mind and realism entirely free of subjectivity (Murphy, 1990), and this approach believes that there is no absolute unity in this world. In this stance, research decides on the nature of reality through the use of both approaches (qualitative and quantitative) (Creswell and Clark, 2007). Creswell (2003) suggests that ontological stance does not presume one philosophical stance better than another one, nevertheless in order to recognize a problem holistically from various perspectives and to overcome mono-method bias, it tends to integrate with other research paradigms. In contrast with positivist stance, which try to establish universal laws and does not believe that results can be universally generalizable, ontological stance presumes that studies tend to take place in social, historical, political and other circumstances (Cherryholmes, 1992). Rorty (1982) suggests that pragmatic approach is based on the realistic context and naturalistic settings, and he also added that it suits better in addressing the real-world challenges.

From the above explanation, the researcher has decided to use pragmatic philosophical approach for this study. Other philosophical approaches such as constructivism, and advocacy-participatory or critical theory scientific paradigms were not appropriate for research investigating to develop a professional case for SMEs to find out the effective use of social media and bloggings to create brand awareness and to engage modern consumers.

Advocacy-participatory approach has been examined putting more efforts on bringing about revolution in practices (Kemmis and Wikinson, 1998). It has also been observed that this approach supports people to free themselves from limitations found in work, media, and language processes as well as in the dealing of control in educational settings. The objective of advocacy participatory method is to create a change through generating political discussion and debate (Stringer, 2007). This research is more concerned regards

to the identification of useful social media channel as well as analysis of the role of these characteristics in the effectiveness enhancement rather than attempting to bring change. Hence, as per noted by Sherman and Torbet (2000), the advocacy research paradigm is not suitable as per collaborative and practical approach for this research, because it seems like an inquiry approach that accomplished 'with' others rather than 'to' or 'on' others. Similarly, another reason for not choosing this approach is that most of these approaches are being used by practitioners who want to enhance their knowledge of training and others who want to employ change such as social change advocates (Lewin, 1946).

Constructivism approach believes in individual's personal learning through experience, and construction of meaning is influenced by the interaction of prior knowledge and new events (Arends, 1998). According to Elliott et al. (2000, p. 256), the approach of constructivism is to learn that holds the individuals actively construct their own knowledge as well as the reality is determined by the learners' experience. It is believed that this theory adopts a socially relativistic ontology by which social actors develop non-normative and subjective knowledge. The approach of constructivism believes that people relate to their world and depends on their historical and social perspectives, and it does not allow the use of an epistemology for organizing knowledge that is based on objective reality (Crotty, 1998). The basic formation in this approach is emerging from both non-interaction and interaction and at all ties social (Creswell, 2002). Similarly, Schwandt (2000) added that it leads people to search for the intricacy of views instead of narrowing meanings to only few concepts or categories. Thus, constructivism method does not fit in this research, because in this approach, researchers are required to identify from their own experiences in order to form their interpretation and locate themselves within their study to recognize the way their analysis flow from their own personal, historical and cultural experiences (Schwandt, 2000; Crotty, 1998).

3.4 Research approaches: Deductive and inductive:

It is essential to choose an appropriate research method as a useful strategy for developing the social research validity (Creswell, 2002). A researcher is required to consider research questions and research objectives carefully in order to select a suitable research approach. Deductive and inductive are the two major research approaches (Saunders et al., 2009). In addition, in the deductive approach, researchers formulate hypotheses which is based on the previous theory/findings, then they collect and analyse the data to test a that hypothesis (Saunders et al., 2009). On the other hand, researchers collect and analyses the data to

develop a hypothesis. None of method is mutually exclusive, because any developed concept (inductive) needs to be analyzed (deductive) in order to establish its explanatory power, and it has also seen that deductive approach tends to start from an inductive approach (Saunders et al., 2009).

Cavana et al., (2001) explains the steps that are involved in both deductive and inductive research approaches in below figure 16.

Figure 16: Deductive and inductive approaches. Cavana et al. (2001, p.36).

According to Saunders et al. (2007), the comparisons between deductive and inductive approaches are demonstrated in table 3.

Deductive methods	Inductive methods
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principles based on science. • Movement flows from theory to data. • Casual relationships between variables need to be explained. • Quantitative type of data is mainly collected. • Measures of control are applied in order to ensure the validity of data. • Concepts are operationalised in order to ensure the clarity of definitions. • The approach is highly structured. • Researcher is independent from the research process. • Samples need to be selected of a sufficient size in order to be able to generalise research conclusions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The aim is to explore the meaning of human attachment to events. • Research context is understood in a deeper manner. • Qualitative type of data is collected. • More flexible approach to research structure to ensure provisions for change during the research. • Researcher is perceived to be a part of the research process. • Research findings do not have to be generalised.

Table 3, Deductive approach vs Inductive approach, (Saunders et al., 2007).

3.4.1 Inductive approach:

Inductive research approach also known as “bottom-up” research and works in the opposite direction as compared to deductive approach (Holyoak and Morrison, 2012). According to Punch (2009), study begins with particular measures and observations which leads to identify patterns and regularities. And later examiner tends to develop tentative hypotheses, and then in last he builds some general theories/conclusions. Furthermore, inductive research method’s nature is exploratory and tend to be more open-ended in comparison with deductive approach.

Creswell (2002) points out that in inductive approach, a researcher is required to examine the data internally even prior to assessing the data that is necessary to identify the answer. It has appeared that as compared to deductive research method, inductive approach has

been used more often among scientists due to generating concrete conclusion about nature which are well supported by several observational facts. Generally, the inductive method has appeared using comprehensive readings of raw data in order to distinguish models, concepts and themes through the understandings of the study (Strauss and Corbin, 1998). For instance, an investigator firstly begins with the area of study and then develop a concept/theory through the data he gathered during study. One of the key strengths of inductive approach is to investigate in depth and create theoretical explanations in detail for most of phenomenon. Nevertheless, it is quite time-consuming, and in this approach, a researcher is required to collect large amount of data that needs to be precise and analysed to find relationship and to develop a coherent theory.

3.4.2 Deductive approach:

In this approach, an investigator begins its research from the top with the wide range of information that follows down to a specific conclusion, and therefore deductive approach refers as ‘top down’ approach. A researcher generally uses deductive approach when the work progresses from general to a specific information (Strauss and Corbin, 1998). Researchers start from a related assumption/theory with a topic of interest, then they narrow it down to the key concept/idea, and then develop particular testable hypotheses. Constructed hypotheses are further narrowed down again as the observations are gathered, which ultimately help the researcher to test the hypotheses with specific data. This process leads the researcher towards original theory verification and to reach a conclusion and decision (Guba and Lincoln, 1994).

An examiner who uses deductive approach look at the data from an external perspective and narrow down the data to reach the specific conclusion. To reach at a conclusion, a thorough observation of several observational facts is not required in deductive approach. By working on these axioms, a researcher can easily start with generally accepted theories before heading towards an answer. According to Wilson (2010), deductive approach has been seen concerning more towards developing hypotheses based on recent theories and then an appropriate strategy is required to test the hypotheses. Similarly, Monette et al., (2004) state that this approach has been appeared to concern with deducing conclusion from the propositions of a hypothesis. As per noted by Babbie (2010), inductive method usually starts with observations and tend to discover pattern within them, whereas deductive method begins with a projected pattern which is after evaluated against observations. Researchers investigate existing theory or phenomenon in the deductive approach and then

assess in a given situation, whether or not the related theory is applicable (Beiske, 2007). Snieder and Lerner (2009) also added that it follows a logical path very closely which starts with a hypothesis and finishes at rejection or confirmation of theory after testing through observations. This method is mostly used in quantitative research and positivist, in which data collection is objective, controlled and standardized, and to make casual interference from a research sample (specific) to the population of interest (general), the deductive approach tends to use statistical inferential techniques. Singh and Bajpai (2011) illustrate that the strength of deductive research method is its quick ability to verify, revise testable assumptions and development of hypotheses. Therefore, it has a great impact and often used in clinical research, science and business management research.

From the above explanation and by considering the nature of the study, the deductive research method is applied in this research to address the research objectives. The key differences among deductive and inductive approach are the way existing literature and statements are employed to guide the study (Creswell, 2003; Patton, 2002). So, the deductive approach has been used to review the theory, and the literature has been utilized to identify themes, questions and interrelationship prior to collect the data.

3.5 Research strategies/designs:

Saunders et al., (2009, p.141) point out that it is essential to have an appropriate research strategy because it facilitate the researcher in achieving the research objectives through answering the research questions; and also argue that “the choice of research strategy will be guided by the research questions and objectives, the extent of existing knowledge, the amount of time and other resources available, as well as the researcher’s philosophical underpinnings” (Saunders et al., 2009, p.141).

There are several research strategies and research designs which can be used for particular research such as case studies, surveys, action research, interviews, experiments, grounded theory, archival and ethnography. Below figure 17, summarizes the different types of research designs.

Strategy/Design	Form of research question	Requires control over behavioural events	Focuses on contemporary events
Experiment	How, why	Yes	Yes
Survey	Who, what, where, how many, how much	No	Yes
Archival analysis	Who, what, where, how many, how much	No	Yes/No
Action-based research	How, why	No	No
Case study	How, why	No	Yes

Figure 17, Examples of research strategies/designs, (Yin, 2009, p.8).

The researcher has chosen survey through questionnaires for this study to attain the research objectives and to answer the questions outlined in the chapter one. According to nature of the study, online survey has appeared more suitable for this study as compared to other strategies e.g., ethnography, archival and documentary, grounded theory, experiment and action research.

3.6 Research choices:

Research choices are the process that help researcher to select an appropriate approach to collect the data that is required to make the final decision regards to research methods (Creswell and Clark, 2017). These choices involve choosing a mixed method (such as quantitative and qualitative method), mono method (such as quantitative only or qualitative only) or multi methods (such as quantitative, qualitative, and documentary evidence). According to Creswell (2002), it is essential to carefully choose an appropriate method for

data collection to make sure that it is in line with the overall presented research problem and particular research questions.

3.6.1 Types of Research Choices:

3.6.1.1 Qualitative approach:

In contrast to quantitative research, qualitative research involves collecting, analysing non-numerical data/information (e.g., audio, video, or textual data) to understand the opinions, concepts or experiences (Gay, Mills and Airasian, 2006). This approach also useful to generate new ideas for the research and together in-depth insight into a problem. It is appeared as an intensive way to gather data in which information is analysed inductively through categorizing and organizing into distinct pattern, that later generates a descriptive and narrative synthesis. Punch (2009) points out that one of the key attributes of the qualitative research is to study the event and act in their natural settings. This method comprised into 2 following features: firstly, the job of the research is achieving a holistic view of the perspective under research and secondly, examiners' attempt to collect the data on the local performers' perception "from inside" (Punch, 2009). Qualitative research method is used to understand the way people experience in the world. In addition, this approach is generally used in social sciences and humanities subjects such as sociology, anthropology, history, health science, and education etc.

3.6.1.2 Advantages of qualitative research:

A researcher is able to capture the changing attitude within a target group through qualitative research such as attitudes in workplace or consumers of a service or product. Qualitative research provides the characteristics and qualities of the investigated phenomenon and unlike quantitative research method, it cannot represent by numbers. Nevertheless, it is possible to quantify the qualitative data through an encoding process and hence, results can bring closer to quantitative research by applying with statistics. According to Norman and Yvonna (2005), qualitative research can identify characteristics of human opinion, emotion and behaviour that is not possible in quantitative studies. Collected data in qualitative research are mostly in the shape of structured interviews or naturalistic scrutiny, and before deciding which data will be significant to the research, a researcher needs to know and examine the behaviour, needs, trends, opinions and other related information (Madrigal and McClain, 2012).

Scholars examine the data for trend, behaviour and themes through qualitative approach instead of performing a numerical evaluation, and these themes can be data driven (emerging from the data) or theoretical (obtained from the literature) or it can be mixture of both. To identify trends, a researcher looks for statements that can be similar from different research population samples. Statement from only one person is known as anecdotal and same statement from 2 different person can be a coincidence. However, when the research gets same statements from lots of different individuals then it turns out to be a trend. Pasick et al., (2009) demonstrate that researchers can benefit business decision, marketing strategies and in product development by identifying trends.

During qualitative data collection, if a researcher is not being able to capture useful insights, then he can quickly change the setting, adapt questions, and alter the other variables to improve the results, thus, qualitative approach offers a much more flexibility (Madrigal and McClain, 2012). This approach encourages researchers to discuss their experiences openly, views, insights, and recommendations in a comprehensive way to produce richer description of phenomenon and to explain the 'how' and 'why' phenomenon. This approach also helps the researcher to reveal the new information due to open-ended and spontaneous discussion as well as due to more naturalistic settings.

3.6.1.3 Criticism of qualitative research:

Qualitative research offers extra flexibility, and it allows for reaction to user data as they appear during a session, whereas quantitative research involves uniformity of data collection for statistical comparison such as standardised instruments and the use of structured questionnaires. It is widely believed that qualitative data cannot computerized as effectively as data collected through quantitative method (Johnny, 2012). Johnny (2012) also added that trends cannot be validated by calculating significant p-value and an effect size through qualitative research method in the same way as quantitative method. It has assumed that collecting large data through qualitative method is time-consuming and extremely expensive. Furthermore, it is difficult to encode behaviour for novices, only expert research can do that, and it is costly and time-consuming to apply behavioural coding to qualitative data. The analysis of such data is highly subjective which increase the risk of interpretation as well reporting prejudice. A small amount of data is presented to the people from the large data collected through qualitative method. The quality of collected data can be affected due to the researchers' presence during interviews and the relationship they can

develop with their contestants. It is not possible to generalize the results to the population of interest due to very small sample size.

3.6.1.4 Quantitative Approach:

Quantitative approach involves collecting numerical data from a targeted sample such as surveys and experiments (Singh, 2007). Quantitative research approach looks at numerical and measurable relationships, and in this process, observational data is collected to answer research questions and its objectives through statistical and mathematical methods. According to Bieger and Gerlach (1996), data collected through quantitative method can be quickly analysed through different numerical methods, however, statistical sophistication is required to assess the test assumptions, quality of data, implement an appropriate data analysis and the statement results effectively. It is widely believed that numerical process (e.g., means and medians) has been used in the past studies to explain variables, and correlations of coefficients and regression in numerical data indicates the relationships among the variables (Bieger and Gerlach, 1996).

Researchers usually utilize quantitative methods such as encoded instruments and surveys to investigate their hypotheses (Creswell, 2012). Investigators first and foremost use quantitative research approach as post-positivist claims to create knowledge, for instance, the use of investigation and dimension of theories, reduction of specific assumptions and causal studies. The results/information collected through quantitative research can be expressed in statics and hence quantified, so it is possible to extract the forecasting and trends from this data (which is in numeric form). Statistical techniques and methods can be utilized for analyses of this type of data, and it involves inferential statistics such as anovas, T-tests and chi-squares, and descriptive statistics such as mode, mean and median. Muijs (2004) demonstrates that these statistical methods and techniques are arising analyses that draw relevant information/evidence from research data which comprises differences, trends and demographics. Madrigal and McClain (2012) also added that investigation shows that it is possible to break the data down even further by using some statistical tools to identify that which factor can be attributed to differences among particular groups, such as status, age and race.

3.6.1.5 Advantages of the quantitative approach:

The results gained through quantitative data help the researcher to choose appropriate statistical tests to use, and thus, further data interpreting and presenting the findings will be straightforward. This data will be more reliable, less open to argument and subjectivity (Bryman, 2012). Quantitative study presents descriptive data which shows snapshot of a target population, but a researcher can face difficulty when it comes to interpretation. The p-value can be defined as the probability under the assumption of no difference or no effect, which is measured from 0 to 0.1 in which a value less than 0.05 refers as a 5% chance to consider the results as coincidental (Goodman, 1999). Investigation shows that sample size effects on these values, and high accuracy to tabulated results can be achieved through bigger samples. Nevertheless, it is appeared that large samples could inflate statistical significance for marginal differences. On the other hand, a researcher may fail to detect significant effects (that exist), in case if a sample size is too small. By using a power calculation, an appropriate sample size can be determined to strength the statistical power result.

An appropriate size of a sample can be decided through using a power calculation to strengthen the statistical power of results. It can be seen through statistical significance whether or not research results are real, and it reflects that only 5% probability that they are due to chance. It is widely acknowledged that effect size adjusts the sample size for being too large or small across different studies and thus it is deemed a better indicator of findings significance. As noted by Punch (2009), during interpreting data, it is essential to take both effect size and statistical significance into consideration/account for better outcomes.

The speed at which analyst can design and implement is a major advantage of quantitative studies. For instance, there are several standardised tools available for survey research to measure relevant construct that can help to develop questionnaires quickly, data can be gathered at low cost rapidly through online surveys and further by using statistical software, collected data can be analysed swiftly. In addition, quantitative results are more representative of the target population because of larger samples are required as compared to qualitative research. Though Bowling (2005) added that it can increase if random sampling strategy of some form is going to be used as well as all other possible confusing/covariate factors has been controlled for. Moreover, in contrast with qualitative method, the quantitative research approach has showed a better quality of study evidence in some disciplines, which makes it easier to publish the study results in better quality

journals, to attract research funding and to persuade main decision-makers to implement the recommendations derived from the study.

3.6.1.6 Criticism of the quantitative approach:

Several studies show that quantitative analysis does not deliver the crucial evidence that is essential to interpret the data and only present data about a subject (Creswell, 2002). So, it is hard to say that why such factors take place in a certain way without this crucial information. Furthermore, such data deficiency may lead to critical errors during product designs' initial stages in the research that involves in making innovation. Thus, interpreting quantitative in conducting such data required a statistical expert. According to Given (2008), over-reliance has been seen on the large sample size and the p-value in several studies that used quantitative analysis, because if the size of a sample is too small then study results/outcomes can be inaccurate.

3.6.1.7 Mixed-methods paradigm:

Methodologies are usually adopted by business and management studies which is taken from the natural science that mostly depend on the positivist research theory. Qualitative methods such as case study plays an essential part in management research in these days (Yin, 1994; Patton, 2002). Nevertheless, other scholars claimed that case study can combine aspects of both phenomenology and positivism as this research is not necessarily qualitative, for instance, open-ended questions and statistical analysis about meaning and live experiences can be combined (Remenyi et al., 1998). Firstly, a case study can develop a theory (inductive approach), then it can go through testing to create generalization (deductive approach). Currently, it is appeared that several scholars do not endorse one method over another anymore. Many researchers point out that different philosophies are not opposed to each other, and they believe that the best methodology is the one which can answer the research questions more appropriately (Creswell, 2003; Knox, 2004). According to Remenyi et al., 1998), a case study has been seen collecting various sources of data from documentary/archival to interviews (that includes survey questions and open-ended questions) and direct observation that includes triangulation and mixed methods to increase the authenticity of the evidence and findings.

3.6.1.8 Mixed-methods approach:

The combination of both qualitative and quantitative research approaches is used in this method to collect and analyse data within the same study (Onwuegbuzie and Turner, 2007). This method serves a purposeful mixing of qualitative and quantitative method in data collection, data analysis and evidence interpretation. Investigations show that this type of data method helps researchers in seeking a more panoramic view of their research landscape, using different perspectives to look at the phenomenon and through diverse research lenses (Onwuegbuzie et al., 2009). According to Creswell (2009), it is a pragmatic approach that does not require a single method or philosophy and it helps the researcher to find a most suitable strategy to answer the research questions.

Mixed-methods approach was developed by Campbell and Fiske in 1959 while they were calculating the validity of psychological characteristics via different approaches. Later various investigators are influenced by them to use their multiple methods' matrix to perceive various approaches to collect the data in a single research study. As Sieber (1973) illustrated that these methods encouraged other researchers to use these methods to field study methods such as interviews and observations (qualitative method) by merging with traditional approach such as surveys (quantitative method). Mixed-method approach can be used concurrently (parallel) or sequentially (consecutive phase) (Creswell, 2002). Teddlie and Tashakori (2009) also added that this approach has been appeared to improve the understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. By the integration of the data, the weaknesses of the quantitative and qualitative can be minimized and their strength can be maximized. The strength and weaknesses of mixed-methods approach can be summarized as shows in the below table 4 (Onwuegbuzie and Johnson, 2006).

Strengths	weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Words, pictures, and narrative can be used to add meaning to numbers.• Numbers can be used to add precision to words, pictures, and narrative.• The researcher can generate and test a grounded theory.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Can be difficult for a single researcher to carry out both qualitative and quantitative research, particularly if two or more approaches are expected to be used concurrently; it may require a research team.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can answer a broader and more complete range of research questions because the researcher is not confined to a single method or approach. • The researcher can use the strengths of an additional method to overcome the weaknesses in another method by using both in a research study. • Can provide stronger evidence for a conclusion through convergence and corroboration of findings. • Can add insights and understanding that might be missed when only a single method is used. • Can be used to increase the generalisability of the results. • Qualitative and quantitative research used together produce more complete knowledge necessary to inform theory and practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher has to learn about multiple methods and approaches and understand how to mix them appropriately. • Methodological purists contend that one should always work within either a qualitative or a quantitative paradigm. • More expensive. • More time consuming. • Some of the details of mixed research remain to be worked out fully by research methodologists (e.g., problems of paradigm mixing, how to qualitatively analyse quantitative data, how to interpret conflicting results).
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Table 4, Strengths and weaknesses of mixed-methods approach (Onwuegbuzie and Johnson, 2006).

It has been recognised that to overcome the weaknesses that emerge using a single approach in the research, mixed-method approach can be applied to combine the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative approaches (Flick, 2009).

According to Yin (2003), "case studies may be based on any mix of quantitative and qualitative evidence". In addition, the triangulation of quantitative and qualitative data tends to lead towards a reliable and credible understanding to the case. Results of the one method can aid in developing the other method by using mix-methods (Greene, Caracelli and Graham (1989), thus this method provides in-depth and better understanding to produce more comprehensive outcomes (Creswell, 2003). Similarly, Morse and Niehaus (2009) also added that mixed methods offer researchers to explore results in more depth.

3.6.1.9 Rationale for using Quantitative Methods:

Quantitative research method can be defined as, “A research strategy that emphasizes quantification in the collection and analysis of data” (Bryman, 2012, p.35). Quantitative research approach generalizes whole population or a sub-population in order to collect a large sample (Carr, 1994), and this method can be used to quantify attitudes, opinions and behaviours of individuals. This quantifiable data can be used to articulate facts and reveal patterns in the study. Thus, results can be derived from the use of statistical and mathematical tools through quantitative method. Beside sampling, quantitative data is less time consuming, because it can use the statistical software (Such as SPSS) to analyse the data (Connolly, 2007).

The nature of this study requires a large sample of a population, which is only possible through quantitative approach and the speed in which researcher can design and implement is a major advantage of quantitative method. For example, there are several standardised tools available for survey research to measure relevant construct that can help to develop questionnaires quickly, data can be gathered at low cost rapidly via online surveys, and then collected data can be analysed swiftly by using statistical software. In contrast with qualitative method, the quantitative research has appeared a higher quality of research evidence in some disciplines (Bowling, 2005), which makes it easier to publish research results in better quality journals. Moreover, the results gained through quantitative data help the researcher to choose appropriate statistical tests to use and thus, further data interpreting and presenting the findings will be straightforward. This data will be more reliable and less open to argument and subjectivity.

3.7 Data collection: Quantitative Study

As mentioned above, quantitative research method will be used to collect the data through releasing an online survey to test the following three objectives:

1. To determine the impact of social media on Brand awareness in today’s modern world.
2. To review the individual characteristics in terms of brands, which helps SMEs to reach their potential consumers and engage them through social media.
3. To give some policy recommendations and suggestions in the light of estimated findings, which saves SMEs from expected damages and help them to reach their potential customers.

Online survey is considered as an effective method in quantitative study (Ho and Dempsey, 2010). According to Leeflang et al., (2014), an online survey technique is widely used in consumer and marketing research to perceive latent variables identified in the proposed conceptual model. Studies show that this technique is usually used to detect antecedent factors and consumer value creation engagement, for instance, to collect large amount of quality data, Carbonell and Rodrigurz-Escudero (2014), Groeger et al., (2016), Buonincontri et al., (2017), Laud and Karpen (2017), Taghizadeh et al., (2016), Nambisan and Baron (2009) and Fuller et al., (2009) had conducted online surveys. It is widely believed that the relationships between antecedents and results of consumer engagement (the logic, attitudes, behaviours, and intentions of the individuals) can be precisely measured by statistically analysing the quantitative results.

The investigator can gain easily excess to several online platforms such as social media networks, emails and virtual communities to build a link with the target respondents if his target respondents used these online channels frequently (Wang et al., 2012; Chu and Kim, 2011). As the target respondents are users of social media platforms, therefore, this method is considered as one of the relevant reasons to use online survey approach for this research. Hence, an online survey distributed by social networking sites is considered as the most appropriate way to reach a large number of target consumers without being limited to a certain geographical location. An online survey does not require to be printed or posted to target consumers, so it is appeared as a low-cost method of releasing questionnaires through online platforms (Llieva et al., 2002). As compared to other survey forms, an online survey provides flexibility to participants, and individuals can respond in their chosen time. According to Burns and Bush (2000), due to flexibility of online survey method, it leads to higher response rate as compared to other methods.

Survey Monkey an online survey tool is used to collect the data, the link for this survey will be shared through email, social platforms (such as Facebook, Whats app). After collecting the responses on Survey Monkey, this collected responses then will be directly exported into SPSS (quantitative data analysis software), which improves the accuracy and efficiency of data processing. Furthermore, in order to ensure that participant who have already completed the survey will not be able to respond questionnaire twice, this survey tool will detect each respondent's IP address.

An online survey provides several advantages, nevertheless, it also come with few criticisms, as this method does not offer guarantee of responses quality from respondents

(LLieva et al., 2002). According to McDaniel and Gates (2013), a researcher is unable to offer guidance instantly in case if participants have any misconceptions and queries during completing the survey, and it can affect on the quality of the collected data. It has emerged that even though contact details of the researcher are provided to each participant at the beginning of the survey, however, most of the time participants tend to skip the questions or withdraw if they face any issue during the process of completing the questionnaire. Hence, Wright (2005) point out that response rate has huge impact on the quality of online survey. The researcher provides a precise online survey design to ensure the high quality of the questionnaire based on the critical evaluations of the online surveys. The process of conducting the online survey that includes survey design, data collection and data analysis can be seen as below.

3.7.1 Questionnaire design:

It is a multi-stage process that involves attentions to several details at once. Wright (2005) illustrates that designing the questionnaire carefully based on a deep understanding of the current study topic and problems is a fundamental step to conduct an online survey. This self-administrated online survey involves four sections. The purpose of the first section is to gain the demographic and personal information from the participants through related questions, that are participant's gender, age, education, occupation, income, expenditure on online shopping and their social media activities.

The second section aims is to understand the factors and individuals' logic to use the social media channels. The aim of the section three is to recognise the individuals' actions on the social media and measure the factors that motivate them to engage with the activities of the social media networks marketing. Then fourth section aims to identify the major categories of social media marketing activities generated by brands to attract and engage modern consumers, which involves the participants' frequency of checking information about the brands products and services on social media channels. The main purpose of the last three sections is to gain better understanding and insight into the relationship between the consumer's behaviour or logic and the influences of brands customer engagement activities on these social networking sites. The researcher has decided to follow the paradigm developed by Churchill (1979) to select the domain of constructs as well as the initial measurement items to develop a set of valid and reliable survey measures.

3.7.2 Initial pool of items:

It is essential to collect and organize a variety of initial items including the measures of indicator variables and latent variables after the identifying the domain of constructs. Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer (2001) demonstrate that it is essential to choose the appropriate items which are aligned with the current study because a single item from the variables can lead to different outcomes especially in the formative measurement model. Studies illustrate that the measurement items must avoid double-barreled items, extremely lengthy items, ambiguously defined items and lack of readable items (Noar, 2003). In this research, multiple items generated from the relevant literature were captured and refined to suit the context of the research. In the next step, to ensure the accuracy and consistency for operationalizing the constructs, a content adequacy assessment of selected and refined measurement items will be conducted. Assessment results of these items will be described

in the next section.

3.7.3 Content adequacy assessment:

Studies highlight that it is useful to check the measurement items suitability before sending the survey to target individuals (DeVellis, 2012). Similarly, scholars added that it is essential carrying out a survey content assessment to recognize and remove and difficulties which may occur (Malhotra and Bricks, 2007). Therefore, the aim of this assessment is:

- To make sure that items specific description represents the domain of the constructs.
- To check the layout, the clarity of wording and the completion time of the questionnaire.

It is widely believed that it is useful to employ a convenient sample in a pilot test that can be outside the target individuals (Hennink et al., 2011). Based on the above suggestion, the researcher decided to ask for feedback from 7 doctorate students who were conducting different studies at the University of the West of Scotland, 3 professors, and 5 other individuals. Research suggests that academics always play an essential role of judge for assessing survey based on their professional knowledge (Sweeney and Soutar, 2001), therefore, researcher asked the academic students for feedback. These students were required to assess and comment on each item and sections such as suggestion regarding questionnaires' structure, layout and clarity.

The pilot survey invitation was sent through emails and other social media platforms such as Facebook and WhatsApp to conduct a survey assessment. The researcher collected the feedbacks and suggestions for these individuals and made appropriate changes in questionnaire structure accordingly. The pilot survey feedback helped the research to make some minor changes and corrections for the main survey.

3.7.4 Sampling strategy:

It is essential to consider a target population into account before the releasing the questionnaire (Neuman, 2013). Quantitative study sample can be described as the segment of chosen participants that can represent the characteristics of the entire population (Fowler, 2013). According to Kothari (2004), different strategies of sampling can influence differently in the procedure of selecting a sample. Probability and non-probability sampling are two major types of sampling methods (Fowler, 2013). Probability sampling can be

defined as “a segment of the population that has been chosen using a random selection approach” (Bryman and Bell 2007, p. 182). In this method, anyone can be selected from the whole population. This technique has been appeared as costly and time-consuming as compared to non-probability sample technique. On the other side, in the non-probability sampling method, the sample is selected by the researcher based on his subjective judgement according to his research. Non-probability sampling is simply based on subjective selection standards that select the sample from a target population rather than random population (Teddlie and Yu, 2007). This method suggests that there is higher possibility of selecting some target units than others. Research show that non-probability technique of sampling offers a sufficient sample with appropriate characteristics that are required for the research (Black, 1999). The results from the target participants through non-probability sampling can generate the reliable and useful research findings. Hence, the researcher has decided to use non-probability sampling approach in this study.

According to Onwuegbuzie and Collins (2007), non-probability sampling approach can be classified into four types that are purposive, quota, convenience and snowball sampling. In purposive sampling method, a researcher selects the criteria which is most appropriate for the purpose of a research (Sandelowski, 2000). Quota sampling allows the investigator to target the sample based on the geographic location such as region, cities and countries (Sudman and Blair, 1999). Convenience sampling aims to identify and employ participants who are easily accessible (Onwuegbuzie and Collins, 2007). Snowball sampling method aims to identify the target sample for the research within the social networks of the researcher, then these participants help to spread the survey invitation by sending to their online social communities (Biernacki and Waldorf, 1981). The Snowball sampling technique also known as “chain referral sample”. Due to not having any geographical restriction, snowball sampling technique is considered as very effective and useful (Biernacki and Waldorf, 1981). As the target sample for this study was social media users and online communities, therefore, snowball and purposive sampling strategies were adopted in this research according to the understanding of different sampling strategies.

Firstly, researcher prepared a list of requirements for participants’ selection to identify the purposive sample. Contestants were asked to withdraw the survey if they did not meet the specific criteria. Snowball sampling technique was used to collect the response of the survey. The sample frame and size are discussed in the following sections.

3.7.4.1 Sample frame:

A sample frame is a criteria of sample selection that are designed to identify the target population based on the research context and the research purpose (Llieva et al., 2002). As this research focuses on modern consumer engagement through activities of social media marketing, thus, the following measures were set as the sample frame for this research:

- Consumers who use social media channels
- Age between 18 and 40
- Individuals who are willing to share their opinions and experiences about the social media and brands.

This research focuses on those consumers who use social media in order to check whether they like to engage in social media marketing activities with brands or not. Therefore, only those consumers are selected from the population who use social media. Furthermore, this study concentrates on adult modern consumers, so age group between 18-40 is selected for the participants, and under 18 young people are considered as children or minorities in some countries and collecting the data from them would require some extra precautions.

3.7.4.2 Sample size:

Sample size of a research is considered as an essential element to conduct equation modelling due to its huge impact on gaining reliable outcomes (Hair et al., 2006). Studies highlight that size of a sample needs to be ten times larger than the constructs that are being tested in the researcher (Sue and Ritter, 2011). Evan and Mathur (2005) suggest that 5-10 valid response per variable are required till up to 300. Hinkin et al., (1997) recommend that the measuring items to sample size needs to be 1:4 or 1:5, while Hair et al., point out that the sample size for structural equation modelling should be around 150-400. Nevertheless, this research adopts a common equation which is developed by Cochran (1977) to obtain a precise sample size number (see equation below).

$$N = \frac{z^2(pq)}{e^2}$$

In this equation,

N: refers to the sample size of the research

z: refers to the selected confidence level

p: refers to the estimate of variance

q: equals to 1-p

e: refers to margin of error

Equation for calculating sample size (Cochran, 1977)

The aim of the current study is to achieve a 95% confidence level that is also recommended by Burns and Bush (2000). This also takes 5% margin of error and 50% variance into the account. The recommended sample size of this research is 384 based on the above calculation. From the above suggestion, the study aims to collect 400 minimum valid and usable responses from individuals.

3.8 Data collection process:

In this study, the procedure of data collection for online survey consists of two parts, pilot test and main online survey. Evan and Mathur (2005) suggest that in order to create a well-written online survey with specific questions and clear measurement items, it is important to conduct a pilot test using sampling strategies and sample frame prior to releasing the main survey. A pilot test offers a researcher to evaluate the reliability of the measurement items as well as to eliminate the low factor loading items. According to Zikmund (2003), preliminary findings and refinement of the questionnaire for the main survey is possible based on the pilot test results. The process of conducting pilot test and the main online survey is described in the following sub-sections.

3.8.1 Pilot test:

Andrews et al., (2007) recommends carrying out a small-scale pilot test to test the statistical properties of the measurement items before releasing the main survey to the large sample. Pilot test sample size can be about 10% of the whole sample (Pavlou and EL Sawy, 2011). Fink (2015) suggested that pilot test sample size between 10-40 is acceptable. Similarly, studies also recommend that sample size of pilot test survey can be generally small (De Vaus, 2013). Therefore, it is decided to conduct a pilot survey for this study with a target to get between 10-15 valid responses. After the pilot test result, few questionnaires were removed and rearranged due to low quality response and unrelated questions in order to provide better reliable and useful results for the remaining measurements items. As a result, the final version of online survey was released to send out to the large target population.

3.8.2 Main online survey:

Firstly, an invitation for the online survey was posted through the Survey Monkey using emails and other social media channels (e.g., Facebook, Viber, WhatsApp), using the snowball sampling strategy to contact target respondents. A cover letter on the front page of survey can help to get a higher response rate (Dillman, 2011). Thus, a cover page was shown to all the Participants, clearly stating the survey purpose and respondents' conditions before they enter the online survey with close-ended questions. These target individuals were asked to share the online survey with their friends and other online community groups.

Studies demonstrate that individuals tend to take part to those surveys that they have interest or concerned about that particular topic (Saunders et al., 2007). Therefore, it may enhance the response rate if the survey release to the community with similar taste to the study. The main survey was released on different social media platforms and through emails.

3.8.3 Response rate:

Response rate plays an essential part in data collection process, and it is calculated by the dividing the useable/reliable responses returned by the total number of eligible in the chosen sample. It is extremely important to receive a high response rate (Saunders et al., 2009). Furthermore, a researcher is required to undertake data cleaning by checking the collected responses (Fan and Yan's, 2010). A researcher needs to exclude the unusable data such as incomplete responses, little variance of the answers and many missing responses.

3.9 Data analysis technique:

The descriptive and multiple regression model based on different variables approach were employed by applying SPSS software to rigorously analyses the collected quantitative data from the online survey. Firstly, for the expressive clarification of results, this research utilized descriptive statistics to find percentage and frequencies associated with brand awareness. Secondly, Inferential statistics, multiple regression model was used on different variable through SPSS software.

3.9.1 Inferential statistics:

Multiple Regression Examination states to a set of procedures for studying the straight-line associations between two or more variables. Multiple regressions guess the β 's in the equation

$$y_j = B_0 + \beta_1 x_{1j} + \beta_2 x_{2j} + \dots + \beta_p x_{pj} + \varepsilon_j \quad (1)$$

In above equation X's represent the explanatory variables and Y is the dependent variable. The subscript j denotes the opinion (row) number. The β 's are the unidentified regression factors. Their estimations are characterized by b's. Each β characterizes the unique unknown parameter, while b is an assessment of this β . The ε_j is the residual of reflection j. While the regression problematic may be resolved by different techniques, the most-popular technique is least squares. In least squares examination, the b's are nominated to reduce the summation of the squared residuals. This set of b's is not certainly the set you need, since they might be inaccurate by outliers--points that are not illustrative of the statistics. Robust regression, another to least squares, pursues to decrease the inspiration of outliers. Multiple regression examination studies the association between a dependent variable and independent variables. The model multiple regression comparison is

$$Y_j = b_0 + b_1 x_{1j} + b_2 x_{2j} + \dots + b_p x_{pj} \quad (2)$$

If $p = 1$, then a model is called simple linear regression.

The intercept, b_0 , is that point, at which, the regression level crosses the Y axis. The b_i are the inclines of the regression level in the way of x_i . These constants are called the fractional-regression coefficients. All fractional regression coefficients characterize the net result the i^{th} variable has on the response variable, allotment the lasting X's in the equation persistent.

When the β 's has been assessed, numerous directories are deliberate to control the dependability of these estimations. One of the best widespread of these consistency catalogues are the correlation quantity. The correlation is a guide that varieties from -1 to 1. Whenever the estimated value is near to zero, there is non-linear association. As the correlation becomes nearer to +1 or -1, the affiliation is stronger. A value of one designates a perfect linear affiliation among two variables. The regression calculation is only accomplished of assessing a straight-line, associations. If a regression study would not be able to discover a relation. It is always sensible to a plot that each explanatory variable along with the response variable, inspecting for curves, remote points, variations in the quantity of inconsistency, and numerous other irregularities that might happen. If the data belongs to a random sample or a larger population and the ϵ_j are normally distributed than statistical tests might be applied.

For a good practice regarding multiple regression, you should have a simple understanding regarding linear regression model. The basic regression model is

$$y_j = B_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_p x_p + \epsilon_j \quad (3)$$

This appearance denotes the association among the response variable and the explanatory variables as a subjective average in which, the coefficients of regression (β 's) denotes as a weight. Dissimilar to the traditional weights inside the weighted average, negative regression coefficients are possible. A central assumption which belongs to this model, the outcome of every explanatory variable is preservative. Furthermore, no one considers that the exact relationship is essentially additive. Relatively, they consider this model as a rational first calculation to the correct model. Increasing the rationality to this calculation, it belongs to the Taylor-series extension of model. On the other hand, this request to the Taylor-series typically manages the 'local neighbourhood' assumption. Alternative assumption stated as the association between the dependent variable with each independent variable is linear. Again, we can say that no one considers that the affiliation is a conventional line. On the other hand, this is a rational first calculation. To attain better calculations, approaches have been established to permit regression models to estimate curvilinear associations. While non-linear regression models could be taken under consideration in these circumstances which may lead to add upper level of convolution relevant to the modelling procedure. A proficient worker of multiple regression distinguishes how to comprise curvilinear constituents in a regression model. A different issue is about adding categorical variables in the regression model. Distinct of the other

consistent numeric variables, categorical variables may be alphabetic, e.g., gender. For the effective use of multiple regression, it is necessary to understand that how to take in categorical independent variables in regression model.

3.9.1.1 Possible uses of regression analysis:

Montgomery and Peck (1982) outlines the following five purposes for running a regression analysis.

3.9.1.1.1 Description:

The predictor is looking for an equation that defines the associations in a data set. This determination makes the least number of assumptions.

3.9.1.1.2 Coefficient estimation:

Coefficient estimation is a current purpose for undertaking regression analysis. In the same way the predictor has a hypothetical association in mind, for the confirmation of this theory, regression analysis may be applied. There is definite interest in the extents of the coefficients. Commonly, this determination for regression edges with the others.

3.9.1.1.3 Prediction:

The major concern is to forecast some dependent variable, such as brand awareness, expected scores, competence, number of beds in a hospital, response produce in a chemical procedure. These estimates are very critical in preparation, observing, or evaluating some procedure. In the same way lots of assumptions and experiences that should be undertaken in this case. For example, you should not generalize elsewhere the collection of data.

3.9.1.1.4 Control:

The regression models tend to use for observing and governing a system. For instance, you might want to put a response variable in a certain strategy. Whenever anyone of regression models is used for the switch commitments, the explanatory variables should be related to the response. In the same way, this practical connection, continue with the time. If not, then continual amendment of the model should occur.

3.9.1.1.5 Variable selection or screening:

An examination is directed for those explanatory variables which explain a noteworthy amount of deviation in the response variable. In lots of applications, it is evident that it is not a one-time procedure but a continuous process of model building.

3.9.1.1.6 Assumptions:

To use multiple regression analysis, the researcher need to consider the following assumptions.

3.9.1.1.7 Linearity:

Multiple regression models should display a linear association among dependent variable and independent variable. It can be assessed by scatter plots in the econometric findings. Nonlinear patterns can also be shown in residual plots.

3.9.1.1.7 Independence:

Independence assumption can be utilised in 2 different aspects:

1. Model misspecification:

If an essential explanatory variable is absent or if an improper form is employed, then the residuals will not be stayed independent. The explanation to this problem is to catch the appropriate functional method or to contain the suitable independent variables.

2. Time-sequenced data:

When regression analysis is executed on time series data the residuals of the data set are often correlated. This existence of correlation between residuals is often called serial autocorrelation. There are two types of autocorrelations, positive of negative and both type autocorrelation leads to the violation of the assumption.

The existence of autocorrelation between the residuals creates many negative impressions:

1. In the presence of auto-correlation regression coefficients are impartial but not effective, i.e., minimum variance assessments.
2. When a positive correlation exists, it may indicate that the mean square error is extremely underestimated.

3. Any of the hypothesis testing that necessary for the use of t or F distribution become invalid.

3.9.1.1.8 Multicollinearity:

Multi-collinearity is the presence of near-linear associations between the set of explanatory variables. The presence of multi-collinearity reasons all kinds of difficulties with regression analysis, that is why it is understood that the data set do not display it properly.

3.9.1.1.9 Effects of multicollinearity:

Multi-collinearity may cause false estimations of the regression coefficients, expand the standard errors of regression coefficients, reduce the partial t -tests, gives false and non-significant p -values, and disgrace the effectiveness of the model in the sense of its predictability.

3.9.1.1.10 Sources of multicollinearity:

There are five sources of multi-collinearity which are as under

Data collection:

The collinearity leads in the data set by the sampling technique. Extracting more and more data on an extended range may cure this problem.

Physical constraints of the linear model or population:

This causes of multi-collinearity will exist, whatever the sampling procedure is used. Many service procedures may lead to the constraints on explanatory variables, which are physically, politically as well as legally and they will create collinearity.

Over-defined model:

In this situation the variables are more than observations. This kind of situation should necessarily avoid.

Model choice or specification:

This causes of multi-collinearity come into existence by using explanatory variables which have higher powers as well as we can say interactions of an actual set of different variables. It is necessary to understand here that if the sampling subspace of X_j is contracted, then any arrangement of variables with x_j may cause an increase in the multi-collinearity problem.

Outliers:

Extreme different values or we can say outliers in the scatter plot can cause multi-collinearity.

3.9.1.1.11 Detection of collinearity:

The following steps used for the detection of multi-collinearity.

1. By studying scatter plots of independent variables, in search for some perfect associations. Also scan at the correlation matrix for the reflection of high correlations. Unfortunately, collinearity does not always show by undertaking two variables at a time.
2. Next, analyse the variance inflation factors (*VIF*). If it contains large *VIF*'s indicates collinear variables.
3. Finally, consider small eigen values displays in the correlation matrix of the explanatory variables. It means that the eigen value of zero or close to zero reflects an exact linear dependency occurs. By using the condition number. Large condition numbers indicate collinearity.

3.9.1.1.12 Correction of collinearity:

There are different types of solution for the correction of multi-collinearity, it can be removed by the collection extra data over a wider x-subspace, similarly by simplifying the model by undertaking variable selection methodology, In the same way if any observation detected with collinearity, you can eliminate that observation and proceed further

3.9.1.1.13 Multiple regression technical details:

This section offering the methodological particulars of least-square regression examination, using a combination of summary and matrix notation.

$$\mathbf{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ \vdots \\ y_j \\ \vdots \\ y_N \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_{11} & \cdots & x_{1p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_{1j} & \cdots & x_{pj} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_{1N} & \cdots & x_{pN} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{e} = \begin{bmatrix} e_1 \\ \vdots \\ e_j \\ \vdots \\ e_N \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{b} = \begin{bmatrix} b_0 \\ b_1 \\ \vdots \\ b_p \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{W} = \begin{bmatrix} w_1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & 0 & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & w_j & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & 0 & 0 & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 & w_N \end{bmatrix}$$

Least squares

It can be calculated by the following equation:

$$\mathbf{b} = (\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{X})^{-1} \mathbf{X}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{Y}$$

When the weights are not used, it may reduce to following equation:

$$\mathbf{b} = (\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X})^{-1} \mathbf{X}'\mathbf{Y}$$

For prediction of values for response variable

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbf{b}'\mathbf{X}$$

To calculate the residuals by following equation

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{Y} - \hat{\mathbf{Y}}$$

Estimated variances

Following formula used for the variance estimation of the residuals

$$s^2 = \frac{\mathbf{e}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{e}}{N - p - 1}$$

Following formula used for the variance estimation of the regression models

$$V \begin{pmatrix} b_0 \\ b_1 \\ \vdots \\ b_p \end{pmatrix} = s^2 (\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{X})^{-1}$$

Variance estimation for predicted mean of Y Values with specific values of X e.g., X_0

$$s_{Y_m|X_0}^2 = s^2 (1, X_0) (\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{X})^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ X_0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Variance estimation for predicted value of Y for a particular value of X, say X_0

$$s_{Y_l|X_0}^2 = s^2 + s_{Y_m|X_0}^2$$

Hypothesis tests of the intercept and slopes

Hypothesis tests could be created by using Student's t distribution with $N - p - 1$ degrees of freedom, with the help of following formula

$$t_{b_i} = \frac{b_i - B_i}{s_{b_i}}$$

Confidence intervals of the intercept and slope

A100 $(1-\alpha)$ % confidence interval for true regression coefficients

$$b_i \pm (t_{1-\alpha/2, N-p-1}) s_{b_i}$$

Confidence interval of Y for given X

A $100(1-\alpha)$ % Confidence interval for the mean of Y at the particular value of X i.e., X_0 may calculated by following formula

$$b'X_0 \pm (t_{1-\alpha/2, N-p-1})s_{Y_m|X_0}$$

A $100(1-\alpha)$ % forecast interval for Y value of a separate at a particular value of X, say X_0 , is give as under

$$b'X_0 \pm (t_{1-\alpha/2, N-p-1})s_{Y_f|X_0}$$

R2 (Percent of variation explained)

R2, formally recognized as coefficient of determination, is explained as the sum of squares divided by adjusted total sum of squares of Y:

$$R^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{e'We}{Y'WY - \frac{(1'WY)^2}{1'W1}} \right)$$
$$= \frac{SS_{Model}}{SS_{Total}}$$

Till here study discussed some necessary theoretical regression analysis and some technical details of regression analysis, and the below purposed model was used to interpret the original findings by defining variables theoretically and to reveal the econometric results.

$$Y = \alpha + \beta X + \mu$$

Where; “Y” is a variable which is dependent.

“ α ” is a constant.

“β” is a coefficient of independent variables.

“x” is an independent variable.

“μ” is an Error term.

Established on the certain variables, the multiple regression equation of this study will be:

$$Z = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \epsilon_i$$

Purposed model:

$$B.A = \alpha + \beta_1 (USM) + \beta_2 (ADV) + \beta_3 (MSOS) + \beta_4 (NCR) + \beta_5 (BU) + \beta_6 (SOH) + \mu$$

The following sections provides the data analysis process of quantitative data for pilot test survey and the main survey.

3.9.2 Data analysis for pilot test:

The term of data analysis can be defined as a process of transforming, cleaning, and modelling the data in order to get useful results and information. DeVellis (2016) suggests that after collecting the data the first step should be conducting a reliability assessment of measurement items. Hair et al., (2006) also added that reliability assessment is an essential element in the study to apply in order to evaluate the measurement items. Since these measurement items are consistent with the selected variables, so it is necessary to validate the reliability of the items (Netemeyer et al., 2003). This statement is well supported by DeVellis (2016) and Hair et al., (2006) by saying that Cronbach’s alpha was used to evaluate the measurement items consistency with selected variables. Research suggest that Cronbach’s alpha of a measuring items can be considered as satisfactory to employ in the survey if it is equal or greater than 0.70 (Hair et al., 2006). It indicates that items cannot be adequate to measure the corresponding construct if Cronbach’s alpha measuring item is lower than 0.70.

The second step in this phase of data analysis involves conducting exploratory factor

analysis (EFA). As per noted by Hair et al., (2006), the main aim of conducting EFA is to remove the irrelevant measurement items, refine the dimensions of each construct and obtain better manageable structure for further model testing. In order to extract the items in EFA the principal component analysis and varimax rotation are selected. The purpose of varimax rotation is to identify if the factor is cross loaded in the multi-components, and the key aim of component analysis is to cut down the number of variables by developing linear combinations which maintains as much of the original construct's variance as possible (Hair et al., 2006). Items can be removed if the factor loading of the item is lower than 0.40 (Conway and Huffcutt, 2003).

3.9.3 Data analysis for main online survey:

The reliability assessment and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) were conducted again with the main large survey sample even though the constructs and measurement items were already validated during the data analysis of the pilot test (Hair et al., 2006). Conducting confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is considered as one of the essential steps for the main data analysis. Gaskin and Happell (2014) state that the aim of the CFA is to evaluate the relationship between the whole structural mode and the constructs, which helps to confirm the hypothesis of the predicted relationship among observed variable and latent variable (Backhaus et al., 2010). Then the structural path of final model is established.

3.10 Limitations of method:

There are some limitations of the selected quantitative (online survey) research methods. In terms of the online survey, all the measurement items are adapted from previous empirical studies. However, as few empirical studies attempted to examine the customer engagement through social networking platforms, including its antecedents and the types of dialogic co-creation activities and its consequences, the selected measurement items may not comprehensively reflect the phenomenon in this research context. Although these measurement items have yielded high factor loadings in previous studies, when they serve a different research context, they may generate different results.

3.11 Ethics:

Ethics are considered as an essential element in all type of research particularly in

quantitative research method. It can be described as “ethics are the utilisation of moral principle in planning, conducting and reporting the results of research studies” (McNabb, 2008, p20). According to Miller et al., (2008), ethics are important, because it restricts to investigators to handle the collected information in a right way. Researchers need to take in their account multiple consideration such as privacy, honesty, plagiarism while data collection (Myers and Klein, 2011).

The questionnaires were designed in ethical way to avoid participants personal information. It was totally depending on individual’s willingness whether they want to take part or not, and no one was forced to participate. In addition, all questionnaires were lawful, and all questions were relevant to the academic fundamentals (Saunders et al., 2007). In addition, respondents’ information will not be published, and researcher will respect their opinions and views and will not create any harm towards their personal interests. All the personal and relevant information gathered through interviews and questionnaires will be securely deleted (Data Protection Act, 1998). Everything will be conducted according to ethics regulation of UWS.

3.11 Summary:

The above chapter outlined the research methodology used in this thesis based on a justified philosophical stance. The quantitative (online survey) study was conducted through online survey. A pilot test was released to 15 participants in which 12 valid responses were collected. The purpose of pilot test was to ensure the measurement items were reliable and valid and to remove irrelevant measurement items. The remaining items were included in the main survey for which 400 valid answers were expected. The descriptive and inferential statistics approaches were used to analyse the quantitative data. The next chapter will highlight the findings for the quantitative data.

Chapter 4: Research Findings

4.1 Introduction:

This chapter describes the crucial findings of the main survey in form of descriptive and inferential statistics, and the results of pilot survey can be seen in Appendix D. The results of the main survey and pilot survey have tried to answer the research questions as below:

1. How does social media influence today's world?
2. How do social media sites impact on individual's lives in terms of consumer engagement and brand awareness?
3. How social media can help SMEs to engage modern consumers?
4. How can SMEs create brand awareness through social media networks?
5. What are the possible risks and threats towards a brand image?
6. What policy should be implemented through social media towards brand image in connection with potential customers?

4.2 Descriptive analysis:

For the analysis of data and expressive clarifications of results, the study has utilised descriptive statistics to find percentages and frequencies associated with brand awareness. The frequency defined as “the total occurrences of an event repeatedly in particular study” while the percentage calculated with the help of following formula.

$$P = F/N * 100$$

Where:

F = Frequency of class

N = Total number of observations

P = Percentage

Graph 1:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 399

Skipped: 23

The purpose of including both genders is to get more accurate results which reflect the significant findings of the econometric model and descriptive findings which may lead towards effective policy that help SMEs in terms of capturing more customers. The study has included 214 males which is about 53.63% of total respondents, and about 180 females which are about 45.11% of the sample size, whereas 23 people skipped this question and only 5 of them mentioned that they do not want to reveal their gender.

Graph 2:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 403

Skipped: 19

Occupation plays an important role of interest in online shopping; therefore, it was necessary to ask people about their occupation. The above graph shows that about 30% of people are employed and 20.35% are self-employed. About 41 people who are about 10.17% of sample size, said that they are engaged in part time jobs. The higher ratio which is about 32.51% of people, said that they are students only while 6.95% people said that they are not working currently.

Graph 3:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 401

Skipped: 21

Income is considered as a key factor for online shopping (Hernandez et al., 2011). The Graph 3 describes that 21.95% of respondents earn less than £10,000 yearly, and most of respondents' salaries are between £10,000 and £29,999 yearly which is about 25.69%. Furthermore, 8.73% individuals earn between £30,000 to £39,999, 3.99% of them falls in over £40,000 category, 24.69% people are not working at the moment, and 14.96% people did not prefer to say about their income.

Graph 4:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 399

Skipped: 23

To recognise the psychology of people related to fashion brands it is necessary to ask people that how often they interact or engage with fashion brands activities on social media channels, because it reflects the interest of customers towards the fashion brands. The above graph 4 reflects that 26.07% people engaged with social media activities many times per day and a higher ratio of 32.08% people interact with brands once or twice per day. The result shows that 17.29% of total sample size interacts with fashion brands 3 to 5 times during a week, 10.28% once in a week and about 14.29% people interact with fashion brands less than once a week.

Graph 5:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 400

Skipped: 22

In today's digital age, there are lots of social media sites like YouTube, Twitter and Facebook etc. So, the researcher has tried to assess that what category of social media is more likely to be used by the respondents to stay updated with the brands. Analysis reflects (Graph, 5) that 58.50% prefer to use YouTube as well as the second most used social media site is Facebook which have 50.75% respondents. Furthermore google+ have 19.50% of users while my space contains a very little ratio of 3.00% people, the trend for using Tagged is only 1.75% which is most less among all other defined categories. Instagram have 47.50% respondents, whereas TikTok, Twitter and LinkedIn have 16.75%, 14.75% and 5.75% users respectively, and about 1.25% respondents uses other social platforms.

Graph 6:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 371

Skipped: 51

Social media has become an essential driving factor in fashion marketing, and modern consumers are interested in social interaction on digital platforms, particularly engaging in a set of social media marketing activities that are facilitated by fashion brands (Kontu and Vecchi, 2014). The above graph 6 shows that 21.56%, 35.58% and 26.15% people use social media very likely, likely, and somewhat likely respectively, to gather brand information on social media platforms. On the other hand, the ratio of people who use social media neither likely nor unlikely for above mentioned purpose is about 7.55%, whereas 3.77% somewhat unlikely, 3.23% unlikely and 2.16% very unlikely use social media sites to gather product information.

Graph 7:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 369

Skipped: 53

As discussed in previous findings, to assess whether people find product information through social media or not, in connection with our previous argument it is necessary to know that which source is mostly used by the people to find product information. In this modern era, networking and micro blogging platforms such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter are the most commonly used social media sites, thus, 51.49% people from the survey also use these sources to find product information. In addition, above graph 7 shows that 29.00% individuals find information through E-commerce sites such as Amazon and eBay, and 27.10% respondents prefer to obtain information from brand websites such as Apple. Another important source of finding information is video sharing sites like YouTube, 33.60% people said that they like to find desired information through consumer generated videos. Tv, radio, news channels and other sources have small ratios of 8.67% and 1.63% respectively.

Graph 8:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 370

Skipped: 52

It is essential for SMEs to understand the consumer's behaviour toward product reviews. Finding shows that 28.11% people very likely, a higher ratio of 41.89% people likely and moderate ratio of 18.65% respondents somewhat likely read product reviews. Further findings shows that 4.59% and 2.16% people review the product neither likely nor unlikely and somewhat likely, respectively. Finally, a small portion of 3.24% and 1.35% respondents read product reviews unlikely and very unlikely before making a purchase.

Graph 9:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 355

Skipped: 67

Previous findings show that individuals use social media and other online sites to read product reviews, but the question is, do they believe in those reviews? To find out, study has asked respondents about this scenario and collected 355 responses which provides a clear picture, that shows 11.55% strongly agree with the authentication of reviews on social media sites. Above Graph 9 illustrates that higher percentage 38.87% and 33.24% of respondents agree and somewhat agreed with the above statement. A 12.39% people say that they are neither agree nor disagree regarding reviews given on online social sites. results also show that the people who are somewhat disagree, disagree and strongly disagree have a small ratio of 1.13%, 2.54% and 0.28% respectively.

Graph 10:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 370

Skipped: 52

Previously we have discussed about product information, sources of product information and about product reviews, but people also use social media for other purposes like to find new trends rather than to find specific product information. So, by keeping in view above discussion the study intends to know the various reasons of using social media in terms of product and services. The results from the graph 10 indicate that 36.68% people use social media to look for the product sales/offers, while a major portion of 40.49% people find product information through social media. Furthermore, 39.13% respondents use these sites to read product reviews, 33.97% of them to follow trends and 16.03% participants use social platforms to find brands information. A small ratio of 7.88% and 1.36% of individuals use social media to engage with brands and for other reasons, respectively.

Graph 11:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 367

Skipped: 55

To know about the customer perception, that either information on social media is trustworthy to them or not, this study added a question in the survey. The findings of the above graph 11 indicate that 10.08% of individuals are strongly agreed, 38.15% are agreed and 35.97% are somewhat agreed with the statement that provided information on social media is trustworthy. A portion of 10.90% people neither agree nor disagree with the above statement. On the other hand, a small ratios 1.91%, 2.72% and 0.27% of participants are somewhat disagreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed with the above-mentioned statement.

Graph 12:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 363

Skipped: 59

The graph 12 reveals that 12.40% people very likely, 39.12% likely and 31.40% somewhat likely get enough information through social media to make purchase decision. A portion of 11.29% individuals fall in neither likely nor unlikely category. Results further reveal that only 2.20% participants say that they usually get the required information somewhat unlikely, and study also labelled two more categories of Unlikely and very Unlikely, having ratios of 2.75% and 0.83% respectively.

Graph 13:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 365

Skipped: 57

The above graph 13 has tried to explore the cluster of respondents by asking them whether their friends share experiences on social media sites or not. Findings demonstrate that 12.60% respondents said that their friends share their experiences on social media sites very likely. A higher ratio of 29.04% and 31.78% participants confess that their friends are likely and somewhat likely share their experiences on social media sites. Graph 13 also shows the category of neither likely nor unlikely having 12.33% respondents. On the other side, about 7.95%, 4.66% and 1.64% contestants believe that their friends share their purchase experiences with the brands on social media platform somewhat unlikely, unlikely and very unlikely, respectively.

Graph 14:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 364

Skipped: 58

The above graph 14 results illustrate the customer behaviour towards the brands and new products' information gathering source. Findings show that 20.33% participants say that they preferred TV and radio to know about new brand and products, whereas a very high intense ratio of 80.22% people clearly vote in the favour of social media channels on this argument. Print media like newspaper gone old fashion in the sense of collecting information regarding brands, it also indicates from our findings and clearly illustrate that only 6.59% people in this category. As compared to newspaper, advertisement on banners is still moving in, having 13.74% people while a tiny ratio of 0.55% use other sources to collect information for new products and brands.

Graph 15:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 365

Skipped: 57

The above graph 15 compares the different methods used by modern consumers/respondents to get in touch with brands. It shown in our previous findings social media channels have high intensity, in this case study findings repeat the trend and social media channels place at first with 64.93% people. Emails is easily accessible by the people; anyone can register with his/her desired brands to get updates. So, it is revealed by the study that 47.12% participants says that they prefer email to obtain information of desired brands. Findings reveal a very small ratio of 10.68% people who preferred phone, 15.07% people prefer post, and the remaining 1.37% people prefer other sources to get in touch with brands.

Graph 16:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 355

Skipped: 67

SMEs use different mediums like TV, radio, newspaper, and obviously social media to transfer products knowledge among consumers. The study has tried to compare different sources to describe which is better and more expressive towards customers in terms of their preference. The findings from the above graph 16 show that 19.44% people strongly agree in the sense of executing advertisement and brand messages on social media sites. A high bracket of 46.48% participants reflects that they are agree on the argument illustrated above. Similarly, some 22.25% of them somewhat agree to this debate. 7.04% of people among those participants who are neither agreed nor disagreed. However, results also reveal that about 1.69%, 2.25% and 0.85% of respondents are somewhat disagreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement that advertising and brand messages are better on social media networks. From the above graph 16 results, it is evident that participants believe that advertising and promotions on the social media channels are better as compared to old fashioned and traditional ways of marketing such as TV and magazines, which also suggested by many scholars in the literature of the study (Berthon et al., 2012; O’leary, 2011; Hanna et al., 2011; Ashley and Tuten, 2015)

Graph 17:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 355

Skipped: 67

The study has tried to analyse here that after using a product, either a customer likes to recommend it to his/her friends or family member or not. As shown in the above graph 17, findings reveal that about 18.87% people strongly agree that worthy products should be recommended to closely related people while traditionally a large proportion of 42.54% people are also agree in the sense of recommending products to their relations. 28.17% people says that they are somewhat agree for recommendation of products. A small portion of 5.63% respondents are neither agree nor disagree with the debate. Moreover, the individuals who disagree with the above statement are 1.13%, 3.10% and 0.56%, respectively.

Graph 18:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 355

Skipped: 67

To analyse the behaviour of people about recommended products, the researcher has asked individuals whether they buy a product or service that is recommended by their friends or family members. Statistics reveal that 21.41% and 38.87% people are strongly agreed and agreed on recommendations. Furthermore 25.63% participants are somewhat agreed, and 9.01% people are neither agreed nor disagreed with the above statement. Moving on opposite direction of disagreement, study reveals 1.69% people are somewhat disagreed while 2.82% participants are disagreed and finally 0.56% people are strongly disagreed.

Graph 19:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 354

Skipped: 68

Buying decision based on different scenarios, some people buy products by reading reviews or some of them preferred family or friend's recommendations, similarly, in our society some people want only expert opinion before buying anything particularly new products. It is appeared from the findings as shown in the above graph 19, that 13.56%, 31.64% and 33.62% participants are strongly agreed, agreed and somewhat agreed respectively with the above-mentioned statement. By exploring further, 11.30% people, neither agree nor disagree about excavating expert judgments through social media. On the other hand, a small cluster of 3.95% are somewhat disagreed but 4.80% and 1.13% percipients are disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

Graph 20:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 355

Skipped: 67

Another important aspect of individuals buying behaviour in today's modern age is consumer generated contents, as these contents reviews are considered as valuable source of information for other individuals regarding online purchase decision (Ghose et al., 2009). It is clear from the above graph 20, that 10.42% people strongly agree, in the same perspective study reveals almost two uniform proportions 31.55% and 31.27% agree and somewhat agree respectively, and a percentage of 17.75% participants are neither agree nor disagree with the above argument. Moreover, results also show that 3.66% participants are somewhat disagreed, 3.94% are disagreed and a very small ratio of 1.41% individuals strongly disagreed regarding buying product recommended through consumer generated contents. These user generated contents allows users to make comments and provide feedbacks on the particular products or services in various forms such as video and blogs, and these contents are believed as high degree of credibility in the customer's eyes (Filho and Tan, 2009).

Graph 21:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 354

Skipped: 68

The above graph 21 shows that 11.30% participants are strongly agreed, 30.51% individuals are agreed, and 28.53% of respondents are somewhat agreed that they share their positive experience on social media sites. About 16.10% people neither agreed nor disagreed with the above-mentioned statement. On the other hand, study explores a proportion of people who are 7.63%, indicates somewhat disagree in sharing their experiences with brands. Similarly, 5.08% and 0.85% respondents are disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

Graph 22:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 353

Skipped: 69

Experience plays an important role in understanding that how a customer understands, assess, and reacts towards a brand (Andreini et al., 2018). Previous finding represents the individuals' sharing behaviour of a positive experience (Graph 21), and the graph 22 shows the outcomes of the individual's tendency towards sharing negative experiences with other online communities. Findings reveal that 16.43% are strongly agreed about sharing negative experience of product. Similarly, a moderate proportion of people are also agreed and some of them are somewhat agreed on sharing negative experiences, having ratios of 29.75% and 27.48%, respectively. A neutral cluster of people also exist with 16.71%, who neither agree nor disagree with the ongoing discussion. On the other side, study reveals that 2.55% are somewhat disagreed while 4.82% and 2.27% are disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

Graph 23:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 355

Skipped: 67

Statistics (Graph 23) shows that 9.01%, 27.61% and 28.73% respondents are strongly agreed, agreed and somewhat agreed to the statement that they are loyal to particular brands. Another moderate ratio of people exist who are neither agree nor disagree with the debate, having 19.15% respondents. A portion of 8.73% people says that they are somewhat disagreed with loyalty towards specific brands. Furthermore, above graph 23 result states that 5.63% people are disagreed and a small proportion of 1.13% participants are strongly disagreed to the above phenomenon.

Graph 24:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 355

Skipped: 67

A total of 355 responses have been collected to find out if individuals enjoy gathering brand and product information on social media networks. Findings reveal that 14.63% people strongly agree with the statement that they enjoy gathering brands and products information from social networking sites. A massive number of respondents also agree and somewhat agree, having ratios of 32.96% and 30.99%, and 12.68% individuals fall in neutral category 'neither agree nor disagree'. On the other side, small ratios of 4.79%, 2.54% and 1.13% participants somewhat disagree, disagree and strongly disagree, respectively.

Graph 25:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 355

Skipped: 67

Findings reveal that 13.52%, 39.44% and 21.13% of respondents strongly agree, agree and somewhat agree that they look for international brands and new products information on social media networking sites. Study also shows the neutral respondents who are neither agreed nor disagreed, having 15.77% people. Oppositely, a small ratio of 4.23% respondents say that they are somewhat disagreed on this question of discussion. Moving further, the graph 25 also illustrates that 3.66% and 2.25% of individuals disagree and strongly disagree, respectively with the above-mentioned statement.

Graph 26:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 355

Skipped: 67

The above graph 26 illustrates individuals' perception that if they find easy to get the most recent information regarding brands on social media channels. Findings demonstrate that 18.87% people strongly agree, a high bracket of 41.69% participants agree and 26.48% of individuals somewhat agree with the above-mentioned statement. The result further show that a 7.89% of people neither agree nor disagree to this argument. Moving further, study reveals that about 3.10% people somewhat disagree, 1.41% respondents clearly disagree, and an insignificant proportion of individuals which is about 0.56% strongly disagree with the current ongoing argument, and they find it hard to obtain latest information on social media platforms.

Graph 27:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 354

Skipped: 68

Exploring another aspect of the study, the researcher is trying to describe the consultation among people on sharing and tagging brand's post which possess a bunch of useful information may lead the potential customer towards their desired brands for online shopping. By analysing the results, the study reflects that 9.04% of people strongly agree that their friends and colleagues usually tag them on the brand's post that has useful information. Findings also indicate that 31.36%, 30.23% of people are agreed and somewhat agreed, and about 11.58% of people are neither agree nor disagree with this argument. Moreover, 8.47%, 6.50% and 2.82% of respondents are somewhat disagreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, which shows that their friends and colleagues do not share online information with them.

Graph 28:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 354

Skipped: 68

Time is money, we often listen to this phrase in daily life, social media is the fastest way to access brands, and it saves time and give desirable utility needs by the customer. How many people think that it saves time? The above graph 28 has tried to explore participants' insights by recording 354 answers. The results shows that 10.45% strongly agree, 40.40% agree and 27.97% of respondents somewhat agree with the phenomena of time saving in contacting brands through social media. About 15.54% of individuals said that they neither agree nor disagree with the debate. Study also shows the ratio of those people who are somewhat disagree, disagree, and strongly disagree are having proportion of 2.54%, 1.69% and 1.41%, respectively.

Graph 29:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 354

Skipped: 68

The above graph 29 represents whether individuals prefer to know about new brands and product through social media or not. Findings show that 12.22% respondents strongly agree regarding looking for a new brand or product through social media networking sites. A higher ratio of 45.74% people confess that usually find new brands and desired branded products on networking sites, and 24.15% and 12.22 % respondents are somewhat agreed and neither agreed not disagreed of the above-mentioned statement. Furthermore, about 3.41% participants said that they are somewhat disagreed and the respondents who are disagreed and strongly disagreed have ratios of 1.99% and 0.28% individuals, respectively.

Graph 30:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 351

Skipped: 71

The above graph 30 illustrates that whether consumer prefer to know other customers' opinions regarding new brands' product or service. The findings from 351 individuals indicate that 16.24% participants strongly agree, who think it is better to know others' opinions. Similarly, a massive ratio of 45.58% are also agreed in terms of exploring experience of other users whereas 23.65% are somewhat agreed with this debate. A neutral cluster of 9.97% people also exist, who are neither agreed nor disagreed. Furthermore, results also reveal that 1.99% people are somewhat disagreed, and 1.42% and 1.14% applicants are disagreed and strongly disagreed, as they do not care about other users' experiences or opinions. it is clear from the above results, that overall consumers prefer to know other people's opinions about a new brand's products/services.

Graph 31:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 351

Skipped: 71

To purchase a productive product, which accomplish the needs and deliver a full utility level to the customer, it is necessary for a buyer to read users' reviews on the product. The findings from the graph 31 demonstrate that 29.43%, 36.00% and 20.00% of individuals strongly agreed, agree and somewhat agree with the argument that they prefer to read other users' product reviews before making a purchase. Further results illustrate that 9.43% and 3.43% people neither likely nor unlikely and somewhat disagree respectively with the above statement. Finally, a portion of 1.14% participants disagreed and 0.57% of them are strongly disagreed about reading reviews of product/service before making a purchase. Moreover, literature has also suggested in the chapter 2, that users' reviews are valuable source of information for other potential buyers (Ghose et al., 2009), these reviews from existing customers can create positive and negative impact on the brand image according to customers' experience (Robert and Kraynak, 2008), online customer feedbacks and reviews are increasing rapidly and creating huge impact on online business in particular (Forman et al., 2008), and negative reviews can damage the whole marketing campaign as well as can easily damage the product or brand image (Ullrich and Brunner, 2015).

Graph 32:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 350

Skipped: 72

Positive reviews tend to attract more potential buyers. Positive experience with a brand strengthens the brand image in consumers' minds (Hepola et al., 2017), and through appropriate consumer engagement it leads to loyalty (Brakus et al., 2009) and equity (Castaneda-Garcia et al., 2018; Mishra et al., 2014). The above graph 32 shows the similar results, that 27.71% people strongly agree, 39.71% agree and 21.43% of participants somewhat agree that they tend to buy products that have positive reviews. About 6.86% of individuals fall in the neutral category who are neither agree nor disagree. On the other hand, study explores a proportion of 2.57%, people are somewhat disagreed, 1.14% and 0.57% respondents are disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively regarding the above-mentioned argument.

Graph 33:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 349

Skipped: 73

The above graph presents an important aspect of this analysis in order to know about the perception of participants, that whether they believe on the social media in sense of displaying a true image of brands or not. To find out the statistics in categories, study runs the analysis on 349 responses and reveals that 10.32% people are strongly agreed, 44.13% people are agreed, and 26.07% are somewhat agreed with the argument that social media shows the true image of a brand. A portion of 10.03% respondents is neither agreed nor disagreed with the above-mentioned argument. On the other side, individuals who are somewhat disagreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed with this argument are 3.44%, 4.58% and 1.43% respectively in the graph 33.

Graph 34:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 349

Skipped: 73

The above results reveal that about 12.89% people strongly agree that it is easy to contact brands on social sites while a large proportion of 40.40% people are also agree, which reflects that social media plays a role of bridge between customer and brands. 28.65% people says that they are somewhat agree with the question asked above. A small portion of 10.60% respondents are neither agreed nor disagreed with the debate. Similarly, only 4.87% people says that they are somewhat disagree, that social media provides easy way to contact with brands whereas those who are disagree or strongly disagree having ratios of 1.72% and 0.86% respectively.

Graph 35:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 349

Skipped: 73

Study asked participants that either brands respond them quickly and efficiently on social sites or not. A less ratio of 07.45% people strongly agreed with the argument but most of the people exist in second and third category of this question, agree and somewhat agree, having ratio 34.38% and 31.23% respectively. If we continue the logic so we also recognize that 15.47% people are neither agree nor disagree with the debate. A small ratio of respondents say that they are somewhat disagreed with the statement, that brands respond to me quickly and efficiently on social sites, having ratio of 7.45% only. Furthermore 2.58% clearly disagree, and 2.58% of them are strongly disagreed with the debate.

Graph 36:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 349

Skipped: 73

To define the other aspect of customers in connection of their comfort, study conduct a question about interaction of brands with customer, study asked respondents that whether they feel more engage and more comfortable with international brands or not. Analysis results from graph 36 show that 11.17% people strongly agree and feel more comfortable by interacting international brands through social media. Similarly, 40.11% and 30.09% are agreed and somewhat agreed, and a percentage of 12.61% participants are appeared as neither agreed nor disagreed about the above argument. Like all other debates, study shows that 2.29% participants are disagree with the question asked above, while 1.43% and 2.29% individuals are disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

Graph 37:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 349

Skipped: 73

In discussion of buying behaviour, another important aspect is consumer generated content video on online social sites such as You Tube, which may influence the buying behaviour of consumer. To confirm the strength of this aspect study contains a question and recorded 355 responses of participants. As shown in the above graph 37, it is appeared that 29.23%, 33.24% and 21.49% participants strongly agree, agree and somewhat agree that consumer's generated content videos provide in-depth information. Furthermore, findings also reveal that a percentage of 9.74% participants are neither agreed nor disagreed about this phenomenon. Study also shows that 2.58% participants are somewhat disagreed , 3.15% individuals are disagreed while a very small ratio illustrate 0.57% people who are strongly disagreed about provision of in-depth information through consumer generated video content on social media sites.

Graph 38:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 348

Skipped: 74

It is evident in human nature that some people are more expressive in nature, these types of people usually share their opinions with others. Study tries to find those people who thought that they share their opinions about international brands and products with other experts especially with some celebrities on social media. Statistics show that 8.91% people strongly agree in the sense of sharing their opinions about international brands. A moderate bracket of 24.14% participants agrees, 27.59% of them somewhat agree and 24.43% participants neither agree nor disagree to the content of discussion. Moving further, study also reveals that about 6.90%, 5.75% and 2.30% respondents are somewhat disagreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively in regards to the above argument.

Graph 39:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 347

Skipped: 75

Study has tried to examine the percentage of those participants who use social media and engage with brands for passing their time. The graph results indicate that about 12.68% of participants strongly agree that they pass their time away by engaging with brands on social media, while a large proportion of 38.54% people are also agreed in the sense of passing time on social media and engaging themselves with brand. Above results also reveal that 20.17% people are somewhat agreed and a moderate portion of 16.71% respondents are neither agreed nor disagreed with the debate. However, only 4.13% respondents said that they are somewhat disagreed, whereas those who are completely disagree or strongly disagree having ratios of 3.10% and 0.56% respectively. Overall findings of this discussion show that more people agreed with the discussion about passing time by engaging themselves with brands on social media.

Graph 40:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 348

Skipped: 74

The above chart (Graph 40) examines whether respondents purchase more from a specific brand's products or services if that brand continues to involve them in social media activities and interactions. Findings suggest that 11.78% are strongly agreed in context of more purchasing from those brands who continuously involve them on social media activities. Similarly, a large cluster of 38.51%, 28.16% and 12.64% respondents are agreed, somewhat agreed and neither agree nor disagree respectively with the current debate. About 4.60% individuals are appeared as somewhat disagree and others are also disagreed and strongly disagreed with ratios of 2.87% and 1.44%, respectively.

Graph 41:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 348

Skipped: 74

Last but not least, to assess whether engaging through social media channels with the brands improves loyalty or not, study has obtained 348 answers from the participants. As you can see in the above graph 41, A large fraction 13.51% and 43.10% of participants are strongly agreed and agreed with the above statement, while 25.86% are somewhat agreed. 12.64% of individuals are appeared as neutral by saying that they are neither agreed nor disagreed with the debate. A small ratio of respondents said that they are somewhat disagreed with the phrase, that loyalty towards brand improves through social media, having ratio of 3.16%. Furthermore, 1.15% clearly disagreed and only 0.57% participants are strongly disagreed with the above-mentioned argument. Literature of this study has also discovered the similar results, as engaging satisfied consumers through social media activities creates WOM (word of mouth) marketing that attracts many more potential customers as well as it improves consumer loyalty (Geyskens and Steenkamps, 2000; Evan et al., 2008; Brakus et al., 2009; Van Dorn et al., 2010; Naumann and Bowden, 2015)

4.3 Inferential statistics:

The obtained results from the multiple regression model are defined in this section which is based on multiple variables that generate influence on brand awareness.

Multiple regression examination states to a set of procedures for studying the straight-line associations between two or more variables. This study interprets the original findings by defining variables theoretically and reveal the econometric results of the purposed model, which is as under:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta X + \mu$$

Where; “Y” is a variable which is dependent.

“ α ” is a constant.

“ β ” is a coefficient of independent variables.

“x” is an independent variable.

“ μ ” is an Error term.

Established on the certain variables, the multiple regression equation of this study will be:

$$Z = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \epsilon_i$$

Purposed model:

$$B.A = \alpha + \beta_1 (USM) + \beta_2 (ADV) + \beta_3 (MSOS) + \beta_4 (NCR) + \beta_5 (BU) + \beta_6 (SOH) + \mu$$

4.3.1 Hypothesis of the study:

The term hypothesis in this situation could be described as the presumed relationship among variables (two or more than two) that can be expressed in the testable statement form.

4.3.1.1 Hypothesis development:

The researcher firstly has identified the essential variables, and then through the logical reasoning in the theoretical framework he formed the relationship among them prior to test the relationship among the variables that whether theorized relationship hold true or not.

4.3.1.2 Directional hypotheses:

Directional hypotheses involves terms such as positive, negative, less than and greater than etc, because relationship direction is indicated among variables. For instance, women are more motivated to work.

4.3.1.3. Non-directional hypotheses:

Non-directional hypotheses represent the relationship, but unable to point out whether the relationship is positive or negative. For instance, there is a difference between work ethics values between Chinese and British employees.

4.3.1.4 Types of hypotheses:

4.3.1.5 Null and alternative hypothesis

The null hypothesis is a proposition that states a definite, exact relationship between two variables. That is, it states that population correlation between two variables is equal to zero (or some definite number)

$$H_0=0$$

The alternative hypothesis, which is the opposite of the null, is a statement expressing a relationship between two variables or indicating difference between groups.

$$H_1 \neq 0$$

Sr No	Variables	Hypothesis $H_0= H_1 \neq 0$
1	Use of social media	<p>H₀: There is insignificant effect of social media use on brand awareness</p> <p>H₁: There is a significant effect of social media use on brand awareness</p>

2	Advertisement	<p>H₀: There is insignificant effect of advertisement on brand awareness</p> <p>H₁: There is a significant effect of advertisement on brand awareness</p>
3	Monthly spending for online shopping	<p>H₀: There is insignificant effect of monthly spending for online shopping on brand awareness</p> <p>H₁: There is a significant effect of monthly spending for online shopping on brand awareness</p>
4	Negative customer reviews	<p>H₀: There is insignificant effect of social media use on brand awareness</p> <p>H₁: There is a significant effect of social media use on brand awareness</p>
5	Brand updates	<p>H₀: There is insignificant effect of brand updates on brand awareness</p> <p>H₁: There is a significant effect of brand updates on brand awareness</p>
6	Sense of happiness	<p>H₀: There is insignificant effect of sense of happiness on brand awareness</p> <p>H₁: There is a significant effect of sense of happiness on brand awareness</p>

Table 5, Hypotheses variables

USM: Use of social media

To analyse the perception of individuals towards brands, it is necessary to ask respondents that up-to what extent they use social media in daily routine life, this variable is categorical in nature having four categories named as Daily, 3 to 5 times a week, weekly, monthly, don't use the social media ever.

ADV: Advertisement

To create brand awareness every entrepreneur should undertake the successful advertisement campaigns, which helps the newly entered brands to change the perception or ideas of people, this variable also contains categories named as very likely, likely, somewhat likely, neither likely nor unlikely, somewhat unlikely, unlikely and very unlikely. These categories decoded with the numeric data, for the purpose of analysis.

MSOS: Monthly spending for online shopping

To understand the awareness of people toward brands it is necessary to analyse their monthly spending for online shopping, this variable reflects the interest of customers for online available branded products, this variable also categorical in nature containing different categories of income written as Less than £200, Between £200 - £499, Between £500-£999, Between £1,000 and £2,000, Over £2,000, these categories also decoded in the numeric data.

NCR: Negative customer reviews

Whenever the new product is launched and used by the pioneer customers, it is very important for the brands to get caught with the positive customer reviews in order to reach their other potential customers, to analyse the impact of positive customer reviews on brand awareness this categorical variable included in the model, later changed to the numeric data.

BU: Brand updates

Some people are conscious about brands updates, and they keep using the social media for the purpose of information gathering regarding brands, to understand the extent of brand updates on brand awareness this categorical variable included in the model, which may change in numeric data for the analysis

SOH: Sense of happiness

Whatever people are doing, it is necessary to feel the sense of happiness, to understand that whether a sense of happiness helps to increase the brand awareness or not this categorical variable includes in the model, and it is also changed later to the numeric data.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F	sig
1	.582 ^a	.338	.328	33.566	.000

Table 6, Model summary

The above table 6 shows the summary of the model that it contains some key statistics which needs to be explained in the light of multiple regression. This table defines the primary interest of researcher.

It defines the R^2 as well as Adjusted R square and Standard Error of estimate which can be used to determine how regression model can be fit into the data. The R Colum shows the value R that is multiple correlation coefficients. It can be considered to be one measure of the quality of the prediction of the dependent variable, in this case the value of R is 0.582 which indicates a good level of prediction. Similarly, the R square Colum shows the value of R^2 , which is also known as the coefficient of determination that is the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variable. Findings reveal that R^2 is 0.338, and it is appeared that our independent variables explained 33.8% variability in the dependent variable. In the same way next value is Adjusted R square, it is used to compare the explanatory power regression model that contains different number of predictors. The adjusted R square is a modified version of R^2 that has been adjusted for the number of predictors in the model and the Adjusted R^2 increase only if the new term improve the model more than would be expected by chance, it decrease when the predictor improve the model by less than expected by chance, the adjusted R square can be negative but it usually not, it is always lower than the R^2 .

Furthermore, some other important findings from the estimated regression model, in this table is F ratio, which tells that overall regression model is a good fit for the data or not. The above table shows that the independent variable statistically significantly predicts the dependent variable, which represents the regression model is a good fit of the data with the f-test value of 33.566. Moreover, it also reveals that the value of significance is less the 5% which indicate the good response of explanatory variables towards response variable.

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error	Significance	t-test
Use of social media	0.149	0.049	0.002***	3.056
Advertisement	0.120	0.054	0.027**	2.221
Monthly Spending for online shopping	-0.149	0.051	0.003***	-2.943
Negative customer reviews	-0.181	0.061	0.003***	-2.945
Brand updates	0.310	0.042	0.000***	7.468
Sense of Happiness	0.243	0.045	0.000***	5.432
Constant	0.842	0.226	0.000***	3.733

*, **, *** Significant at 10, 5 and 1 percent respectively Table 7, Variables results
NS: Non-Significant

Estimated multiple regression model:

$$Z = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \text{USM} + \beta_3 \text{ADV} + \beta_4 \text{MSOS} + \beta_5 \text{NCR} + \beta_6 \text{BU} + \beta_7 \text{SOH} + \epsilon_i$$

$$Z = 0.842 + 0.149^* \text{USM} + 0.120^* \text{ADV} - 0.149^* \text{MSOS} - 0.181^* \text{NCR} + 0.310^* \text{BU} + 0.243^* \text{SOH}$$

4.3.2 Use of social media:

The major study outcomes describe that by undertaking different important variables; like, use of social media, reflects the intensity of interaction among people and brands, obviously the increase in the use of social media may increase the brand awareness because when anybody go for social media sites, blogging or other networking sites, they may go through the different brands as they appear on different web pages during scrolling or by singing in. Findings reveal that the use of social media is significantly related with the brand awareness, which means that the study rejects the null hypothesis and accept alternative

hypothesis, as it is significant at the 1%. It can also be evident with t-test value, which is 3.056, and the t value should be greater than ± 2 , which reflects in our results. Likewise, the coefficient of social media shows that, if one percent increases in the use of social media, the brand awareness will increase by 0.149%, by holding other independent variables constant. Similarly, literature also suggests that due social media influence, the behaviour of customer shopping is changing (Geissinger and Laurell, 2016), receiving positive response from consumers (Hussey, 2012), and social media also introducing new and better ways of communication among brands and their customers (Verhoef et al., 2010).

4.3.3 Advertisement:

In order to influence the human psychology in terms of brands, it is necessary for SMEs to bring something worthwhile in terms of advertisement which makes their product attractive towards customers, and that much high influence generated through the advertisement contents helps them to capture their potential customers. Promotions and advertisement play key role in the success of any product, it leads towards the higher profits through a block chain of whole-sellers and retailers (Hollebeek et al., 2014) which may also lead to increase the employment level and national income of the country. Therefore, by keeping in view the importance of this variables study includes it in the purposed model and estimation indicates the acceptance of alternative hypothesis. Statistics reveal that if advertisement increase by one percent, then brand awareness increase by 0.120 percent, by holding other independent variables constant. This variable is also significant in nature with response variable evident by t value and level of significance. Moreover, literature also emphasises on advertising through social media networks. As past studies show that modern ways of social media marketing are replacing old fashioned and traditional ways of marketing (Ashley and Tuten, 2015), and advance social marketing blogs tend to integrate with leading social media platforms such as Facebook and YouTube to increase widest consumer outreach and their engagement (Rose et al., 2011; Jett, 2012).

4.3.4 Monthly spending for online shopping:

Income is the most important factor in any model used for the prediction by independent towards response variable. In today's modern world, the trend for online shopping increases day by day because it saves time, providing access to the brands on doorsteps everything related to shopping can be done on mobile phones or laptops in case of online shopping. It can be done through social media sites which plays a role of medium of exchange between

the buyer and seller, so this variable is also important in nature, but it shows tricky result in the sense of inverse relationship with response variable. It shows that if one percent increase in online shopping then brand awareness decrease by 0.149 percent, by holding other independent variables constant, this inverse relationship can be define in a sense of customer's loyalty towards specific brands, that means a customer only spends or do online shopping with desired brand and not go for the other ones so by increasing his/her spending and sticking him/herself at one brand and not look around for other brands which may provide max utility at the same price, so we can say it results in lack of brand awareness or decline in awareness in terms of other brands. This variable is significantly related with response variables as it shows by t-test value which is greater than ± 2 or it also indicated by level of significance which is less than one percent and the rejection of null hypothesis.

4.3.5 Negative customer reviews:

Another important content of social media that SMEs need to consider in their account is the reviews of the products. Reviews can be positive or negative, and mostly it comes from the product users who share their experience after using the branded products. It is widely accepted that products with positive reviews tend to lead higher sales and profit and this positive experience strengthen the brand image in consumers' mind (Hepola et al.,2017). On the other hand, negative customer reviews represent bad image among consumers (Ullrich and Brunner, 2015), that may lead towards the loss for the host company. Therefore, it is essential for SMEs and brands to avoid such situation by handling these reviews carefully and quantify the situation that up-to what extent negative customer reviews can influence the brand awareness. The econometric results from the research show the inverse relationship between negative customer reviews and brand awareness. Findings reveal that this explanatory variable is significantly related with response variable as it is evident by t-test value and level of significance that indicates the acceptance of alternative hypothesis and rejects the null, findings further reveals that if negative customer reviews increase by one percent than the brand awareness decrease by 0.181 percent, by holding other explanatory variables constant. Marketers who are engaged in social media activities, should be able to control and handle these negative feedbacks/reviews before these comments are found by millions of other online users/communities, which can damage the brand or product image (Gendel-Guterman and Levy, 2017).

4.3.6 Brand updates:

Brand news and updates plays an important role in generating brand awareness and consumer engagement. It is often evident in daily life that mostly people subscribe the brands' websites and follow the social media channels of particular brands in order to get latest news and information from their desired brands. Some people register with emails to get the messages and updates in case of any update from the brands. Such steps from consumers provide opportunities for SMEs to engage their existing consumers efficiently, and to create brand awareness by motivating their online followers to share their posts to friends and family.

To quantify the impact of a brand updates on brand awareness study got econometric results by applying appropriate methodology which shows that by if one percent increase in brand updates the brand awareness increase by 0.310 percent, by holding others constant, this variable is also significantly related with response variables in terms of prediction, and it is reflected by t-value which is 7.468 as well as it indicated the acceptance of alternative hypothesis. Similarly, social media networking sites provide businesses day to day interaction with their consumer, which allow them to monitor individuals' trends, fashion and their behaviour (Hill and Morgan, 2011). So, brands can easily capture more potential consumers and keep them engaged by sending brands' product information, latest news and discounts/sale according to consumer's' interests.

4.3.7 Sense of happiness:

Anything which is necessary for human life, it become more worthwhile when it gives a sense of happiness while performing it. This variable a bit more social in nature, which predicts the human behaviour in terms of engagement with brands through social media. This study tries to analyse that if a customer gets a sense of happiness by interacting with brands through social media sites, whether or not this experience will enhance brand awareness and consumer engagement among brand and consumers. Therefore, the study includes this variable and obtained the statistical findings from the proposed model which defines that this variable is significant at level of one percent and rejecting the null hypothesis, its t-test value 5.432 indicates that it is significant to the response variable. Findings further reveals that if one unit increase in sense of happiness the brand awareness increase by 0.243 percent, by holding other independent variables constant. Entertainment has appeared as an important driving factor that encourage consumers' behaviour, stability

and continuity to follow-up, which develops positive emotions/feelings towards a certain brand (Kang, 2005). By adding entertaining and other positive elements into social marketing campaigns can attract more consumers and it may facilitate marketers to engage existing consumers in a more proactive way (Kim and Ko, 2012), as it provides sense of happiness among consumers, so it can also develop e-WOM online communities (Evan et al., 2008).

Chapter 5: Discussions

5.1 Introduction:

This chapter targets to deliver a comprehensive debate of outcomes concerning all three research objectives. The chapter begins with a general summary of the study, which is necessary to examine the previous chapters. Furthermore, the literature review of the social media considered in terms of discussion in the same way; next section delivers the discussions on review of literature. Successively, a comprehensive discussion regarding findings in terms of its descriptive and statistical analysis which enlighten the research objectives of this study (objective 1 and 2) are delivered separately. Subsequently, the research objective 3, which is the major aim of this study that a worthwhile policy is provided for the SMEs in order to capture their potential customers and this will be fulfilled in the light of previous, descriptive and quantitative findings and it is discussed separately. Finally, a conclusion, on the discussions is delivered end to end with established theoretical model.

5.2 Summary of the thesis:

Social media is considered as one of the important topics which is highly discussed in these days. Even organisations have recognised the advantages of social media networks rather than private individuals, particularly regarding communication with consumers in order to initiate direct dialogues with particular target groups of people. It has been seen that companies across all the industries are establishing online presence on social media channels and using social media as an integral part of their marketing mix to get competitive advantage in the marketplace. A positive association and communication can be established among the brands and customers, by interacting with a suitable social media channel (Gummesson, 2002). Customers are permitted to oblige as inventors of branded content, it happens due to numerous influences as well as participation and social linked behaviour (Fournier and Avery, 2011). Evans (2008) has suggested that a social media channel consists of 100 followers will be reflected 10 times extra valued as associated to a channel who have only 10 members in terms of accessibility. Alexander and Jaakkola (2015) illustrate that customer engagement is necessary to mobilize the behaviour of buyers by improving their assessment process. It entails by a firm, that customer needs a most primer examinations (Paek and Nelson, 2009). Similarly, Harris and Harrigan (2011) suggest that firm should organize buyers who increases the business for sustaining high sales.

A better consumer engagement model must be energetic as well as multidimensional, which needs to improve satisfaction with the products and services, loyalty or trust may also consider accomplishing self-brand presentation's conclusions. Generally, customer engagement characterizes the interest of a customer for a brand (MSI, 2010). Moreover, Fierro et al., (2013) state that "such buyer commitment contains transactional and non-transactional procedures, and they are well-defined through loyalty and buying purpose or brand assurance, such as blogging". Customer engagement is reflected as a necessary component which defines a fundamental part in a commercial presentation. Numerous researchers put their efforts to classify the appearances to make customer's participation (Tripathi, 2009; Sashi, 2012).

The SMEs typically ignore or not well aware of the importance of customer's engagement (Carter, 2008). Therefore, such organisations can be evident in terms of struggling to accomplish long term relationships with their consumers as well as to attach/engage them with their brands. Further it is suggested by Dutot (2013), that brands should not only show their interest to gain market stakes, but they also need to engage customers with their brands for a long-term performance. As it is worth noted by Escalas (2004), that it is much more necessary to have a self-brand association with purchasers for consumer assignment in relations to comrade and definite themselves regarding to their essential satisfaction. In the same way, customers incline to preserve the loyalty, which may consequence in terms of change in their continuous behaviour for buying additional products (Park et al., 2007).

By continuing the argument that consumers should be engaged by entrepreneurs in a particular kind of activities and keep them occupy with their brand, but a cluster of ingenious customers may also deliver some ground-breaking and expedient material and concepts. Although, due to nonexistence of control over consumers, they may act as a hazard to enterprises (Cheung, Lee and Thadani, 2009). Subsequently Brodie et al., (2011) define customer commitment as a unidimensional perception as well as consumer behaviour is really a leading constituent nonetheless, Van Doorn et al., (2010) exhibit that attitudinal forerunners are much more imperative factors that make control on the consumer engagement. Furthermore, Backer-Olsen and Hill (2006) argue that an effective model of consumer engagement may appeared and characterized by creation of brand societies self-identities. Literature also defines large gaps, which are yet to recognise the suitable ways to develop brand identities and associations with modern consumers.

The literature convers the importance of consumer engagement, the impact of social media platforms on individuals and businesses, and also emphasises on better consumer engagement through social media channels to create brand awareness. It also explains that how social media marketing networks replacing the traditional ways of marking (Kotler and Armstrong, 2007; Brodie et al., 2013; Ashley and Tuten, 2015). The aim of the study is to assess the consumer engagement and social media impact to enhance brand awareness, and accordingly this study proposed three main objectives to understand the role of social media in today's modern age to engage modern consumers and to enhance brand awareness. A thorough literature review (chapter 2) is conducted in order to address these three objectives. A research design is selected in chapter 3, based on the research paradigms and quantitative method is used to collect the data through survey. The findings of the collected data are presented in previous chapter 4 in the form of descriptive and statistical analysis.

5.3.1 Objective 1:

To determine the impact of social media on customer engagement and brand awareness in today's modern world.

A value of a brand can be improved by increasing social media linkages affiliation among the brand and online channels that also enhance brand awareness (Berthon et al., 2012). An entrepreneur needs to explore about social media podiums that may use competently for the purpose to reach its probable customers, to appeal excellence predictions as well as to absorb customers in their brand.

(1) Social media influence in today's modern world:

Social media refers as a digital technology that is evolving with the leap of period (Kane et al., 2014), and it provides a network for online communities to exchange information (Singh and Diamond, 2012). Social media offers individuals with common interests a platform to come together and share their opinions, ideas and thoughts with each other (Weber, 2007). The influence of social media consequences is measured, massive and powerful in context of brand awareness as well as in engagement of customer. However, in context of enactment, it does not define about the clear image of its efficiency (Dutot, 2013). A number of clients have been evident in contributing to promote blogs to get supplementary information about a particular product and service, which leads to help the buyer to make good decision (Scott, 2009). It has been evident in the literature that the

speculation in terms of investment on social media has been improved three times from the last three years.

Literature also establishes that marketing related to social media like blogs, Facebook, LinkedIn etc., measured as a necessary component in publicizing for SMEs because of general perception of social linkages in this modern era (Ashton, 2009; Key Note, 2014). Blogging (different kinds of social media networks) is reflected a crucial constituent for communication among buyer and brands (Luck and Ginanti, 2013), Bloggers' probable extent towards high number of buyers, blogs are emerging as a popular component for imbedding marketing mix (Ahuja and Medury, 2010). In the same way, Schmallegger and Carson (2008) illustrate that the blogs create some certain pre-purchase capacities by the encouragement of customer's opinion in context of different product under marketing mix. Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) demonstrate about several different studies that research recognise the different roles for blogs in order to improve marketing statements. Similarly, market research in terms of blogging and social media provides the product advantages and disadvantages (Bijmolt et al., 2010).

The major findings of this study describe the impact and the role social media networks play in individuals' life, which defines the aspects of social media creating brand awareness by commission of different imperative variables, social media is one of them. It is evident that social media channels make a path available for new start up's SMEs in context of ecological improvement as well as also help them to observe current contender's actions and engenders high value of customer (Wilson and Gilligan, 2005).

Social media promotions established on accessible internet organization (Palmer and Koenig-Lewis, 2009), According to Pace (2008), the use of social media in context of capturing potential customers, is not only inexpensive but also supplementary active medium of exchange for creating brand awareness. Burmaster (2009) points out that social media and networking sites deliver opportunities of interaction, for example Facebook and You Tube works as bridge among brands and their consumers, as consumers find latest information and product reviews on these channels, which in turn leads to increase in brand awareness (Hill and Moran, 2011). By keeping in view, the above argument, the results of the research also reflects that as use of social media increase by the people it may cause an increase in brand awareness, it is also evident in the econometric findings of this study and this enhancement of brand awareness may happen by social media because the buyers may

understand the contemplation on feedbacks which are defined online by other people (Weiss et al., (2008).

Findings (Graph 6) indicate that about 82 percent people use different social media platforms to find product information, and about 58 percent individuals interact and engage with brand' social media activities on the daily basis (Graph 4). These findings also mentioned in the literature that people spend half of their time on social media activities (Riegner, 2007), and Facebook and YouTube have over 2 billion and 1.5 billion users respectively worldwide (Statista, 2018). Thus, it is evident that social media has become a part of individuals' life and offers various opportunities to businesses. Similarly, literature highlights that these social sites allow businesses to explore consumers' attitudes and behaviours and provide them opportunities to develop trust and healthy relationship with consumers for better consumer engagement (Badea, 2014). Furthermore, brands are seen investing more on social sites to develop their social media presence to reach a large audience through social media wide approach to create brand awareness (Nielsen, 2011).

(2) Social media impact on individual's life:

Social media creates dominant impressions on individual's life in today's world, and it is evident in literature that customer targeting is easier now a days than ever before due to increase in social media podiums. It has been seen that due to rise in digital technology, individuals devote most of their time on social media activities like Instagram, Facebook, YouTube etc. (Riegner, 2007). It is extensively understood that social networks are forthcoming destination and plays a role of medium of exchange with one another and develops new trends, interests and their purchasing behaviour (Burmester, 2009). Facebook and YouTube define recent tendencies and provide assistance to brands in terms of getting instantaneous reaction from their businesses (Hill and Moran, 2011). Through instant and valuable answers which are available on You Tube and Facebook, customer care facilities on social media are seemed to be more valuable (Tariq and Wahid, 2011) as it solved customer complaints efficiently (Parveen, Jaafar and Ainin, 2015). It shows that online collaborations can improve the statement and associations among users and brands (Sashi, 2012). The major findings of this are similar to the literature discussed above, as it is shown in graph given below

Graph 42:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 400

Skipped: 22

In today's modern world, there are lots of social media sites like YouTube, Twitter and Facebook etc. The researcher has tried to assess that what category of social media is more likely to be used by the respondents to stay update with the brands, for this purpose he asked them about their preferred social media site. Analysis reflects (Graph 42) that 58.50% of individuals like to use YouTube, 50.75% Facebook, 47.50% Instagram, 19.5% Google+, whereas TikTok, Twitter and LinkedIn have 16.75%, 14.75% and 5.75% users, respectively. Moreover, a very small ratio of 1.25% respondents have mentioned that they do not use social media from the enlisted categories in questionnaire. Moving with the argument, literature also shows that social media is one of the supreme revolutions of technology which not only provides an ability to interconnect with others and it also made businesses proposals in the marketplaces which unswervingly they want to target.

Literature in this study also shows the similarity with the above results, as Facebook, YouTube and Instagram sites are extremely popular particularly among young individuals. Currently, Facebook has more than 2.1 billion users (Statista, 2018), online users who use Facebook are about three quarters and 7 out of 10 users use their Facebook account

everyday (Duggan, 2015), 87% of Facebook users are young adults between 18-29 years old (Duggan et al., 2015), Instagram has over 300 million active users monthly and on an average, over 80 million photos are being shared on Instagram daily (Instagram, 2016). It shows how active these social channels are, and SMEs and brands can reach them through these channels and can engage them through social media activities.

User generated contents (UGC) are another important and new form of communication among brands and people that is emerged in the literature review. It refers to the contents that are mostly made by the users, thus it is considered as more authentic, honest and high degree of credibility in the consumer's eyes (Filho and Tan, 2009). This study findings (Graph 20) agree with the literature and illustrate that about 73% of participants tend to buy products that are recommended through consumer/user generated content videos. Furthermore, results (Graph 37) also show that 84% individuals believe that consumer generated videos on online social sites (such as on YouTube) provide in-depth information about the product that can influence their buying behaviour. Therefore, various brands are trying to find celebrities and social media influencers to endorse their products or services via generating videos on social sites. However, these consumer generated contents also involve multiple risks and threats, as negative and inappropriate comments or poor product feedbacks can significantly damage the product or brand image/reputation (Ullrich and Brunner, 2015). In addition, Findings (section 4.3.5) also suggest that negative reviews create bad image of the product among consumers, and they do not buy the products with bad reviews/feedbacks.

5.3.2 Objective 2:

To review the individual characteristics in terms of brands, which helps SMEs to reach their potential consumers and engage them through social media.

SMEs usually face different experiments and define risks before attaining achievements, as for the marketing, the social media obliges knowledge of experts. Normally, SMEs approve social media marketing to spread their messages to a large audience, as they reflected social media in terms of cost efficiency. But many scholars exhibit that social media may become costly and difficult to adopt, as it depends on different factors such as target groups' age and size etc (Dutot, 2013). In addition, consumer satisfaction can be increased by connecting with customer through social media channels (Khan and Fasih, 2014), which leads to repurchases in the future (Tripathi, 2014).

Basically, this objective is included in this study to define some of individual characteristics which can help SMEs to reach their potential customers and keep them engaged via different social activities.

(1) Social media can help SMEs to engage modern consumers:

Customer engagement plays an integral part in a long-run business performance, many researchers have tried in the past to identify the characteristics to engage consumers (Sashi, 2012; Tripathi, 2009). Several SMEs have been seen struggling because they ignored importance of customer engagement (Carter, 2008), firms are required to engage consumer with their brand in order to perform long term and they should not only show interest to gain market share (Dutot, 2013). Customer satisfaction is considered one of the most important factors that leads to customer engagement and represents healthy relationship and consumer loyalty towards a brand (Evan et al., 2008). Furthermore, according to Khan and Fasih (2014) customer satisfaction can be improved through social media channels by connecting them through various social activities. Word of mouth marketing, which is considered high valuable for any brand, is a result of satisfied customers that lead to repurchases from the same brand in future and increase customer loyalty with a brand (Tripathi). The findings (Graph 19, 20, 32) also highlight similar results as literature refers, that individuals tend to buy a product that have positive reviews or recommended through consumer generated videos. Moreover, participants state that they do not buy products that have negative reviews which is result of bad experience of customers. This also suggested by literature that negative reviews and negative word of mouth marketing can damage the brand image/reputation as well as the whole marketing campaign (Cheung et al., 2009).

Many studies examined that the social media has capability to translate customers into dealers through feedbacks and word of mouth promotion. These buyers can make optimistic and undesirable impression on brands, in the light of their experience with the products (Robert and Kraynak, 2008). Similarly, Ghose, et al., (2012), define that consumer generated contents in terms of positive or negative reviews are measured as appreciated basis of evidence for other persons regarding online purchase decision and also enhance customer engagement. This statement is also confirmed by findings of this study. The results from graph 20 illustrate that about 84% individuals prefer to know other people opinions and reviews before making a purchase, and about 80% of participant shared that they like to know about new products and brands through social media sites. Thus, the results suggest that these social platforms offer various opportunities for SMEs and brands

to engage the consumers in an effective manner.

Products reviews rapidly increases on social media networks due to globalization and it creates massive influence on the commercial businesses via online sources (Forman, Ghose and Wiesenfeld, 2008). Likewise, these negative reactions cannot be ignored by the entrepreneurs. Another study by, Hennig-Thurau et al., (2004) also explains that SMEs need to accomplish their social network in connection with their marketing campaigns correctly through which they got immediate response either it is negative or positive which helps SMEs to take possible quick action in order to make perfection in their products or services. Furthermore, negative reviews generated by customers can harm the entire marketing campaign. It is extensively supposed that social media sites are reachable to everyone, so the customer can easily post a negative experience which may destroy the image of brand (Cheung, Lee and Thadani, 2009). Study asked people that what kind of online sources may use by them in order to get in touch with brands as shown below graph 43.

Graph 43:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 365

Skipped: 57

As world is going to be revolutionized, we saw lots of developments take place in our daily life. SMEs can use those sources to address the customers. Study tries to compare social media channels with other existing sources used by customers to get in touch with brands. As shown in the above graph 43, findings explain that social media channels have high intensity, in this case study results repeat the trend and social media channels place at first with 64.93% people. About 47% participants prefer to use email to get in touch with brands via subscribing their preferred brands and products. These results are well supported by the literature (Section. 2) and provide opportunities for SMEs to use an appropriate social media channel to engage their consumers. These social media channels deliver high quality interaction with consumers that enable customer to co-create the unique experience with the firm and add better value through positive word of mouth (Prahalad Ramaswamy, 2004).

Findings (graph. 14) illustrate that about 80% participants said that they prefer to know about new brand and products through social media platforms rather than other old and traditional ways such as through TV, radio, magazines, branners etc. Moreover, results (graph. 16) also demonstrates that 88% individuals agree that advertising and brand messages are better on social media channels as compared to TV, radio and newspaper. These results prove that SMEs can enhance their consumer engagement in much more proactive way through social media channels, and these results are well supported by the existing literature in section 2. As per noted by Berthon et al., (2012) that advertising and products promotion on social media channels are more powerful as compared to traditional way (such as TV, newspaper), because it social channels can transform single-way communication into multi-way communication, and further this enthusiastic communication can change consumers' attitudes and behaviours towards buying-decision making process (Godey et al., 2016; Constantinides, 2014).

(2) SMEs can create brand awareness through social media networks:

In general, the channels of social media attract people with same interests to come together and share their feelings and opinions with each other (Weber, 2007). Young adults are spending half of their time on these modern social networking sites for various reasons such as to communicate with friends or family, to find new trends, to find product information and to read/see product reviews etc. According to Kim and Ko (2012), the marketing activities on social media platforms are characterized as entertainment, word-of-mouth, entertainment, interaction and customization communication. Entertainment is emerged as

an essential element that encourages consumers' behaviour, stability and continuity to follow-up that develops positive feelings in the follower's attitude for a brand (Kang, 2005). Moreover, Hamid et al., (2016) demonstrate that people particularly young generation is very active on social media channel, and information is being shared on social networks simultaneously in real time, therefore these platforms has become latest and up-to-date source of information for consumers as well as for businesses. The quantitative findings of the study also demonstrate that individuals who are very likely, likely and somewhat likely use social media channels to find information are 21.56%, 35.58% and 26.15% respectively (Graph, 6). In addition, results from graph 10 describe that 34% participant utilize social media channels to find trends and latest fashion, which is also suggested by Godey et al., (2016), that another crucial component of social media marketing activities is trendiness that introduce the current, latest and popular information for individuals.

Chen et al., (2011) point out that Corporations are appeared using these online-based social sites in two different aspects for their marketing purposes. Firstly, they use social media platforms (such as Facebook and YouTube) for direct marketing actions, which means that firms are using social media marketing tool to promote and advertise their products to social media users and also try to get their feedback (Hanna et al., 2011). Because marketers believe that they can spread their message to more consumers on social media channels as compared to traditional channels like TV and magazines. It also appeared in this study findings, as graph 14 shows that about 80% individuals prefer to get information about new brands or products through social media channels, only 20% and 6.5% participants prefer to get information through TV/radio and newspapers/magazines, respectively. Furthermore, quantitative findings in graph 33 illustrate that 80% of respondents agreed that social media shows the true image of the brand, and consumer believe that information regards to a product or brand is more accurate and trustworthy as they can read other people opinions on these social sites. The second aspect is the experience that a customer gets with from a brand's product, and he/she shares to other individuals (Chen et a., 2011). Social media has power to change the consumers' behaviour and purchasing intentions, and it also influences people to share their experience and knowledge to others (Lu and Hsiao, 2010; Hajli, 2013). This statement is also confirmed in the quantitative results which show that about 70% individuals like to share their positive experience with others, and further 73 % individuals share their negative experience on social sites to warn other people.

It is necessary for the marketers of SMEs to respond actively on social sites because any bad remark from consumers may result in damage of brands image. In current times social

media is growing in developing countries, it is evident in literature that Facebook have 191.3 million active users in its native country while in India it has around 195.16 million active users (Singh, 2016).

Blogging is another option in context of social marketing strategies for SMEs that can develop relationship among consumers and brands to enhance brand awareness, as many of organisations develop blogs for the purpose of product marketing (Gilmore et al., 2001). In the same way, Stokes (2011) illustrates that marketing activities executed on social media, offer SMEs lots of reasonable methods in context of product marketing and services. Similarly, SMEs can influence millions of potential buyers who are influenced by social media that is established for online internet structure (Palmer and Koenig-Lewis, 2009). The graph 36 presents that approximately 81% individuals believe that interacting with international brands through social media sites make them feel comfortable and more engaged. Likewise, the graph 39 illustrates that 12.68%, 38.54% and 20.17% respondents are strongly agreed, agreed and somewhat agreed respectively that they pass their time away by engaging with brands on social sites. Finally, the graph 41 shows that about 82% participants are agreed that engaging through social media activities with brands improve their loyalty. Hence, marketers need to select an appropriate strategy to engage consumers through social media to keep them engage in their marketing activities to enhance brand awareness.

By linking the above argument with the findings of this study SMEs should focus on consumers behavior in terms if his/her preferences in gathering information. Here, just to understand, that whether people find product information through social media or not, in connection with our previous argument it is necessary to know that which source is mostly used by the people to find product information. It will help SMEs to in context of decision making, to choose right platform of social media in order to execute their advertisements for the creation of awareness among their potential customers, and it will ultimately help them in capturing and increasing sales of their particular product.

Graph 44:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 369

Skipped: 53

In today's digital age, networking and micro blogging platforms such as YouTube, Twitter, Facebook and Instagram are the most commonly used social media sites, and almost everyone uses these platforms. The above graph 44 shows that 51.49% people from the survey use networking and microblogging sites to find product information. In recent times, E-commerce sites also provide easy access to customers to find product information and reviews before making a purchase online, and our result shows that 29.00% respondents prefer to find information through E-commerce sites. Some people are much brand conscious and wants to find information only from the websites of brands, so results indicate that 27.10% individuals prefer brands websites. Another important source of finding information is video sharing sites like YouTube, 33.60% people said that they go through video sharing sites to find desired information. Tv, radio, news channels and other sources have small ratios of 8.67% and 1.63% respectively.

The results of the study are applicable for the most of the small medium organisations particularly who have online presence. Social media networking sites also offers various

opportunities to offline businesses such as introducing new products and services and sending out vouchers/coupons through social platforms may attract consumers to their physical stores; thus these social sites can help offline businesses to create brand awareness among targeted consumers. Furthermore, the findings of the research benefits many different types of SMEs such as beauty and fashion goods, entertainment, health and fitness, real estate, lifestyle and travel, education, recruitment, restaurants and retails. As social media is getting popular day by day, therefore developing social media marketing strategies provide long term benefits and opportunities to SMEs and brand.

5.3.3 Objective 3:

To provide some recommendations and suggestions in the light of estimated findings, that can save a brand from unexpected damages and threat, also help them to reach their potential customers.

Although, it has appeared that marketing via social media platforms provides several advantages and cost-efficient strategies to reach a large audience worldwide, however, SMEs may face a number of risks and challenges because social media marketing requires specialised knowledge in this field (Stelzner, 2011). Numerous SMEs have been seen adopting marketing activities through social sites due to easy to use and cost effectiveness, but previous research reveal that sometime social media can be hard to adopt and expensive due to several factors such as style of management, type of business, size and age (Cheng et al., 2015).

The study conclusion has disclosed the relation in range among restrained and sturdy concerning to the entire model. However, the study also defines the strongest relation of brand awareness with social media. Thus, the researcher absolutely consider that use of social media has an influence on brand awareness and praise those brands who uses social media in brand industry for direct and circumvent providing evidence about the product. In modern times, social media considered as a foundation for information penetrating, at the same time it is essential to investigate the differences in the demographic and other factors in order to avoid the threats and unexpected damages to the existing brands.

1. Possible Risks and Threats towards a brand image:

The term 'brand' can denote the people as well as things, and ideas, furthermore the procedure of targeting, positioning, and collaborating assistances (Stern, 2006). Branding is a multi-dimensional hypothesis that embraces product appearances as well as brand reputation or image, sustenance and dissemination services, company reputes, and company strategy (Cretu & Brodie, 2007; McQuiston, 2004). Similarly, brand insights are inclined, to some degree, by relations associated to the continuing affiliation, business standing and service knowledges. Brand sensitivity mentions to the mark, to which product evidence is aggressively reflected in administrative buying discussions (Hutton, 1997; Kapferer & Laurent, 1988). The brands are the most likely to affect the organisational purchasing process. Therefore, it proposes that convinced branding approaches are expected to be extra effective than others dependent on buying circumstances. So, it recommends that as buying risk upsurges, purchasing centre brand sensitivity will probably decline because consumers engaged in decision-making are expected to pursue, expose and highlight non-brand evidence to calculate the contending proposals. However, it is evident that decision makers have incomplete evidence handling capabilities; the risk or sensitivity towards brand image may upsurge as an appliance to diminish risk when the buying risk developments at higher levels (Tybout, Calder, & Sternthal, 1981).

SMEs are required to engage time and human resources to manage their online presence on social media sites effectively. It is extremely important for marketers or employees to respond actively to online consumer's messages, complaints and feedbacks on the daily basis. The employees who are engaged in social media activities with consumers should be highly trained so that they can handle any possible scenario, for instance, negative feedback or negative product review can be found by thousands of other customers if it will not manage appropriately on time, and thus it can damage product reputation and brand image (Gendel-Guterman and Levy, 2017).

Graph 45:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 353

Skipped: 69

The positive experience sharing may increase the sale of SMEs products/services but what about the negative experience sharing? It seems like a risk which can decrease the sale or may cause damage to branded products. It is usually expected that some observers are adequate for justifying risk; furthermore, the risk is infrequently studied beyond the evidence. (Dr. Lawrence F. Cunningham, 2004). To analyse the percentage of people who share their negative experiences on social media sites about the product, study conducts a question and with help of 353 responses findings (Graph 45) reveal that 16.43% are strongly agree about sharing negative experience with others, similarly a moderate proportion of people are also agree and some of them are somewhat agree on a sharing negative experience, having ratios of 29.75% and 27.48% respectively. A neutral cluster of people also exist with 16.71%, who neither agree nor disagree, and on the other side, 2.55% are somewhat disagree while 4.82% and 2.27% are disagree and strongly disagree respectively with this statement.

Studies demonstrate that consumers aim to find the product information as well as information about the brand and a business, or they tend to ask other individuals for some advice on social media sites (Dessart, 2017). This statement is also confirmed by the quantitative findings of this study, as the graph 30 describes that about 84% of participants prefer to know other people opinions regarding brands' products and services before making a purchase, and about 83% people believe that product reviews on social media sites are genuine and trustworthy (Graph, 9). Literature further defines that when the impression of supposed risk on the customer buying procedure for facilities is studied, the outcome of apparent risk is supposed to have a better result on the customer for facilities (Murray & Schlacter, 1990). In the same way services are usually imperceptible, no standardized, typically vended without assurances, and frequently need to be knowledgeable earlier they can be measured (Parasuraman, 1985). Mostly service buyers trust less on brand devotion and more deeply upon private evidence in order to decline the risk. (Dr. Lawrence and Cunningham, 2004).

2. Implementation of policy through social media in connection with potential customers:

Competition law has typically absorbed on 'unfair' interchange among competitors, more consideration may now to be located on the belongings of commercial observes on customer welfare, in terms of price, choice and convenience. John Vickers reproved that there is a movement to assimilate consumers and also competition laws, together procedurally as well as functionally, emphasizing the necessity of two strategies, 'effort jointly in tandem if not as one', similarly, 'Competition strategy should be buyer orientated and customer policy should have competition at its basic'. (Vickers, 2005).

Marketers are required to control and assess the results of social media marketing to understand the effectiveness of a particular marketing strategy. It is believed that different social media marketing channels have different impact on the businesses (Dessart et al., 2015), depending on the business type and customer target. So, according to Simon et al., (2016), marketers of SMEs are required to select an appropriate social media channel for a specific purpose. For instance, a new brand's product detailed video (as a user generated content) can be shared on YouTube through a social media influencer, as individuals believe that consumer generated content videos on social sites provides in-depth information about the product (Graph, 37).

Graph 46:

Source: Survey Monkey

Answered: 354

Skipped: 68

This study has tried to analyse if individuals like to buy a product that is recommended by an expert on social media channels such as on blogs and YouTube, because the percentage may reflect about the need of policy in order to meet the competition in the market. Consumer policy defines the mutual goals of serving markets; the two policies frequently target diverse kinds of manner in a non-interchangeable way: customer policy e.g., may point at confusing and misleading promotion, whereas the competition policy might aim at cartels. The results from the above graph show that participants who are strongly agreed, agreed and somewhat agreed with the above-mentioned statement are 13.56%, 31.64%, and 33.62% respectively. About 11.30% people are neither agreed nor disagreed about excavating expert judgments through social media. On the other hand, a small cluster of 3.95% are somewhat disagreed, 4.80% and 1.13% respondents are disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

Moving forward to the end of these discussions, the study has tried to address its three

objectives, and each objective consists of two questions. The research has summarized the study in this chapter, and then discussed its descriptive or econometric findings with the existing literature (Chapter 2) which provide the guidelines to the SMEs in understanding the impact of social media on brand awareness that may lead SMEs to develop a policy in order to capture their potential customers. The below figure 16 summaries the study.

Figure 18

Chapter 6: Conclusion & Recommendations

6.1 Introduction:

The concluding chapter of this thesis defines the conclusion by explaining the different contributions, implications, limitations, and future guidelines of this study. First, it sketches the influences of the knowledge in context of consumer engagement, social media and the brand awareness. Furthermore, it consequently deliberates the influences of the methodology on brand awareness. Secondly, it delivers the theoretical and descriptive implications that are based on a set of different contributions. Third, it will indicate the restrictions of this thesis. Finally, the guidelines for future research associated to this research topic are given in the last section.

Social media is considered as an integral part of daily life in today's modern information age as a communication network, and these channels reflect consumer's preferences, consumption habits, likes, dislikes, experiences and opinions (Dessart et al., 2015). Research in internet has proven that social media technology plays an essential role in how customers experience the brands (Vernuccio et al., 2015). Marketers can find various opportunities from this widespread communication area in which individuals interact with other online users. These networking sites provide substantial opportunities to marketers to improve their product communication actions, e.g., time, expenses, as well as facilitate to reach out of large audience. The networks of social media allow firms to create their own brand profiles, create social activities, and generate different video or image contents to share with the large consumer masses to engage them with their brand. This thesis has been conducted to examine whether social media channels play significant role to engage consumers and in creating brand awareness or not.

6.2 Contributions:

This thesis has delivered different contributions in terms of theoretical and practical fields through developing and by analysing the conceptual model that determine the impact of social media effectiveness on Brand awareness and consumer engagement in today's digital world. Study quantitative results review individual characteristics through descriptive analysis and statistical analysis, a distinctive set of individual characteristics identified, which enables SMEs to understand the individual's behaviours and attitudes and results also point out the various opportunities that social sites offer to SMEs and brands to reach

their potential customers and engaged them through different online activities. Basically, study defines different dimensions as a contribution towards literature including theoretical and practical, study discusses these contributions in the sections given below.

6.2.1 Theoretical Contribution:

The first contribution of this study is to provide a detail understanding about the role of social media platforms and their importance in terms of technology development which may lead to the ease of access between consumer and entrepreneur. Social media can adopt different actions like cooperating, swapping evidence, allocation and transfer of messages over an electric standard, attractive jointly and interrelating, allocation fillings like thoughts as well as texts and images (Thackeray et al., 2008), and it became obligatory component in numerous companies (Hanna et al., 2011). Social media was used to interconnect the people and blogs that were used to debate particular matters to the public. But now different trades are exploring these networks for the advancement and to improve their communication networks for consumers by discovering different opportunities. According to Simon et al., (2016) and Tafesse (2016), the extensive use of online social platforms such as YouTube, Instagram and Facebook have helped SMEs to find trends, individuals' characteristics and culture without any constrain of geographic boundaries.

The technology of social media is accelerating rapidly, and these social platforms are keep bringing new ways to enhance consumer engagement and brand awareness, and blogging has been growing consecutively and established positive reaction by audience (Hussey, 2012; Ta'eed, 2010; Chan, 2011). Social media is carrying the power from marketers and delivering it to the consumers. The study findings show that mostly individuals use social media channels many times per day, and they prefer to use these online channels to stay updated with the brands. So, marketers need to utilise this opportunity to promote their products by targeting these potential consumers on social sites. Brands have become more global and diffused across the borders and cultures due to technological advancement of these social platforms (Frank and Watchravesringkan, 2016). Furthermore, promotion is basically one way that customers study about new products. Social media networks are being used to find the trends, to compare the products and particularly to read other users reviews. This statement also has been confirmed in this study findings because no one desire to mark poor selections when it comes to buying (Evans, 2008).

Secondly, this study shows that how modern ways of social media marketing is replacing outdated and traditional ways of marketing strategies (Brodie et al., 2013), which necessarily help to build trust and loyalty of customers of their favourable potential brands (Hollebeek et al., 2014). It is problematic for many SMEs and new brands to run marketing campaigns on television and other traditional ways to reach out their potential customers, because it involves high cost, but now a day's social media marketing has altered the communication ways and delivers different approaches to reach their potential customers (Singh and Diamond, 2012). Furthermore, social media channels offer similar marketing opportunities to small-medium corporations with same prospects as large businesses. These social platforms are extremely valuable to develop strategies in accordance with consumer behaviour and tendencies. Progressive marketing blogs incline to participate with important social media podiums for the purpose of marketing, such as YouTube, Instagram and Facebook. The main determination of using blog marketing is to escalate the broadest outreach of consumers (Rose, 2011; Jett, 2012).

The research further emphasises on the importance of trust, a consumers' trust on a brand is considered a key of successful purchase (Brodie et al, 2013), and further indicates a communal mistake that takes place in businesses, that they are unable to think about the two parties who are involve in doing business. Any business which is about to commence, is necessarily demands respect and loyalty among stakes. Similarly, businesses should treat their consumer as allies and target them with customised messages according to their interest (Soderlund, 2001; Fournier,2011). To preserve a common and promising association, trust is measured as a mutual interest (Luck and Ginanti, 2013), and accordingly, if one party turns treacherously without others' it can be resulted in termination of associations. A fruitful and solid brand continuously tries to improve strong and long-term affiliation with potential customers, which results a comfortable business investment in brand improvement. (Martenson, 2007).

Moreover, loyalty is another important aspect of healthy relationship among brand and consumer, which represents the consumer commitment to repurchase a product/service form a brand despite competitors' actions and influences (Oliver, 1999). Behaviour of customer defines his loyalty about a particular brand. For example, how long he/she remain a customer for a particular brand, (Soderlund, 2001). It has examined that positive experience with a brand strengthen the brand image in consumers' mind directly and indirectly through customer engagement (Hepola et al., 2017), which leads to loyalty (Brakus et al., 2009) and equity (Mishra et al., 2014; Castañeda-García et al., 2018). The

findings of the study illustrate that a large portion 13.51%, 43.10% and 25.86% participants are strongly agreed, agreed and somewhat agreed respectively that engaging through social media activities with brands improve loyalty. Moreover, the study findings also demonstrate that respondents trust the product information and product reviews on the online sites, because they believe that these feedbacks are from genuine users. Loyal customers have positive impact on a business performance in a competitive environment (Lee et al., 2003).

Third, the thesis points out the important factors in social media marketing activities that can enhance brand awareness among consumers. A brand awareness shows the level of consumer acceptance, recognition, and a recall of a brand in any case (Perreault et al., 2013). It also can be defined as, “the ability of a potential buyer to recognize or recall that a brand is a member of a certain product category” (Aaker, 1991:61). Word of mouth plays an important role to create brand awareness, as it is emerged as the most powerful tool in brand building beside the product itself (Vark, 2007). Positive experience with a brand enhances customer satisfaction, which is considered an essential driver that leads to customer engagement and consumer loyalty towards a brand (Evan et al., 2008). It has been examined that customer satisfaction can be improved through social media platforms by connecting these satisfied consumers via different social marketing activities (Khan and Fasih, 2014), and these satisfied consumers facilitate in enhancing brand awareness among other consumers through word-of-mouth marketing, which is considered high valuable for any brand, and also leads to consumers loyalty (Tripathi, 2014). However, negative reviews and negative word of mouth marketing can damage the brand image/reputation as well as the whole marketing campaign (Cheung et al., 2009).

Brand performance and marketing effectiveness are the key awareness measures that are extensively used in a research, which commonly used to relate to brand awareness (Barroso and Llobet, 2012). Brands are considered as most valuable assets for an organisation these days that adds economic as well as strategic value to its proprietors. Positive communication, which is result of positive experience with a brand or product, on social media platforms can influence brand equity, which is a brand knowledge structure created in the consumers’ minds (Mishra et al., 2014; Castañeda-García et al., 2018). A brand equity knowledge is the feelings, thoughts, image, comprehension and experience in the consumer’s minds regarding a brand (Kotler and Keller, 2009). There are many advantages for SMEs having strong brand with positive brand equity such as brand extension opportunities, larger margins, great loyalty and increase marketing communication

effectiveness (Keller, 1993). Furthermore, research illustrate that high-level brand equity tend to lead higher individuals' preferences and buying intentions (Cobb-Walgren et al., 1995).

Marketers are appeared using social media tools to create and enhance brand relationship with their consumers. Brand awareness which is the result of consumers' exposure to brand (Alba and Hutchinson, 1987) plays an essential role in individuals' decision-making process through bringing three advantages which are learning, consideration and choice advantages (Keller, 1998). Social media channels are extremely popular now a days especially among modern/young consumers. Findings of the study highlight that participant use social media platforms daily to find trends, to communicate with others, to find product information, to read reviews, to pass their time, to stay updated with the latest information and to engage with brands. Thus, it is clear that an appropriate selection of social media channel for a brand can be exceptionally useful to reach out its potential consumers to create brand awareness and to improve their brand image/reputation.

Fourth, this study provides a broader view for SMEs to understand consumer engagement in value formation process from a customer perspective. Social media plays a vital role in customer engagement, this study findings highlight the link among customer engagement with brands through social media by enlighten different aspects. Social media offers online networks for communication and social interaction among people and different brands (Stelzner, 2009). According to Kim and Ko (2012), consumer engagement can be improved through social media marketing activities, as these activities are characterized as entertainment, interaction, word of mouth, product information and customised communication. Furthermore, entertainment is considered as an important component that encourages individuals' attitude/behaviour, stability, continuity to follow up, that creates positive feelings and emotions in the follower's attitude for a brand (Kang, 2005).

This research has investigated the logic, activities and other variables of participants which influences consumers engagement behaviour. Even though, there are many previous research that have investigated the behaviour of consumer engagement on social media channels (Maslowska et al., 2016; Brodie et al., 2011; Van Doorn et al., 2010), and few of them have been seen putting an effort to explore the process, antecedents and consequences of consumer engagement situation simultaneously. The findings from the online survey have provided some substantial evidence to advance the understandings regarding behaviours of modern consumer engagement in such study perspective. The results suggest

that brands are capable of engage modern consumers through appropriate selection of social media channels, and also able to understand individuals' behaviours and preferences. Young/modern generation are very active on the social media channels, and various contents and information are being shared simultaneously on these channels in real time, thus, these online sites has become up-to-date and latest source of information for businesses as well for people (Hamid et al., 2016). Moreover, positive experience with brands improves consumer satisfaction, which leads to customer engagement and signifies healthy relationship and loyalty towards a brand (Evan et al., 2008).

Although, social media delivers lots of opportunities for the businesses having online presence, but also includes numerous challenges and threats and provide a medium to share the information which is available for everyone (Hart el., 2000). So, among customers anyone can leave the positive or negative reviews for products. These negative reviews/feedbacks may cause destruction for the reputation of brand which surely will not capture and engage customers. Similarly, it is obvious in literature that it is easier to engage the customers through social media as compared to other traditional methods and as it is discussed throughout the argument, that positive feedback can create positive word of mouth and develop customer satisfaction that leads consumer loyalty towards a brand. (Cheung, Lee and Thadani.,2009; Dutta., 2010).

Finally, this study provides the understanding about the customer activities and preferences in consumer's daily life. It was necessary to analyse the daily interest of the consumers in order to suggest the suitable strategy to engage them and to attract them. To achieve this aim, this study has included several questions in online survey and findings have provided valuable information an insight looks regarding their preferences (Chapter, 4). Literature illustrates that one of the crucial elements that encourages individuals' behaviour is entertainment, it develops positive feelings and emotions regarding brand in the follower's minds on the social media networks (Kang, 2005). According to Manthiou et al., (2013), a user emphasises the content that arouses his attention if he finds the content pleasing and amusing. In this way, businesses can encourage individuals liking and sharing entertaining contents and would be able to turn it into their advantages by reaching to large audience (Schivinski and Dabrowski, 2015).

Modern consumers like to share their experiences and stories with other online consumers on social sites in such manners that influence the understandings of other consumers about the brand or product (Hughes et al., 2016). According to Andreini et al., (2018), experiences

are considered as key aspect in understanding the way individuals react and assess a brand. People have been seen engaging and interacting with brands' social marketing activities in various ways in order to assess them (Baxter et al., 2018), sometimes they are also appeared as to co-create these experiences (Rialti et al., 2018). As per noted by Seidman (2013), individual differences and personality traits are the driving factors of consumer online engagement and individuals' personal characteristics are the primary intention of joining social media activities. Furthermore, addition of latest trends and fast fashion characteristics in social media marketing activities can influence consumers to express their individual's lifestyles and fashion attitudes (Gabrielli et al., 2013). Dessart (2017) also added that most of individuals try to obtain information regarding a brand, product and a firm and consult other consumers on social media sites for some advice. According to Schultz and Schultz (2004), It has been examined that it is not possible to manage online brand through a pre-determined and well-structured manner like the way a factory can run.

Although social media marketing allows brands and firms to spread their messages effortlessly and have communication with their consumers without any geographical restrictions, nevertheless, marketers are required to put some efforts to understand the individuals' personality traits and preferences that can facilitate to select an appropriate social platform and right contents to attract online users (Chang et al., 2015). This study opens an understanding about customer engagement process, which has responded the questions concerning when, where and how customers' engagement can take place. Moreover, it has also examined in this study that what activities are involved in the brand awareness process. Precisely, the results of this thesis reflect that most of the customers prefer to get in touch with brands through social media and actively participate in social activities initiated by brands, and these customers typically browse and connect with international brands many times per day. In descriptive findings, it is evident that customers also like to engage in dialogues and communications with brands.

6.2.2 Practical Contribution:

This thesis has been capable to deliver some applied contributions to support the international brands for capturing their potential customers through social media marketing strategies on international networking platforms. Firstly, like some of other existing studies (e.g., Erkan ad Evans, 2016; Kim and Song, 2018), a mix sample of individuals (male and female) is adopted between 18-40 age group in this research, who actively engaged in social media activities and follow international brands rather than general consumer sample. To

understand the customers' motivations in terms of engaging with brands, this study has defined that which type of customer gain bigger chances to get insight the brand-facilitated events on social media rather than the other common social media users. In the same way, social media networks undertake online businesses and generate many details for different SMEs to go online and enhance their marketing for customer engagement by establishing a brand. The value of different social media stations, essentially become much important and displays its appearance online (Gummesson, 2002).

Secondly, this research was conducted in a pandemic situation, via online survey through survey monkey, which ultimately delivers exceptionally distinct findings to understand the scenario of brands and customers in current pandemic situation. On the other hand, many studies argue that numerous SMEs wish to use predictable promotion techniques rather than different blog for treatment of those promotion concerns that may not be involved in customer concerns (Walsh and Lipinski, 2009).

Thirdly, the target groups of people in terms of their ages were selected (between 18 – 40 years) for this research by conducting online survey, so that results can be applied to overall modern consumers who use social media sites. According to the descriptive and econometric results, it has evident in this study that by considering social media as a medium of exchange information and communication between customers and brands, it will ultimately lead towards the enhancement of brand awareness and consumer engagement. Therefore, by observing the individuals' characteristics in terms of product and brands, the implications can be utilised by SMEs for their brands enhancement. Based on these contributions, the implications on this research are discussed in the next section.

6.3 Implications of research findings:

This section presents theoretical and managerial implications in the light of discussion (section 5), based on the contributions discussed earlier in the section 6.2.

6.3.1 Theoretical implications:

Looking at theoretical perspective of this study, it illustrates numerous major arguments about brand awareness, customer engagement and social media marketing communication. Firstly, this thesis highlights the trend, impact and role of social media platforms in today's modern era, that is emerged in consumer's daily life and ecosystem. This finding offers outstanding opportunities for brands to understand the value of social media networks to

enhance consumer engagement. This phenomenon requires from firm to concentrate on consumers' desire, attitudes and behaviours, which is possible through social media channels (Paek & Nelson, 2009; Alexander & Jaakkola, 2015). In the same way, obsessive elements for oblivious procedures indicate that many buyers answer to their opinions about the experiences of the branded product (Abdul et al., 2011; Hollebeek et al., 2014).

Secondly, this research suggests that social media channels enhance communication among consumers and brands which leads to better consumer engagement. Compared to previous studies, customer engagement policies should look into their characteristics, establishments' goals, occupational competition and also economic times. In the same way the policy for customer engagement must include essential customer choices, their loyalty as well as brand equity and provide opportunities for new product development (Hoyer *et al.*, 2010; Verhoef, *et al.*, 2010). But this study has considered customer's preferences reflects by the use of social media, as it defines the behaviour of customers towards brands by using social network sites. The quantitative findings also confirmed that the use of social media has positive effect on brand awareness' reflecting those different types of online promotion activities leads towards enrichment and helps to welcome upcoming brands. However, the daily life of customer which elaborates in marketing practices may define further and explored in future.

Thirdly, this research agrees and enlightens the fact that consumers use social media platforms for finding desired information as well as also for understanding the fashions and trends of the market. In addition, individuals are appeared sharing their experiences with other online users on social media sites. These experiences can be positive or negative, consumers' positive experiences enhance consumer satisfaction that led to positive WOM (word of mouth), which is considered high valuable marketing to improve brand awareness. Both the statistical and descriptive results proved that negative customer reviews have inverse relation with the brand awareness while positive customer reviews have direct relationship with response variable of this study. The study findings also suggest that customer that have bad experience with the product or service, tend to share their experience on social sites and leave the negative review, which considerably has bad impact on the product image of the certain brand, and it also discourage other potential consumers. Furthermore, study also assessed the clusters in terms of individuals' preferences to get in touch with their desired brands.

Fourth, by investigating the quantitative results, this study has been capable to deliver numerous implications for customers' online engagement with brands. It highlights that customers like to share and express their thoughts and experiences on social networking platform regarding brands and their products. There are several other individual's preferences and pattern are examined in this study such as particular way to find product information, whether they read product reviews prior to make a purchase, if the reviews are trustworthy, their preference to get in touch with brands, if they feel sense of happiness and pass their time away by engaging with brands on online sites etc. Moreover, customer also expects to attain higher level of service from their online engagement experience. The study also indicates that this study data is collected during pandemic situation of Covid-19, thus, researchers should explore again the individuals' characteristics and preference from a customer perspective after this situation.

6.3.2 Managerial implications:

This research contributions delivers numerous implications and directions for marketers to design the strategies and activities for social media marketing that can facilitate consumer engagement and enhance brand awareness through social media.

First of all, the social media users, who showed their willingness for the development of this thesis and shared their experiences regarding international brands and different social media networks, were generally modern/young consumers between 18 and 40 age group and appeared extremely active on social media. Most of them were well-aware with the idea of this study. They have shared their purchase preferences and experiences with products and brands through social media. Thus, the results of the study suggest that SMEs and international brands can develop and maintain a sustainable relationship with these modern consumers through the effective use of social media channels, and marketers can enhance consumer engagement with their existing customers through social media activities to improve consumer loyalty. Similarly, study also suggests that brands need to put some more efforts to add some entertaining and other important aspects into their marketing campaigns according to individuals' traits on social media channels to attract more consumers, and marketers need to keep posting on these social channels regularly to keep them engaged.

The findings suggest that many participants agreed that they spend their free on social media channels by looking for trends, fashion contents, entertaining videos, user-generated

videos and new brands or products. Furthermore, findings indicate that consumers are highly influenced by consumer generated contents and tend to exchange information after using a product or a particular brand. Based on quantitative findings, study presents some valuable suggestions for marketers as below:

1. Facilitating the social activities that develop customer to customer interactions

As the quantitative findings of descriptive analysis and statistical analysis reveals that consumers spend most of their free time on social media channels and like to share their purchasing experiences and other valuable information with other consumers. So, marketers need to design their social or other marketing activities in such a way that can stimulate the customer's interactions to exchange their opinions with other potential customers. Moreover, the findings also suggest that although, modern consumers have become more independent than ever before, however, they heavily rely on friends/family recommendations and other consumers' opinions, their purchase experiences, and their reference group on social channels. Thus, marketers need to encourage these consumers to invite their peers or friends in engaging together with brand activities.

2. Facilitating the social activities to encourage consumers to share their interests

As literature states that social media allows individuals with same interest to come together and share their opinions, ideas and other valuable information, the findings also indicates that consumers have more opportunities to interact with other users with same interest on social media. Hence, brands' marketers can create various interesting topics (such as traveling, film, music, news, good and festival) according to consumer's interests, to encourage them to share with other users/customers with the similar interests, and then brands can build and expand their personal relationship with these new consumers on social media after the interaction.

3. Facilitating the social activities to encourage consumers to help each other

As findings suggests that consumers like to share their purchase experiences and opinions with friends and other online users to help them to choose right product/service. The brand's marketers should encourage these consumers to provide assistance whenever they see any question asked from others on the social media channels or a brand page, and such consumers who always contribute their expertise to help others should be rewarded by the

brands. Because these positive interactions between consumers can create word-of-mouth marketing, which can easily attract many more potential consumers.

Secondly, Finding also directs that the higher opportunities are available to engage and reach modern customers through social media marketing as compared to other traditional ways such as television, radio and magazines etc, that may permit customers to find relevant aspects needed in their purchase and compare mutual interests among brands and themselves. Social media sites (e.g., Facebook, YouTube, Instagram) advertise and target according to individuals' searching behaviour, attitudes, and daily life routine patterns. In addition, result shows that customers' engagement would also be possible by expressing their own thoughts which helps SMEs to launch a successful campaign by keeping in view the demands of consumers and it may lead the brands for encouragement of customers by asking and analysing the intensity of interaction with social media activities. Thesis also emphasizes the importance of customer preferred medium to get in touch with brands, whether it is Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn and TikTok etc. Similarly, study also define the intensity of customers enjoyment in case of gathering information through social media networks.

Third, both descriptive and statistical findings of this thesis reveal that brand awareness can be improved through the increase in promotional activities as well as effected by ground realities of the host country. The findings reflects that the increase in brand awareness can be developed if customers get their answers of their queries from their desired brands on time, as it gives them a high level of satisfaction and enhance customer engagement. More specifically, the quantitative findings reveal that the increase in sense of happiness directly related customer's brand awareness and engagement. In other words, brands need to hire devoted social media staffs that may work for capturing potential customers and help them to gain sense of happiness while getting in touch with social media networks of brands. For instance, this study results suggest finding a celebrity or an influencer to endorse the brands' products on his social media account.

Moreover, quantitative findings demonstrate that many customers tend to engage with brands' social media sites to stay updated with new products and promotions that may impact purchase intention or brand awareness. This study strongly recommends that it is necessary for brands to keep posting blogs, brand updates and other social activities regularly to keep their online consumers engaged, to enhance consumer engagement and to create brand awareness through positive e-WOM. The study further suggests that brands

may need to use some tactics to motivate customers to provide the product feedbacks towards branded products that can help in the improvement of products and services, and it can attract other potential consumers.

6.4 Contribution to the SMEs sector:

The results of this study provide substantial opportunities to SMEs to improve their product communication actions such as time, expenses and facilitate them to reach out to a large population. The findings suggest to SMEs to create their own brand profiles, create social activities, and generate image and video contents to share with a large consumer masses which can assist to attract and engage them with their brands. The findings also illustrate that social media platforms e.g., Facebook, Instagram and YouTube can help SMEs to find trends, individuals' characteristics and culture without any constraints of geographical boundaries. Furthermore, results show that modern consumers like to share their experiences with their friends, family and other online communities, which can create word of mouth that plays as an essential role to create brand awareness. Similarly, positive experience with a brand enhances customer satisfaction which is considered as valuable driver that leads to customer engagement and customer loyalty towards a brand. Therefore, the study recommends the SMEs to facilitate the social activities that develop customer to customer interactions and encourage them to share their experiences. In addition, it has been examined that customer satisfaction can be improved through social media platforms by connecting these satisfied consumers via different social marketing activities (Khan and Fasih, 2014), and these satisfied consumers facilitate in enhancing brand awareness among other consumers through word-of-mouth marketing, which is considered high valuable for any brand, and also leads to consumers loyalty (Tripathi, 2014). Moreover, it has proved in the findings and literature that it is easier to engage modern consumers through social media platforms as compared to traditional ways, and customer's positive feedback can create positive word of mouth and develop customer satisfaction which leads to consumer loyalty.

The research findings agree and enlighten the fact that individuals use online social sites to find and understand the fashions and trends of the market as well as to find other desired information, so SMEs having social media presence can also find the latest trends and consumers behaviour. UGC (user-generated-contents) are appeared very popular in these days, and UGC are considered extremely authentic by consumers. Findings (Graph 20) show that about 74% agree with the statement that they trust on UGC and prefer to buy a

product that is recommended buy them, and it has also appeared in the study that these users/consumers generated videos provide in-depth information about the product. Therefore, it is recommended to SMEs to find the experts and social media influencers who have millions of followers to use their products and provide the in-depth feedback on social media platforms. Moreover, the study outcomes provide SMEs and marketers several other modern consumers preferences and patterns of daily routines regarding brands and products on social sites such as particular ways to find product information, whether they read product reviews prior to make purchase, whether they believe that reviews are trust worthy, how they prefer to get in touch with brands etc.

This research suggests to SMEs that social media channels enhance communication activities among consumers and brands which leads to better consumer engagement. Although, social media sites provides a number of advantages nevertheless, these platforms also involves numerous risks and challenges. Customers with bad experience can leave negative feedback / negative product reviews, and results of the study show that consumers do not buy products with negative reviews so it is recommended that SMEs should handle these feedbacks appropriately in their earliest possible time, because these reviews and feedbacks can damage the brand images/reputation (Ullrich and Brunner, 2015; Cheung et al., 2009), which definitely will not help to capture and engage the consumers. In addition, quantitative outcomes of the study shows that consumers trust the reviews given on social media platforms and they read product reviews before making a purchase, so marketers of SMEs need to manage these positive and negative reviews carefully. This research recommends SMEs to provide appropriate time for these social media channels in order to determine suitable ways to handle these crisis situations more effectively such as fake news (Berthon et al., 2018), brand sabotages (Kahr et al., 2016), negative publicity (Gendel-Guterman and Levy, 2017), negative reviews (Ullrich and Brunner, 2015) and collaborative brand attacks or online firestorms (Rauschnabel et al., 2016), with an emphasis on adjusting these negative experiences according to their nature. Hence, social media marketing must be managed appropriately because reputational risks can be easily exceeded than the reputational advantages on social media networks.

6.5 Research limitations:

This study has tried to assess the impact and role of social media networks to engage modern consumers and to create brand awareness. Although this thesis has delivered several contributions towards knowledge and practice however, it also comprises several limitations.

First, in terms of the brand awareness, there are many other factors that may have not been considered to understand brand awareness through social media. This study has recognized some factors of consumer perceptions and social media use that can reveal the customers online activities in context of engagement with brands on different networking sites. However, as brand awareness is not a much complex concept, but it also cannot be established properly by only two factors i.e., use of social media and customer engagement, this should need additional investigation to find out some more potential factors that can denote brand awareness.

Second, in regard to the customer engagement, this study did not much discuss about the entertainment factors involved on social media. For instance, celebrity endorsements that are more extensively used approach of using celebs as a publicity tool but necessarily the choice of the celebrity should be similar with the culture and society (Seno & Bryan, 2007). The future study is suggested to explore some specific contents that should be elaborate in terms of entertainment activities on social media. Furthermore, some other concepts like organic e-WOM and amplified e-WOM are essentially required to be re-defined and endorsed properly.

Third, concerning the magnitude of customer engaging on social media for brand awareness, this thesis has conversed more about the positive side as compared to the negative outcomes in terms of excess use of social media. However, it is appreciated to discover the negative impacts and conflicts that may produce from excess use of social media for brand awareness; by exploring these negative impacts, the understanding of customers engagement behaviour on social networking sites can also possible.

Fourth, the result of this study belongs to the scope pandemic time of Covid-19. The data from the respondents was collected during pandemic crisis. It is possible that customers' thoughts may have changed due to pandemic situation of covid-19, as changing the habits of consumer spending as a result of Covid-19 pandemic contributed to the spike in ecommerce sale because of lockdown and the fear of contracting the virus that kept

consumers away from the digital stores. For instance, US retailers' online sales went up 44% from \$598.02 billion in 2019 to \$861.12 billion in 2020 (Digital Commerce 360, 2021).

Figure 19, Source: Digital Commerce 360 (15 Feb 2021).

In addition, the researcher has only collected the individual responses; it can also be possible to undertake future research that responses should also be collected from the branded companies towards their potential customers.

Fifth, study tried to collect a sample of (n=422) to generate a consistent outcome of the regression model, but 21 of the respondents' data removed in terms of clearing data, the target respondents of this sample were the individuals aged between 18-40, which specifies that the findings from the online survey could not deliver much comprehensive findings. In order to understand the complete picture customers' engagement through brand awareness by using social media, future research must undertake respondents aged more than 40 years in order to provide purposeful implications for the brands.

6.6 Directions for future research:

The aim of this section is to provide some suggestions for the future research to extend the understanding towards consumer engagement behaviour and brand awareness through social media.

At first, this study has tried to develop a case study for SMEs and brands in order to engage their potential customers by using social media networking sites. The purpose of this thesis is to identify the attributes and characteristics of targeted customers via social media channels. Social media marketing strategies offer SMEs and brands inexpensive means to market their products, but lack of knowledge and inappropriate approaches could be a challenge for them. It is widely accepted that sometimes SMEs failed to compete with large organisations because of less resources and inappropriate marketing strategies (Weinberg and Pehlivan, 2011; Stokes, 2011). Therefore, in the light of above discussion it is recommended for future research to discover the causes of failure of SMEs among large organisations in terms of their potential skills as well as to define the ways of generating sufficient resources for the brand competition.

Secondly, by considering brand awareness and customer engagement, this thesis finds valuable implications by undertaking descriptive research and employing multiple regression technique. But to get insight of brand awareness process, new and other methods such as interviews and experiments are essential and need to be adopted in future research, as new methods which are connected to individuals' nervous system are able to provide accurately more insights of consumers' mind and logic (Finne and Gronroos, 2017). These new techniques can help to get some more valuable implications which ultimately will allow SMEs and brands to reach their potential customers around the globe.

Third, future study is required to conduct a comparative research between different cultures to analyse the difference of consumers' behaviours, preferences and engagement logics. This type of study would be able to investigate the psychological factors that influence on the consumers' online social behaviours of western and non-western countries. In addition, future studies can examine the comparison of different brands by undertaking demographical and cultural factors that influence on the consumers. Furthermore, the future research also suggests associating the different online tools for brand awareness other than social media, in both western and non-western culture that may deliver some valuable implications for brands to design their marketing strategies.

Fourth, the findings of this thesis have acknowledged that brand awareness is positively related with the use of electronic media and large proportion of customers are satisfied in terms of online shopping by considering positive customer reviews and consumers generated contents. Findings also acknowledged that the higher use of social media in current times is because of covid-19 pandemic situation, so the future research can examine the effect of pandemic situation on purchase decisions and individuals' social behaviour engagement.

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- The research ‘Muhammad Mateen Anjum’ will be conducting this research for his doctorate thesis under the supervision of relevant university members, such as, Bronwyn Betts.
- Quantitative data will be collected through online survey by releasing the questionnaires through emails and other social sites such as Facebook, WhatsApp, and Viber etc.
- The collected data will be stored for 6 years and then it will be disposed of under the Data Protection Act, 1998. The questionnaires were designed in ethical way to avoid participants personal information. It was totally depending on individual’s willingness whether they want to take part or not, and no one was forced to participate. In addition, all questionnaires were lawful, and all questions were relevant to the academic fundamentals. In addition, respondents’ information will not be published, and researcher will respect their opinions and views and will not create any harm towards their personal interests. All the personal and relevant information gathered through interviews and questionnaires will be securely deleted (Data Protection Act, 1998). Everything will be conducted according to ethics regulation of UWS.
- The data will be kept in electronically password protected file in the University server. If for some reason, researcher needs to store this electronic data at a different server, then it will be store in an encrypted manner to ensure data is kept secure.
- The research was reviewed and passed by the ethics committee at West Scotland University.

What is involved in the study?

Quantitative Data (Questionnaires) will be collected through an invitation for the online survey via Survey Monkey using emails and other social media channels (e.g., Facebook, Viber, WhatsApp). A cover page will be shown to all the Participants, clearly stating the survey purpose and respondents’ conditions before they enter the online survey with close-ended questions. No one will be force forced to participate.

Will your participation in this research remain anonymous?

Your participation will remain anonymous throughout the research.

What are the risks involved in this study?

There will be no risk involved in this study. As far as possible participants' contribution will be kept confidential. You will have the opportunity to remove any information or images at any stage of the research.

What are the benefits for taking part in this study?

As this research is targeting modern's consumer regarding their online social media activities (18-40 age group), so, participants may enjoy taking part in this research. Once this primary research will be completed, it will provide guidelines to the marketers on how they can improve their social marketing strategies to capture more consumers.

What are your rights as a participant?

Taking part in the study is voluntary. You may choose not to take part or subsequently cease participation at any time.

Will I receive any payment or monetary benefits?

You will receive no payment for your participation.

Appendix B: Participant consent from

Title of Project:

Assessing the impact of social media to engage modern consumers and to create brand awareness.

Name of Researcher:

Muhammad Mateen Anjum

Please initial box

1. I confirm that I have read the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason

3. I understand that data collected might be examined by the relevant member of University of the West of Scotland, when necessary, I hereby give permission for them to have access to information provided.

I agree to take part in the above study.

Name of Participant Date Signature

Name of Researcher Date Signature

Appendix C: Main Survey

Main Survey

Q1. Your age is between 18-40.

Answer Choices

Yes

No

Q2. Do you use social media?

Answer Choices

Yes

No

Q3. Are you willing to share your experience and opinion about following and interacting the social media and brands?

Answer Choices

Yes

No

Q4. If you agree to take part in this survey voluntarily, please tick the box

Answer Choices

Yes

No

Q5. What is your gender?

Answer Choices

Male

Female

Prefer not to say

Q6. What is your age?

Answer Choices

18-24

25-30

31-40

41+

Q7. What is your education level?

Answer Choices

High school or lower

College

Bachelor's Degree

Master's Degree

Doctorate/PHD or higher

Q8. What is your occupation?

Answer Choices

Employed

Self-employed

Part-time employed

Student

Not working

Q9. What is your yearly income?

Answer Choices

Under Â£10,000

Between Â£10,000 and Â£29,999

Between Â£30,000 and Â£39,999

Over Â£40,000

Not working at the moment

Prefer not to say

Q10. How much monthly do you spend on online shopping and brands?

Answer Choices

Less than £200

Between £200 - £499

Between £500-£999

Between £1,000 and £2,000

Over £2,000

Q11. Do you use social media channels to stay updated with brands?

Answer Choices

Very likely

Likely

Somewhat likely

Neither likely nor unlikely

Somewhat unlikely

Unlikely

Very unlikely

Q12. How often do you interact or engage with fashion brands' social media activities?

Answer Choices

Many times per day

Once or twice per day

3 to 5 times per week

Once a week

Less than once a week

Q13. In a typical month, which of the following social networking websites do you use most

often?

Answer Choices

You Tube

Facebook

Google+

Myspace

Tagged

Twitter
Instagram
Linkedin
TikTok
Other (please specify)

Q14. How often do you use social media channels?

Answer Choices

Daily
3 to 5 times a week
Weekly
Monthly
Don't Use

Q15. Do you use social media channels to find product information?

Answer Choices

Very likely
Likely
Somewhat likely
Neither likely nor unlikely
Somewhat unlikely
Unlikely
Very unlikely

Q16. Do you use social media networks to read product reviews?

Answer Choices

Very likely
Likely
Somewhat likely
Neither likely nor unlikely
Somewhat unlikely
Unlikely
Very unlikely

Q17. Which particular way you prefer to find product information

Answer Choices

Networking and micro blogging platforms such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter

E-commerce channels such as Amazon and eBay

Brands website such as Samsung and Apple

Consumer generated photos and video sharing sites such as You Tube

Tv, radio and news channels

Other (please specify)

Q18. Which particular reasons you use social media in terms of product and services?

Answer Choices

To look offers/sales

To find product information

To read product reviews

To find trends

To find a brand information

to engage with brands

Other (please specify)

Q19. Do you believe the information provided on social media is trustworthy?

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q20. Do campaigns and advertisings on social media impact your purchasing behaviour?

Answer Choices

Very likely
Likely
Somewhat likely
Neither likely nor unlikely
Somewhat unlikely
Unlikely
Very unlikely

Q21. Do you get enough information from social media channels to make a decision?

Answer Choices

Very likely
Likely
Somewhat likely
Neither likely nor unlikely
Somewhat unlikely
Unlikely
Very unlikely

Q22. Do your friends share their experiences on social media sites?

Answer Choices

Very likely
Likely
Somewhat likely
Neither likely nor unlikely
Somewhat unlikely
Unlikely
Very unlikely

Q23. How would you prefer to know about new brands/products?

Answer Choices

Through TV and radio
Through social media channels
Through News papers

Through banners and advertisement

Other (please specify)

Q24. How would you prefer to get in touch with brands?

Answer Choices

Emails

Social media channels

Calls

By Post

Other (please specify)

Q25. Advertising and brand messages are better on social media than TV, radio and newspaper.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q26. I recommend a product/service to a friend or family member.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q27. I trust the product reviews given on social media.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q28. I share a positive experience with a brand or a product/service on social media channels.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q29. I share a negative experience with a brand or a product/service on social media channels.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q30. I buy a product that is recommended by a friend or family member.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q31. I buy a product that is recommended by an expert on social media channels such as YouTube and Blogs.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q32. I buy a product that is recommended through consumer-generated content.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q33. I am loyal to only few particular brands.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree
Somewhat agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Somewhat disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q34. I enjoy gathering brand and product information on social media networks.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Somewhat agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Somewhat disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q35. I usually search for information about international brands on social media channels.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree
Somewhat agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Somewhat disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q36. It's easy to get the most recent information regarding brand information on social channels.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree
Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q37. I use social media channels to read product reviews.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q38. My friends and colleagues usually tag me on the brand's post that has useful information.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q39. It saves me time to contact and respond to brands through social media.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q40. I prefer to know about new brands and products through social media.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q41. I prefer to know other people opinions in regards to a new brand's product or services.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q42. I prefer to read users reviews of a new product/service on social media channels before

making a purchase.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q43. I buy products that have positive customers reviews.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q44. I buy products that have negative customers reviews.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q45. Social media channels show the true image of a brand.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q46. It is easy to contact brands on social sites.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q47. Brands respond to me quickly and efficiently on social sites.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q48. Interacting with International brands through social media makes me feel comfortable

and more engaged.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q49. Consumer-generated content video on social sites (such as on YouTube) provides in-

depth information about the product.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q50. I found myself sharing my opinion about international brands and products with other

experts especially with some celebrities on social media.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q51. I gained a sense of happiness from engaging with brands through social media.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q52. I pass my time away by engaging with brands on social media.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q53. I would like to purchase more from a brand's product if they continue to involve me in

social media activities and interactions.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q54. Engaging through social media with brands improve loyalty.

Answer Choices

Strongly agree

Agree

Somewhat agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Somewhat disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Appendix D: Pilot Survey

Pilot Survey

Q1. Your age is between 18-40.

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Yes	84.62%	11
No	15.38%	2
Answered		13
Skipped		0

Q2. Do you use social media?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Yes	100.00%	13
No	0.00%	0
Answered		13
Skipped		0

Q3. Are you willing to share your experience and opinion about following and interacting the socialmedia and brands?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Yes	100.00%	13
No	0.00%	0
Answered		13
Skipped		0

Q4. If you agree to take part in this survey voluntarily, please tick the box

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Yes	100.00%	13
No	0.00%	0
Answered		13
Skipped		0

Q5. What is your gender?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Male	50.00%	6
Female	50.00%	6
Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
Answered		12
Skipped		1

Q6. What is your age?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
18-24	8.33%	1
25-30	58.33%	7
31-40	16.67%	2
41+	16.67%	2
Answered		12
Skipped		1

Q7. What is your education level?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
High school or lower	8.33%	1

College	16.67%	2
Bachelor's Degree	33.33%	4
Master's Degree	8.33%	1
Doctorate/PHD or higher	33.33%	4
	Answered	12
	Skipped	1

Q8. What is your occupation?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Employed	41.67%	5
Self-employed	8.33%	1
Part-time employed	25.00%	3
Student	8.33%	1
Not working	16.67%	2
	Answered	12
	Skipped	1

Q9. What is your yearly income?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Under Â£10,000	8.33%	1
Between Â£10,000 and Â£29,999	58.33%	7
Between Â£30,000 and Â£39,999	8.33%	1
Over Â£40,000	0.00%	0
Not working at the moment	25.00%	3
	Answered	12
	Skipped	1

Q10. How much monthly do you spend on online shopping and brands?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Less than Â£200	33.33%	4
Between Â£200 - Â£499	41.67%	5
Between Â£500-Â£999	16.67%	2
Between Â£1,000 and Â£2,000	8.33%	1
Over Â£2,000	0.00%	0
	Answered	12
	Skipped	1

Q11. How often do you interact or engage with fashion brands' social media activities?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Many times per day	33.33%	4
Once or twice per day	33.33%	4
3 to 5 times per week	8.33%	1
Once a week	16.67%	2
Less than once a week	8.33%	1
	Answered	12
	Skipped	1

Q12. Do you use social media?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Yes	91.67%	11
No	8.33%	1
	Answered	12
	Skipped	1

Q13. Do you use social media channels to stay updated with brands?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Yes	83.33%	10
No	16.67%	2
	Answered	12
	Skipped	1

Q14. In a typical month, which of the following social networking websites do you use most often?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
You Tube	75.00%	9
Facebook	58.33%	7
Google+	25.00%	3
Myspace	0.00%	0
Tagged	8.33%	1
Twitter	33.33%	4
Instagram	58.33%	7
LinkedIn	8.33%	1
TikTok	16.67%	2
Other (please specify)	0.00%	0
	Answered	12
	Skipped	1

Q15. How often do you use social media channels?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Daily	72.73%	8
3 to 5 times a week	18.18%	2
Weekly	9.09%	1
Monthly	0.00%	0
Don't Use	0.00%	0
	Answered	11
	Skipped	2

Q16. Do you use social media channels to find product information?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Yes	100.00%	11
No	0.00%	0
	Answered	11
	Skipped	2

Q17. Do you use social media to read product reviews?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Yes	90.91%	10
No	9.09%	1
	Answered	11
	Skipped	2

Q18. Which particular way you prefer to find product information

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Networking and micro blogging platforms such as Fa	63.64%	7
E-commerce channels such as Amazon and eBay	45.45%	5
Brands website such as Samsung and Apple	18.18%	2
Consumer generated photos and video sharing sites	27.27%	3
Tv, radio and news channels	0.00%	0

Other (please specify)	0.00%	0
Answered		11
Skipped		2

Q19. Which particular reasons you use social media in terms of product and services?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
To look offers/sales	54.55%	6
To find product information	36.36%	4
To read product reviews	63.64%	7
To find trends	27.27%	3
To find a brand information	9.09%	1
to engage with brands	9.09%	1
Other (please specify)	0.00%	0

Answered	11
Skipped	2

Q20. Do you believe the information provided on social media is trustworthy?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Yes	60.00%	6
No	40.00%	4
Answered		10
Skipped		3

Q21. Do campaigns and advertisings on social media impact your purchasing behaviour?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Yes	100.00%	10
No	0.00%	0
Answered		10
Skipped		3

Q22. Do you get enough information from social media channels to make decision?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Yes	70.00%	7
No	30.00%	3
Answered		10
Skipped		3

Q23. Do your friends share their experiences on social media sites?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Yes	63.64%	7
No	36.36%	4
Answered		11
Skipped		2

Q24. How do you prefer brands to get in touch with you?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Emails	72.73%	8
Social media channels	45.45%	5
calls or texts	9.09%	1
By post	0.00%	0

Other (please specify)	0.00%	0
Answered		11
Skipped		2

Q25. How would you prefer to know about new brands?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Through TV and radio	9.09%	1
Through social media channels	100.00%	11
Through News papers	0.00%	0
Through banners and advertisement	18.18%	2
Other (please specify)	0.00%	0
Answered		11
Skipped		2

Q26. How would you prefer to get in touch with brands?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Emails	63.64%	7
Social media channels	54.55%	6
Calls	18.18%	2
By Post	9.09%	1
Other (please specify)	0.00%	0
Answered		11
Skipped		2

Q27. Advertising and brand messages are better on social media than TV, radio and newspaper.

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	9.09%	1
Agree	54.55%	6
Somewhat agree	36.36%	4
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0
Somewhat disagree	0.00%	0
Disagree	0.00%	0
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
Answered		11
Skipped		2

Q28. I recommend a product/service to a friend or family member?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	36.36%	4
Agree	36.36%	4
Somewhat agree	18.18%	2
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0
Somewhat disagree	9.09%	1
Disagree	0.00%	0
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
Answered		11
Skipped		2

Q29. I trust the product reviews given on social media.

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	9.09%	1
Agree	27.27%	3
Somewhat agree	27.27%	3
Neither agree nor disagree	18.18%	2

Somewhat disagree		9.09%	1
Disagree		9.09%	1
Strongly disagree		0.00%	0
	Answered		11
	Skipped		2

Q30. I look for trends on social media channels

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree		44.44%	4
Agree		33.33%	3
Somewhat agree		0.00%	0
Neither agree nor disagree		11.11%	1
Somewhat disagree		0.00%	0
Disagree		11.11%	1
Strongly disagree		0.00%	0
	Answered		9
	Skipped		4

Q31. I share a positive experience with a brand or a product/service on social media channels.

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree		10.00%	1
Agree		40.00%	4
Somewhat agree		10.00%	1
Neither agree nor disagree		20.00%	2
Somewhat disagree		0.00%	0
Disagree		20.00%	2
Strongly disagree		0.00%	0
	Answered		10
	Skipped		3

Q32. I share a negative experience with a brand or a product/service on social media channels.

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree		30.00%	3
Agree		30.00%	3
Somewhat agree		10.00%	1
Neither agree nor disagree		10.00%	1
Somewhat disagree		0.00%	0
Disagree		20.00%	2
Strongly disagree		0.00%	0
	Answered		10
	Skipped		3

Q33. I buy a product that is recommended by a friend or family member.

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree		20.00%	2
Agree		60.00%	6
Somewhat agree		20.00%	2
Neither agree nor disagree		0.00%	0
Somewhat disagree		0.00%	0
Disagree		0.00%	0
Strongly disagree		0.00%	0
	Answered		10
	Skipped		3

Q34. I buy a product that is recommended by social

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	10.00%	1
Agree	20.00%	2
Somewhat agree	40.00%	4
Neither agree nor disagree	30.00%	3
Somewhat disagree	0.00%	0
Disagree	0.00%	0
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
	Answered	10
	Skipped	3

Q35. I buy a product that is recommended by an expert.

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	0.00%	0
Agree	30.00%	3
Somewhat agree	50.00%	5
Neither agree nor disagree	20.00%	2
Somewhat disagree	0.00%	0
Disagree	0.00%	0
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
	Answered	10
	Skipped	3

Q36. I buy a product that is recommended through consumer-generated content.

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	10.00%	1
Agree	60.00%	6
Somewhat agree	30.00%	3
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0
Somewhat disagree	0.00%	0
Disagree	0.00%	0
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
	Answered	10
	Skipped	3

Q37. I am loyal to only few particular brands.

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	20.00%	2
Agree	30.00%	3
Somewhat agree	20.00%	2
Neither agree nor disagree	10.00%	1
Somewhat disagree	0.00%	0
Disagree	20.00%	2
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
	Answered	10
	Skipped	3

Q38. I enjoy gathering brand information on social media networks.

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	20.00%	2
Agree	50.00%	5
Somewhat agree	10.00%	1
Neither agree nor disagree	10.00%	1
Somewhat disagree	0.00%	0
Disagree	10.00%	1
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
	Answered	10
	Skipped	3

Q39. I usually search for information about international brands on social media channels.

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	30.00%	3
Agree	40.00%	4
Somewhat agree	20.00%	2
Neither agree nor disagree	10.00%	1
Somewhat disagree	0.00%	0
Disagree	0.00%	0
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
	Answered	10
	Skipped	3

Q40. It's easy to get the most recent information regarding brand information on social channels.

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	30.00%	3
Agree	50.00%	5
Somewhat agree	20.00%	2
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0
Somewhat disagree	0.00%	0
Disagree	0.00%	0

Strongly disagree		0.00%	0
	Answered		10
	Skipped		3

Q41. I use social media channels to compare the products.

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree		10.00%	1
Agree		70.00%	7
Somewhat agree		20.00%	2
Neither agree nor disagree		0.00%	0
Somewhat disagree		0.00%	0
Disagree		0.00%	0
Strongly disagree		0.00%	0
	Answered		10
	Skipped		3

Q42. I use social media channels to read product reviews.

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree		20.00%	2
Agree		80.00%	8
Somewhat agree		0.00%	0
Neither agree nor disagree		0.00%	0
Somewhat disagree		0.00%	0
Disagree		0.00%	0
Strongly disagree		0.00%	0
	Answered		10
	Skipped		3

Q43. My friends and colleagues usually tag me on the brand's post that has useful information.

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree		0.00%	0
Agree		40.00%	4
Somewhat agree		20.00%	2
Neither agree nor disagree		0.00%	0
Somewhat disagree		0.00%	0
Disagree		40.00%	4
Strongly disagree		0.00%	0
	Answered		10
	Skipped		3

Q44. I get better product comparisons on social media sites.

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree		10.00%	1
Agree		40.00%	4
Somewhat agree		30.00%	3
Neither agree nor disagree		10.00%	1
Somewhat disagree		0.00%	0
Disagree		10.00%	1
Strongly disagree		0.00%	0
	Answered		10
	Skipped		3

Q45. I like to stay in touch with brands through social media channels.

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree		0.00%	0

Agree	60.00%	6
Somewhat agree	40.00%	4
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0
Somewhat disagree	0.00%	0
Disagree	0.00%	0
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0

Answered	10
Skipped	3

Q46. It saves me time to contact and respond to brands through social media.

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	20.00%	2
Agree	60.00%	6
Somewhat agree	10.00%	1
Neither agree nor disagree	10.00%	1
Somewhat disagree	0.00%	0
Disagree	0.00%	0
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0

Answered	10
Skipped	3

Q47. I prefer to know about new brands and products through social media.

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	10.00%	1
Agree	80.00%	8
Somewhat agree	0.00%	0
Neither agree nor disagree	10.00%	1
Somewhat disagree	0.00%	0
Disagree	0.00%	0
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0

Answered	10
Skipped	3

Q48. I prefer to know other people opinions in regards to a new brand's product or services.

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	30.00%	3
Agree	70.00%	7
Somewhat agree	0.00%	0
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0
Somewhat disagree	0.00%	0
Disagree	0.00%	0
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0

Answered	10
Skipped	3

Q49. I prefer to read users reviews of a new product/service on social media channels.

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Responses
Strongly agree	30.00%	3
Agree	50.00%	5
Somewhat agree	20.00%	2
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0
Somewhat disagree	0.00%	0

Disagree	0.00%	0
Strongly disagree	0.00%	0
Answered		10
Skipped		3

Q50. Social media channels show the true image of a brand.

Answer Choices	I strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	I strongly agree	Total	Weighted Average
1	1	1	1	5	0	0		2	4
								10	10
								3	3

Q51. It is easy to contact brands on social sites

Answer Choices	I strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	I strongly agree	Total	Weighted Average
1	0	1	3	1	1	0		4	4.8
								10	10
								3	3

Q52. Brands respond to me quickly and efficiently on social sites.

Answer Choices	I strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	I strongly agree	Total	Weighted Average
1	2	0	4	1	0	0		3	3.9
								10	10
								3	3

Q53. interacting with International brands through social media makes me feel comfortable and more engaged.

Answer Choices	I strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	I strongly agree	Total	Weighted Average
1	2	0	1	2	2	0		3	4.4
								10	10
								3	3

Q54. consumer reviews on the products on social sites provide a true image of a product.

Answer Choices	I strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	I strongly agree	Total	Weighted Average
1	2	0	1	1	3	0		3	4.5
								10	10
								3	3

Q55. Consumer-generated content video on social sites provides in-depth information about the

Answer Choices	I strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	I strongly agree	Total	Weighted Average
1	2	0	1	1	2	0		4	4.7
								10	10
								3	3

Q56. I get discounts and offers on branded products on social channels.

Answer Choices	I strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	I strongly agree	Total	Weighted Average
1	1	1	2	1	2	1		2	4.3
								10	10
								3	3

Q57. I found myself sharing my opinion about international brands and products with other experts especially with some celebrities on social

Answer Choices	I strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	I strongly agree	Total	Weighted Average
1	2	0	4	2	0	1		10	3.5
								Answered	10
								Skipped	3

Q58. I gained a sense of happiness from engaging with brands through social media.

Answer Choices	I strongly agree	2	3	4	5	6	I strongly disagree	Total	Weighted Average
1	1	1	1	3	0	2		10	4.4
								Answered	10
								Skipped	3

Q59. I pass my time away by engaging with brands on social media.

Answer Choices	I strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	I strongly agree	Total	Weighted Average
	1						1	2	3.5
		4						10	
			0	2	0	1	1		
								Answered	10
								Skipped	3

Q60. I trust brands by engaging with them through social sites.

Answer Choices	I strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	I strongly agree	Total	Weighted Average
	1							2	3.8
		3						10	
			0	2	1	1	1		
								Answered	10
								Skipped	3

Q61. I would like to purchase more from a brand's product if they continue to involve me in social media activities and interactions.

Answer Choices	I strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	I strongly agree	Total	Weighted Average
	1							2	4.2
		1						10	
			1	2	2	1	1		
								Answered	10
								Skipped	3

Q62. Engaging through social media with brands improve loyalty

Answer Choices	I strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	I strongly agree	Total	Weighted Average
	1							2	4.4
		2						10	
			0	1	2	1	2		
								Answered	10
								Skipped	3